

**An investigation of the impact of destination marketing on
tourist satisfaction: A case of Pakistan tourism industry.**

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Acknowledgements

First and foremost, I would like to thank my mother who has been there for me through thick and thin. I want to say thank you to my closest friends who have been my light in the darkest of times. I would also like to thank my father for being an inspiration and being present in spirit, my achievements are dedicated to him and I owe him a great deal.

Abstract

Tourism is a well-known business concept worldwide, however, extremely underrated and underexplored in Pakistan. A country plagued with terrorism is how Pakistan is seen as in most Western countries in the world. Pakistan is home to 8 out of world's 20 highest mountain peaks. Not only that, it has some of the best preserved world heritage sites, beaches, cultural and religious monuments and mouth-watering food. Then why is it that Pakistan isn't on people's mind when they plan a trip? Is it just bad marketing or is it that the country really is what the media says? There are many questions that need answering in order to get to the bottom of this issue. For instance, Maldives derives 32% of its GDP from tourism alone, Macau gets 50% of their GDP from tourism and Aruba 32%.

This research contains primary and secondary research, primary research in form of face-to-face and online interviews as well as survey questionnaires. Secondary research in form of literature review. This study used survey questionnaires as the source of collecting data from 339 respondents that were handed out to people within various settings to ensure a good mix of backgrounds used to gain different perceptions. The questionnaire responses were analysed using the SPSS statistical software, then quantified and scrutinised. In addition to quantitative research, semi-structured interviews of 10 tourism providers were conducted, the goal behind the interviews was to gain understanding of tourism ins and outs from the perspective of business owners and employees. This type of research is called 'mixed-method' research, and mixed-method research helped in determining the core issues facing the tourism industry in Pakistan.

The findings of this research produced very useful information for the local businesses as well as tourism decision makers for various touristic spots within Pakistan. The findings

indicate that most people who have visited Pakistan, for leisure purposes, have thoroughly enjoyed their visits, however, there are some issues that still need to be addressed. As per the findings it is essential that tourism providers focus on providing a range of recreational activities, take measures to ensure their customers feel safe during their visit, and work on providing a generally pleasurable tour, the local authorities should ensure that the main tourist attraction locations in the country have impeccable facilities as the research below indicates that word-of-mouth marketing is perhaps the most influential forms of marketing.

The findings of this study can be used by tourism providers and local tourism businesses to successfully establish a sustainable business. These findings have practical uses for marketers, business owners, local tourism representatives as well as future researchers. This study can be used as a stepping stone to further research within the field of destination brand and destination marketing.

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1. Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1. Introduction

Tourism industry is a catalyst in bringing socio-economic wellbeing to the masses, particularly in the developing countries. It is a branch of the service sector which can bring a substantial influx of foreign visitors to both developed and developing countries. Tourism in developing Asian countries is a powerful means to attract foreign exchange and boost the local economy. It brings foreign investment, creates jobs for locals and promotes sales of local specialities. Pakistan is an example of a developing country which can become an important destination for international tourists with its unique attractions. To make tourism successful, Pakistan must take advantage of the opportunities for tourism development, using marketing and promotional activities.

The purpose of this study is to analyse the current situation of tourism industry in Pakistan and to also evaluate the marketing tactics that are utilised by tourist operators in the country. One of the greatest strengths of the tourism industry in Pakistan is its rich culture, heritage and diversity in terms of ethnic population and their traditions, which is a lucrative attraction for not just foreign but local tourists as well. The downside however weighs out the positives of this particular industry in Pakistan, although the nature of those weaknesses can be changed through strategic implementations. For instance, Pakistan possesses stunningly natural beauty as well as a myriad of historic exquisiteness. Influx in tourism can lead to a greater economy as witnessed by various nations globally, that rely solely on their ability to host millions of tourists yearly. According to the World Travel and Tourism Council, tourism contributed to 9.3% (PKR 342.9bn, 10bn GBP) of total investments in the country in 2015 (WTTC, 2015). It is predicted that those contributions

will rise by 7.6% per annum by the year 2026, achieving a whopping PKR 729.7bn (21bn GBP)

There are currently many tourist and destination providers in Pakistan and their main target audience is the local population of Pakistan. The marketing tactics employed by those organisations are successful to an extent but somewhat fail to attract international tourists, one of the main reasons behind lack of international tourism is the political situation of the country. However, since 2010 the tourism figures have improved significantly, and people are far more open to visiting Pakistan than in the early 2000's. To be able to attract foreign visitors, these organisations need to reach out to those people through various means of marketing. This study will examine how tour operators and travel agents across Pakistan promote their business to the masses, what challenges they are faced with and how they overcome obstacles to make their organisation known.

The basis of this study is the tourism industry of Pakistan, wherein the destination marketing as well as tourist satisfaction concepts will be analysed. The current marketing practices employed by tourism developers and providers will be examined and analysed. The affect of destination marketing on tourist satisfaction will be assessed. The primary goal is to find shortcomings that have not been found by any other researcher and suggest recommendations based on those findings. This research will intend to leave room for future research.

1.2. Overview of main goals/research aim

Tourism is one of the biggest industries in the world, people are keen to travel and explore different countries and environments and take risks. Tourism plays a vital role in development of a country's economy, infrastructure and brings in many socio-economic advantages. Tourism has many advantages for a country, for instance; for a country to attract tourists infrastructure standards should be of global standards, this makes

appropriate authority to make positive changes to local infrastructure. Tourism brings financial prospects for local communities and businesses. One of the best advantages of tourism is that it creates a lot of job opportunities for locals. Although tourism has been a subject of extensive research in the last century, Pakistan tourism industry has been researched very little due to political and economic factors. A lack of research in the field has left a major gap in literature based on Pakistan tourism industry and thus is a research subject with vast potential. However, filling the gap in literature will take time due to the immensity of the gap.

The goal of this study, as stated in research objective, is to analyse factors that affect destination marketing and tourist satisfaction in Pakistan. The tourism industry has recently experience an influx in tourist figures, however, in comparison to countries of similar caliber, Pakistan is far behind. It is, therefore, essential to investigate the causes that prevent the industry's success. Once primary and secondary researches have been conducted and findings have been analysed, recommendations could be made to improve the current situation.

1.3. Main research question

What are the internal and external environmental factors that affect destination marketing in Pakistan and what can tourism providers do to achieve tourist satisfaction?

1.4. Research objectives

- 1. To investigate the relationship between destination marketing and tourist satisfaction in context of Pakistan tourism industry.**
- 2. To investigate the current destination marketing practices employed by tourism providers in Pakistan.**

- 3. To provide strategic recommendations to enhance business performance to ensure high levels of tourist satisfaction.**

1.5. Research questions

- 1. What is the relationship between destination marketing and tourist satisfaction in the context to Pakistan tourism industry?**
- 2. What are the current destination marketing practices employed by Pakistan tourism providers?**
- 3. What strategic recommendations can be provided to enhance business performance to ensure high level of tourist satisfaction?**

1.6. Research problem

A research problem can be defined as a statement about a specific area of concern, difficulty, or a gap in literature that will be addressed through a study (McCombes, 2020). In social sciences, sometimes a research problem is presented as a question. Research problem could help solve a practical issue or aim to add to theory to expand knowledge. It is fundamental to have a clear idea of research problem when deciding to undertake a research project, to avoid ending up with an unfocused study. A clear and concise research problem statement will help make research objectives achievable. It should be noted that a research problem statement does not depict how to solve the problem in question, it is merely an explanation of the issue at hand (Costellanos, 2008).

One of the biggest issues Pakistan faces is the distorted image of the country in mainstream international media. As a result of which, the tourism industry has experienced a loss for a number of years now. The tourism industry and destinations in Pakistan see a very small number of international tourists, which has resulted in a lack of diversity. There are many

reasons as to why that could be damaging to a country's economy. Internal tourism has been the only hope and source of income of tourism developers and providers in the last two decades. Critical issues such as safety threat and political instability have done irreversible damage to Pakistan's image and to the tourism industry to some extent. Despite the issues, it has been noted that the number of international tourists has gone up slightly in the last half decade. However, the rise in those number is gradual and low. Destinations such as the Swat Valley and parts of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa region of Pakistan were previously restricted due to insurgency and safety issues. However, according to recent reports those areas are free of such activities and considered the safest in the country. The issue now is that, it isn't well publicised that many destination are safe and secure for visitors and therefore the tourism situation stays almost the same as before. The marketing and promotion strategies of those destinations need a clear direction in which to proceed to allow for success. Awareness among the masses is the key to getting visitors thinking about the destinations.

Considering the problem statement, it can be assumed that there is gap in knowledge regarding the issue being discussed. This research aims to highlight the issues that cause the problem by surveying and interviewing different types of stakeholders. Once the findings have been analysed, strategic recommendations can be made. Through exiting data and literature it is evident that, there is a strong need for promotions of destinations in Pakistan. tourism brings about many positive changes for local community, local businesses and local government. There are certain countries in the world that rely solely on tourism for their economies and tourism does have the potential to bring about a steady cashflow. In the case if Pakistan, tourism industry was in decline for a few year but has been growing recently. It is quite challenging to predict what the future of tourism would be if appropriate investments are not made. First world countries such as the UK, Canada, New Zealand and the United States have had extensive research into tourism and destination marketing and have the means to do so. However Pakistan is a developing country in a developing continent and therefore, can not be compared with those countries

due to different micro-structures and market characters (JTB, 2005). This research intends to examine the internal and external factors that affect destination marketing and tourism industry in Pakistan. the study will present several researches based on tourism marketing and will develop a conceptual framework and hypotheses to be tested later against data findings.

There is also a lack of literature and research on tourism industry of Pakistan due to various reasons, the country has been politically and socially unstable in the past and has been distant from the globe due to the unstable nature of economy. This research is designed to scrutinise the marketing practices of various potentially successful tourism organisations and destinations and assess the level of tourist satisfaction.

1.7. Research gap

Marketing and Tourism are subjects that are widely researched by researchers, scholars and business managers worldwide. Tourism marketing has revolutionised with social media platforms, people can look up destinations from the comfort of their homes and decide if they want to visit that place by looking at pictures and reviews. It is therefore essential that tourism providers invest in a marketing budget and advertise their products and services. As stated above, the literature relating Pakistan's tourism industry is, at best, mediocre and limited. It can be presumed that it is due to little interest of foreign tourists in the region and perhaps because Pakistan is a developing country and does not have the means to allocate this responsibility to anyone. The gap in literature is an opportunity to delve deep into the tourism segment and find answers to unaddressed questions.

1.8. Research Contributions

Tourism can be a source of revenue and can aid tremendously in improving a country's trade position (Faulkner, 1992). Various governments around the world have taken steps to enhance their position in the global tourism market. Committees and organisations focused mainly on tourism have been set up most countries to come up with effective ways to promote their destinations. Therefore, it can be said that tourism's significance can be measured by its contributions to a country's economy. The growth of the industry globally has been extraordinary over the last 40 years and according to the World Tourism Organisation, tourism is now the largest industry in the world. Travel and Tourism's direct contributions to worldwide GDP were US2.9 billion alone in 2019. United States was the largest contributor with US580.7 million (Lock, 2019).

The research anticipates to outline the challenges faced by local tourism providers in destinations in Pakistan and in doing so, also highlight the issues facing tourism industry as a whole in the country. Since the literature on the subject is limited, this study will not only add to existing research but also help future researchers further explore Pakistan's tourism industry as it seems to be heading into a positive growth direction. The issues to look out for are challenges faced by tourism developers and tourism providers, those challenges could be external factors as well as internal.

1.9. Significance of research

Problem statement can help identify the exact contribution of the study, it can be derived by observing a one to one correspondence between the problem statement and significance of the study. It is also essential to recognise the importance of the study to the society as well as individuals including the researcher.

This research is significant to a range of people as well as an immense segment of local businesses. It intends to leave a gap for future researchers to make significant contributions in the coming years. The field of tourism marketing does not get the attention it requires specifically with regards to Pakistan. Pakistan has a lot to offer to tourists from all round

the world but due to the political and social situation in the past two decades has affected the industry for the worst. The situation seems to be gradually improving and there has been a steady incline in tourist figures. The importance of this research is answered by the objectives of the research, it is essential to investigate the relationship between destination marketing and tourist satisfaction to find out ways to enhance the satisfaction levels.

1.10. Dissertation Structure

- Introduction:

This chapter overviews the aims and objectives of this research. The chapter provides readers with the reason as to why this research is being conducted. It also provides a brief excerpt of relevant facts and figures of the tourism industry of Pakistan and states the significance and contribution of this study.

- Literature Review:

Literature review is perhaps the most significant part of any research as it goes through past and present theories on the subject. Literature review helps researchers develop their own theories. This chapter will look at past and current literature on a number of topics; tourism, tourist satisfaction, marketing, destination marketing and development. The purpose is to analyse theories on the three core subjects of this study, the chapter is divided into two parts, first; tourism theories are analysed and tourist satisfaction literature is discussed extensively. The second part of literature review explores marketing, which is a broad topic therefore only the relevant forms of it will be discussed (relationship, social media, web-based, work-of-mouth, recommendations) to avoid going off-topic.

- Conceptual Framework:

Conceptual framework is an analytical tool used to organise ideas and gather a broad understanding of a phenomenon. It is used mainly to explain the relationships between variables in a research. Conceptual framework chapter in this research presents a theory

based on the potential relationship independent and dependant variables, dependant variable being tourist satisfaction.

- **Methodology:**

A research method is a systematic plan for conducting research. Sociologists draw on a variety of both qualitative and quantitative research methods, including experiments, survey research, participant observation, and secondary data. Quantitative methods aim to classify features, count them, and create statistical models to test hypotheses and explain observations. Qualitative methods aim for a complete, detailed description of observations, including the context of events and circumstances. Methodology chapter of this research explains in detail the theories and approaches used to collect data and analyse findings. It also explains and justifies the methods used to perform empirical research. Two main types of primary data collected were through survey questionnaires and formal interviews. Surveys were used for tourists who had visited Pakistan, and tourist operators were interviewed to get a balanced view of both sides. Secondary research was extensively conducted as it is essential to include researches performed in the past.

- **Data Analysis and Findings:**

This chapter will analyse the collected data; quantitative research will be analysed using SPSS software to get accurate results. Qualitative research will be analysed using the thematic analysis method. The findings will be discussed in detail and linked to the conceptual framework proposed.

- **Conclusion and Recommendations:**

This chapter will draw conclusions and summarise the whole study. This chapter will also provide the researcher with an opportunity to make strategic recommendations to issues that are identified in the discussions chapter.

1.11. Conclusion

The introduction chapter gave an overview of the problem of the research, and the structure this study will follow. As with most research projects, this study will go over existing literature to establish a conceptual framework, which will help in forming dependant and independant variables, and eventually a theoretical framework will developed. The below chapter will be introducing Pakistan, it's economy and it's current tourism practices.

2. Tourism in Pakistan

This chapter is solely focused on providing information on Pakistan's tourism industry. This chapter will enlist the organisations currently working to promote tourism in the country as well as the main touristic attractions that can be promoted further to boost tourism based revenue in Pakistan. this chapter will also discuss the issues the tourism industry has faced in the past and faces to this day, for instance the impact Covid-19 had on the ecomony of Pakistan, and in particular the tourism industry.

2.1. Introduction

Pakistan, officialy known as Islam Republic of Pakistan, is a country in South-East Asia. It is one of the most populated countries in the world, with a population of over 200 multiethnic people. Pakistan separated from India in 1947 after both countries gained independence from the British Empire, it has since struggled with attaining political, and sometimes social, instability (Ziring, 2021). Islamabad is the capital of Pakistan, while Karachi is it's largest city, which is located on the coast of the Arabian Sea.

Pakistan has a great potential touristically due to its rich heritage and culture, ethnic and geographical diversity, and eventful history (Iqbal et al, 2018). Pakistan has a diverse

population which results in cultural diversity, every ethnicity has their own language and customs. It has quite a few archeological sites from thousands of years ago. It has a myriad of other attractions such as world renowned high mountain peaks, beaches, lakes, scenic views and a host sports and adventure activities.

Although it can be argued that despite possessing the natural gems as stated above, the infrastructure and government handling of tourism has let the tourism industry down (Shahbaz, 2018). Ahmed and Anwar(2016) conclude, in their research regarding impacts of terrorism and infrastructure on tourism, that infrastructure is significant in all stages of tourism, both long and short term. On the other hand, terrorism also impacts a country's tourism industry but the effects are relatively short term as compared to infrastructural inadequacy.

Loayza and Wada (2012) state that although infrastructure in Pakistan has improved gradually over the last five decades, it still has a long way to go. Other similar countries, for instance Sri Lanka, Egypt and Malaysia, have excelled at a much faster pace in shorter amount of time and now host millions of tourists a year. Transport sector in Pakistan is significantly unsatisfactory, with low density of paved road, poor quality rail lines and airports. One major issue is electricity outage, electricity is cut off everyday for several hours, which has a negative impact not only on tourism operators but also other local businesses. On the plus side the telecommunication industry has performed really well as compared to countries such as Sri Lanka and Egypt. Mobile phone industry is very active and internet penetration has improved drastically in last two decades.

Loayza and Wada suggest that if Pakistan were to improve and match their infrastructure to the same level of Malaysia, it would see a 3.7% increase in GDP per capita with variable assistance from telecommunications, electricity and transport sectors.

According to an article written in The Economist (2017) Pakistan Government continues to build new road, airports and railways when existing ones are hardly in use. Pakistan's first motorway was built 22 years ago, barely any traffic can be seen along the 223 miles stretch between Islamabad and Lahore, two major and highly populated cities in the

country. There simply is not a major need for any more motorways in Pakistan, that money would be better suited to fix the electricity crisis that has been plaguing the country since 1990s. Pakistan's energy crisis is a complicated matter, it has more to do with leaderships' hesitance to implement unpopular changes rather than that is pure supply. This originated from, then absence of a robust energy strategy, lack of revenue to support generation of electricity which in turn results in low liquidity for Pakistan weak economy as well as leaderships' reluctance to enforce certain changes due to fear of public backlash. To solve the energy crisis would be a big step toward fixing the frail economy which requires strong political drive, abundance of funding, and new energy producing sources.

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Figure 1. International Tourist Arrival-Pakistan (Source: World Bank Data)

According to the World Bank, 1.6 million international arrivals landed in Pakistan, a significant rise from the previous year (907,000). However, the figures went down again in 2012, where only 966,000 international arrival landed in the country. The figures have been fluctuating, the PTDC reported that over 1.7 million tourists visited Pakistan in 2017, out of which 30% were domestic travellers (Dawn.com, 2018). The challenge with these statistics is that it is difficult to distinguish the actual number of tourists from the number of overseas Pakistani visiting their family and friends. It is difficult to present accurate figures due to lack of statistics. A report by WTTC shows that 30% of inbound arrivals, in

2019, were from the UK, 16% from the USA, 8% from India, 8% from China and 33% from the rest of the world (2020).

Tourism has a positive impact on a country's economic condition. In developing countries globally, tourism contributes towards income generation, foreign exchange earnings and employment. The level of impact tourism has on an economy depends upon a country's unique characteristics (Lemma, 2014). A study shows there is a positive relationship between sustainable tourism development and economic growth (Hussain et al, 2019). Tourism has played a significant role in Pakistan's economy, 1 out of 4 jobs were created by the tourism industry in the last five years. In 2019, travel and tourism contributed 5.9% towards the national GDP and currently employs 6.2% of the total population (WTTC, 2020).

2.2. Tourism Organisations & Committees in Pakistan

2.2.1. Pakistan Tourism Development Corporation

Pakistan Tourist Development Corporation also known as PTDC is the official tourism development organisation of Pakistan, it is a semi private body established by the federal government. Their vision is to make the growth of tourism sector a priority through a sustainable approach, to considerably improve quality of life in the country whilst promoting Pakistan's culture and rich heritage. PTDC states that their main mission is to construct a welcoming environment for country's tourism industry by providing world class facilities that correspond with the rich cultural heritage, exceptional archeological history and exquisite scenic beauty by coordinating between public and private sector to create a friendly image of Pakistan, all the while, preserving the country's rich culture.

PTDC states that their main goals are to project a tourist friendly persona. And market their products and services in tourist generating markets. They strive to work on development

of much needed infrastructures and facilities within the country, specifically in tourist destinations. They intend to create a space to encourage private sector organisations to work with the local government in promoting tourism successfully. PTDC's Managing Director Syed Intikhab Alam formed National Tourism Strategy (2020-2030) coupled with a 5 year action plan (2020-2025) which will direct the tourism sector in the following years. To ensure tourists receive exceptional customer service, an initiative titled National Minimum Standards was also put in place ((Pakistan Tourism Development Coporation, 2021). PTDC currently owns several motels and hotel in North and South Pakistani. Most of those motels and hotels are majorly owned by the PTDC while a small number of shares belong to private sector businesses. PTDC also owns Pakistan Tours Ltd which organises tours and provides other touristic services and product to national and international customers.

PTDC management consists of it's board of directors, at a maximum 22 directors can be on the board. The minister in-charge if the Ex-Officio Chairman and the Secretary Incharge is the Vice Chairman of the Board. Managing Director is the Chief Executive and also Principal Reporting Officer to the board.

Key Personnel of Pakistan Tourism Development Corporation

Sayed Zulfiqar Abbas Bukhari	Chairman
Mr Awn Chaudry	Advisor to PM on Sports and Tourism
Mr Aftab ur Rahman Rana	Managing Director
S Mr .W.A Jaffery	PS to Advisor on Sports and Tourism
Mr. Ashfaq Ahmad	General Manager (Motels

Mr. Adil Zaidi	Manager (Finance & Accounts)
Ms. Sadia Nauman	Manager (Publicity & Promotion)
Mr. Mukhtar Ali	Manager (Tourist Information Centers)
Mr. Muhammad Asif	Manager (Admin & Personnel)
Mr. Muhammad Shabbir	Assistant Engineer (Planning & Development)

Figure 2. Key Personnel of PTDC (own table)

2.3. Types of Tourism

2.3.1. Religious Tourism

Yeoman explains that religious tourism involves visiting a place of sacred value such as a shrine or a building of worship for satisfaction. Religious traveling is about people experiencing their beliefs in a location sacred to their religion (Kasim, 2011). People in Pakistan belong to four major religions; Islam, Hinduism, Sikhism, Christianity, and Buddhism. Pakistan is also the birthplace of Sikh faith, therefore, some regions in Punjab are considered highly sacred by Sikhs all around the world.

One of the main sites is Gurdwara Nankana Sahib, it is the most sacred site for people of Sikh faith as it is the birthplace of Baba Guru Nanak, founder of the faith. Each year, around 6000 Sikh people from other countries visit the temple. Kartar Pur is a town located in Narowal district in Punjab. It is known to have been founded by the first Sikh Guru, Guru Nanak and also for establishing the first Sikh commune in 1504 AD. It is the second most sacred site for Sikh pilgrims. In 2019, Pakistan's Prime Minister inaugurated the opening of a cross-border known as Kartarpur Corridor which allows Indian Sikhs to visit the site without a visa. On the very first day of inauguration, 500 people visited the site from

neighbouring India. Kartar Pur Corridor is estimated to make 5.55 billion Pakistani rupees a year, 15.574 million rupees a day (Trips.pk, 2020). Another architectural wonder is the Gurdwara Darbar Sahib in Kartar Pur, which was built to commemorate the death of Sikhism founder Guru Nanak. It is also a sacred site for the followers of Guru Nanak as that is the spot where he is said to have taken his last breath.

Takht-i-Bahi Monastery is an archaeological site located in Mardan, KPK region. Pakistan has a rich Buddhist history as many monks over the centuries passed by the region and some set up their temples. Recently, a 48 feet long Buddha statue has been discovered in Haripur, it is considered to be one of the oldest sleeping Buddha in Buddhist history. Over the decades, different government authorities have been able to keep the site well-preserved.

Katas Raj Mandir is a complex of many sacred Hindu temples. It is 1500 years old and considered sacred as Lord Shiva cried and his tears dropped into the pond within the Temples thus making it a must visit for Hindus. There are 19 structures within the complex however some of them have not been well-maintained. The government began restoration works to help preserve every part of the temple. In 2018, Pakistan government issues 139 visas for Indian Hindu pilgrims to visit Katas Raj Temples (Outhwaite, 2019).

Hinglaj Mata Mandir is a Hindu temple, it is known for commemorating a Hindu Goddess Hinglaj Mata. For devotees of Goddess Hinglaj Mata, it is considered to be of high importance to visit the temple. It is located in the middle of Hingol National Park in the Lasbela District of Balochistan. Many Pakistani Hindus visit the site every day, recently there has been a significant development in roads leading to the area which has made religious tourism to the location easily accessible.

There are many Sufi shrines in Pakistan as over the centuries, many Sufi saints and 'peers' lived and spread the message of peace and tranquility. The shrines such as Data GanjBaksh in Lahore, Lal Shahbaz Qalandar in Sindh, Baba Fariduddin Ganj Shakar in Pakpattan are visited daily by hundreds of thousands of pilgrims (Rasul et al, 2016).

2.3.2. Cultural Tourism:

Pakistan came into being in 1947 when it gained independence from India and the British Empire. Pakistan as an independent country isn't old but its culture and heritage is thousands of years old. Pakistani culture comes in many different forms, from various ethnicities to languages, literature, arts, poetry, music and clothing. Although the main religion is Islam, Pakistan is much more diverse than the media show it to be, for instance, there is a significant number of people from the Baha'I Faith, Buddhists and Zoroastrianism registered as Pakistani citizens (Ghauri, 2012). There are six major languages that are spoken in Pakistan, however unofficially there are over 75 languages belonging to different ethnic groups. Despite having different languages in each states, almost all Pakistanis understand Urdu, which is the national language of Pakistan. English is widely used in government offices, education institutes and the military. It is also an official language along with Urdu.

Punjab: Punjab is the highest populated province in Pakistan, with a population of over 110 million and is the 2nd largest state area wise. Punjab is renowned for its rich culture, as is evident in its cuisine, language, poetry, dancing, and history. Lahore is Punjab's capital and largest city, it is one of the most populous cities in the world. Lahore has been capital of many dynasties for over 11 centuries, it was once a capital for the Mughal Empire and therefore exhibits Mughal architecture and literature. The Mughal Emperors built many monuments across India, however, the one sin Lahore are most lavishly decorated.

Walled City of Lahore: Walled City of Lahore, also knows as Inner City, is a historic part of the city of Lahore. It was built in 1000 CE by Mughal Emperor Akbar and includes monuments such as Badshahi Mosque, Shalimar Gardens and Lahore Fort.

Badshahi Mosque and Lahore Fort: Badshahi Msoque is a mosque built during the Mughal Era by Aurangzeb in 1671. It is considered one of the most significant and iconic landmarks of Lahore. It is the third biggest mosque of Pakistan and biggest mosque of the Mughal Era. Lahore Fort is located next to the mosque, it was built to protect Lahore from being attacked. Lahore Fort is now a UNESCO world heritage sites. The mosque and the

Fort are located in the ‘Walled City of Lahore’, it was built in 1000 CE and is a location of great interest for tourists.

Shalimar Gardens: Shalimar Gardens, known as Shalimar Bagh in Urdu, are a garden complex built during the Mughal Era. Shalimar Gardens were built to create a sense of utopia where humans exist in perfect peace and harmony. It was built in 1642 during the reign of Shah Jahan, in 1981 they became a UNESCO world heritage site. The Gardens are now a major tourist attraction.

Faisal Mosque: Faisal Mosque, just like the Badshahi mosque, is a major tourist attraction in Pakistan, it is situated in Islamabad. It was built in 1986 and was the largest mosque in the world at the point of completion. It is now the sixth largest mosque in the world. Faisal mosque has the capacity to house 300,000 worshippers.

Rohtas Fort: Rohtas Fort is a 16th century fort situated in Jehlum city in the Punjab province. The Fortress was built on order of Sher Shah Suri, it is known for its beautiful architecture and large walls and has managed to stay intact as it was never attacked. It is also now a UNESCO world heritage site.

Lok Virsa Museum: Lok Virsa is a museum in Islamabad that displays all the living cultures in Pakistan. The museum opened in 1974 and is said to be one of the greatest representations of Pakistani culture.

Derawar Fort: Derawar Fort is a fortress in Ahmadpur Punjab, it was built in the 9th century. It is located in the middle of the Cholistan desert. It is a landmark for Bahawalpur and Cholistan desert. The site is popular with tourists, however, it is noted that the Fortress is in dire need of repairs. It is also reported that it is likely that the fortress is surrounded by various Indus Valley civilisation archaeological sites, that haven't been uncovered yet (Syed, 2011).

Takht-i-Bahi: Takht-i-Bahi is a UNESCO world heritage site located in Mardan, KPK. It is a site of a Buddhist monastery which was founded in the 1st century CE. The site was in use till the 7th century. Seri Bahlol is a city located near Takht-i-Bahi that is also an archeological site and has

Chitral: There are various cultural festivals that take place all across Pakistan. The Kalash people of the Kyber Pakhtunkhwa region have various festivals that are of great interest to local and international tourists due to the unique nature of Kalash traditions and culture. One of the most important Kalash festival is Chilam Joshi, it begins on 13th May and lasts four days. During the festival, men and women meet in hopes of finding a spouse. The people sing and dance and pray for good health and world peace. This festival is a positive and colourful representation of the Kalash culture (thenews.pk, 2016).

Karachi: Karachi is the biggest and highest populated city in Pakistan. It is located in the Sindh province, considered the most progressive city in Pakistan, is also the main business hub. Karachi has the largest seaport in Pakistan through which most trade is performed.

Desert Tourism: Cholistan: Cholistan Desert is one of the largest deserts in the Punjab province of Pakistan. It is well-known among local tourists for its scenic beauty and monuments such as the Derawar Fort. The desert is said to have traces of the ancient Indus Civilisation which dates back to 4000 BCE. Cholistan desert holds the Cholistan Jeep Rally each year which has become an event of interest for motorsports enthusiasts from Pakistan and internationally (Adnan, 2017). The PTDC inaugurated the Cholistan Resort to attract visitors to stay in the region. The resort is a much needed addition as the region lacks in hotels, and general facilities. The main objective of the resort project was to urge tourists to explore the local area which has a lot of tourism potential (TDCP, 2021).

2.3.3. Eco-tourism

As the world population becomes aware of the environment and climate concepts, ecotourism had been blooming. Ecotourism refers to a form of tourism that is environmentally friendly. It involves visitors visiting places that have been free of tourism and are protected. Ecotourism has become an important industry for many developing countries, since it is a great way to bring income while protecting their environment. Ecotourism can be seen as a form to reduce poverty levels, while promoting tourism in a sustainable way. This type of tourism will help bring in capital for local community developments and human rights (Arshad et al, 2017).

Pakistan is a potentially great country for ecotourism as it has some of the best destinations to offer for ecotourism. For instance, the high mountains (Karakoram, the Himalayas and the Hindu Kush), the endless deserts, beaches and shorelines, coniferous and tropical scrub forests, glaciers and diverse flora and fauna, provide endless opportunities for eco-friendly and sustainable tourism. There are 19 mammal orders in the world, out of that 10 are found in Pakistan. Some of them include Blue Whale, The Kashmir Pigmy Shrew (Israr et al, 2009). Wild Boar hunting is another activity that has attracted a few foreign tourists to Pakistan, although it is a highly controversial topic.

2.3.4. Historical and Archeological Tourism

Pakistan is home to several ancient archeologies and is a place of interest for history appreciating tourists. Indus Valley civilisation was a bronze age civilisation that existed in Harappa and Mohenjo-daro. Harappa and Mohenjo-daro are in present day Punjab and Sindh and are 5000 year old deserted cities. Harappa was the main city of Harappan civilisation, which had a population of five million people and existed between the 3rd and 2nd millennium. Harappa and Mohenjo-daro have been well-preserved by various governments over the years and are a point of interest for many tourists (Fakhar, 2010).

Gandhara, present-day Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, is a highly sacred region for Buddhists since it is home to many Buddha statues. Buddhism is deeply embedded in the history of Pakistan as the land that covers Pakistan now, was once a part of a few different Buddhist empires. It is said that Gandhara once was considered one of the most beautiful places in the world, the cities were named differently; Peshawar was known as 'Purushapura', Taxila as 'Takshashila' and Bamyan as 'Varmayana'. This civilisation existed in the 1st millennium BC all the way to the 11th century. Many artifacts were preserved and are displayed in various museums across Pakistan.

For a short period of time in the 16th century, Lahore was made the capital city of the Mughal Empire. The Mughals left Lahore with a great legacy, they build monuments such the Lahore Fort, Badshahi Mosque, Jahangir's Tomb, Nur Jahan's Tomb, Wazir Khan Mosque and many other architectural marvels. The Mughal era also left a great impact on architecture and local cuisines of present-day India and Pakistan. In essence, Pakistan a highly cultured and historic country and has material for everyone's pleasure.

Thatta: Thatta is city in the province of Sindh. In medieval times Thatta was the capital city of many dynasties. Thatta has one of the largest Necropolis known as the Makli Necropolis. It is a UNESCO world heritage site that consists of various monumental funeraries, some of them belonging to famous Sufi saints and royalty. Makli is visited by thousands of people from all over Pakistan and abroad for tourism purposes.

2.3.5. Adventure and Recreational tourism

There are very few places in the world that have the splendour and magnificence that is found in the northern areas of Pakistan. A few of these places are the Swat Valley, the Hunza Valley, Balakot, Chitral, Naran, Kaghan, Malam Jabba, Neelum Valley, Shangla, Deosai, Lake Saiful Maluk, Ayubia and Gilgit Baltistan. Every inch of the area is etched with natural beauty, most of which is untouched. Some other amazing destinations

including the mountains; Himalayas, K2 and the Hindu Kush have incomparable views and are deeply attractive to adventurers (Khalil et al, 2007).

Many tourist operators provide adventure activities in many different destinations. The K2 is a perfect playground for extreme adventure seekers, as it is one of the most difficult and highly dangerous mountains to conquer (Gulwani, 2018). There are several expeditions that are offered as the mountain peaks have different heights. Whitewater Rafting, kayaking and canoeing is a commonly available adventure in rivers of Hunza, Kunar, Gilgit, Swat, Neelum and Chitral. In some places, training courses are available to put adventure junkies at ease, different level of rafting and kayaking are also offered. Cycling through Pakistan is becoming a common practice among foreign tourists, cycling through the mountains of Karakoram is an activity unlike any other and is offered by specialist tour operators. Skiing is offered in spots such as Astore, Naltar, Bruzil, Ratu and Malam Jabba. Skiing resorts are also found in these spots and some places offer skiing lessons. Paragliding and Parasailing are offered in Rajdhani, Rawaal, Pir Chinasi, Chitral and Birmoghlash.

Cholistan Jeep Rally is an event that has taken place since 2005, it is an off-road jeep rally race that takes place in the middle of the Cholistan desert. Over a 100 drivers take part in the race and over 100,000 people witness the events. A rally of 50 bikers and 50 cars left for the official Karachi to Gwadar in efforts to create harmony between Balochistan and other parts of Pakistan. The rally is known as 'Peace rally' since it is an attempt by the government to display a peaceful image of Pakistan. The rally will be held yearly and people will be invited to experience (tribune.com.pk, 2021).

The Deosai Mountain is one of the highest plateaus in the world, it is situated on the boundary of western Himalayas and the Karakoram. Deosai was believed to be haunted for centuries and given the name 'The Land of Giants' perhaps due to the silence that prevails

there. The weather of the region is extremely unpredictable, sometimes in the middle of summer it starts snowing. Due to the existing wildlife and harsh weather, the area is uninhabitable and has therefore remained untouched and has retained its natural glory. The mountains are covered in snow for most part of the year and for a few months, they're covered in a range of beautiful flowers (Bukhari, 2019). Many trekking and skiing sports take place at Deosai mountains

Shandur Polo Festival takes place every year in July on Shandur Pass, it takes place on the world's highest Polo ground at 3700m from the sea level. The polo matches take place between Gilgit-Baltistan and Chitral district teams and are normally free style games. The festival has taken place yearly since 1936 and invites visitors to watch the matches. The festival also arranges for folk music and dancing and sets up village camps for visitors.

2.3.6. Business tourism

China-Pakistan Economic Corridor also known as CPEC is an infrastructural project that is currently under construction throughout Pakistan since 2013. Inadequacies resulting from poor transportation infrastructure are estimated to cause a loss of 3.5% of the total annual GDP. One of the main goals of CPEC are to establish fast and efficient transport networks that will connect ports like Karachi and Gwadar to the northern areas and China's Xinjiang state. This will result in reduction of times and costs of transportation of resources like energy and goods. CPEC has enabled business tourism to a large extent, from architects to engineers to businessmen to government officials are travelling to Pakistan all around the year to work on the project (Rauf, 2018).

2.4. Tourist types

- Local tourists

Local tourists are tourists visiting the destinations from within Pakistan, since Pakistan is an Islamic Republic, the expectations of local tourists differ enormously from international tourists. Since Pakistan is a developing nation with high levels of unemployment, people

look for the cheapest option possible for their vacations. An instance is, many local tourists are offered considerably lower prices compared to their foreign counterparts. This is due to the fact that Pakistan is a lower-middle income country, and that coupled with high unemployment figures, it is unlikely that local tourists are willing to fork out a big sum. As a conservative country, many of the local visitors abide by Islamic laws, such as segregation of sexes in some cases, as well as family friendly activities. Most organisations providing tourist experiences are well equipped in this instance and provide excellent choices for people from within the country.

- **International tourists**

International tourists are essential to any tourism industry in the world, many countries rely on foreign tourists for income and revenue. Pakistan is a country of many cultures, languages and religions, and offers something for everyone. International tourists are generally respectful of local culture, however, due to the conservative nature of the local environment many people are out off the country. International tourists are better suited for tourstic business than local tourists, as international tourists are willing to pay hefty amounts for products and services. It is a well-known fact amongst tourism providers that foreign tourists pay higher amounts as compared to their counterparts. The main issue faced by tourism providers is to provide value for money for foreign tourists, as the expectation are generally much higher than local tourists.

2.5. Worldwide Ranking

The travel and tourism competitiveness report in 2019 ranked Pakistan 121 out of 140 countries. The report considers several factors and policies to asses the tourism and travel sector of a country. It is somewhat of an improvement for Pakistan as the same report ranked Pakistan 124 out of 136 countries in 2017. However, the low ranking still suggests that the development and sustainability of the tourism industry in Pakistan is not up to par. The neighbouring countries have done well in comparison. For instance, the same report

ranked India 34 out of 140 countries, which suggests that India has superior tourism policies in place.

Some of the sector highlighted by the TTCI report suggest Pakistan needs severe improvements. Some of lowest ranked divisions are environmental sustainability, air transport infrastructure, safety and security ICT resources, international openness and prioritisation of travel and tourism, Pakistan ranks in the bottom 20% in those sectors. It did well in the price competitiveness index, which indicates it is an inexpensive country to travel to. It came in top 20% in cultural resources and business travel. It is evident from the statistics above that tourism executives hasn't been performing efficiently in using the strengths of tourism in Pakistan to create a desired destination for worldwide tourists (Calderwood et al ,2019).

2.6. Economy

Pakistan since it's inception in 1947 has always been relatively unstable, politically and socially. Pakistan's economy has been improving as the current government has taken positive steps in order to better the poor economic conditions. There have been new initiatives such as housing schemes for less fortunate, employment opportunities and economic reforms (Uddin, 2018)

In regards to business and international funding, Pakistan's economic freedom score is 54.8 which makes it the 135th freest economy in the world. Pakistan currently score quite low in many economic calculations worldwide, even amongst Asia Pacific countries. This shows that the overall score of Pakistan is very low within various economic indices, however, the growth of cotton exports within the last 5-7 years has shown great potential for further growth, and is a very positive sign towards country's economic development. Although, due to rife corruption across almost all departments and divisions within the government, the economic potential faces hindrance. Nonetheless, it can be said with confidence that the power lies with national and international consumers, and despite all the aforementioned issues Pakistan has managed to attain stable growth level due to credit

agreements with the IMF. Moreover, in the year 2019, the economic growth was expected to fall to 3.3% from 5.5% in 2018 a net 0.7% points lower than the IMF previously estimated. The scholars argue that this occurred due to measures carried out by the authorities to enact the country's macroeconomic imbalances. However, this is also argued that in the upcoming future, growth is anticipated to slow down for 2.4% from the year 2020 till 2022. This is due to the reason that the country is working to sustain a strong monetary and fiscal stance.

Pakistan is one of the richest countries in South Asia, it is seen as a major business hub for many Western and Middle Eastern countries, which is mainly down to its favourable geographical location. Although it is still safe to say that the country is plagued with not only inter-level corruption but also political instability, however, even with all the hindrances the economy has boomed and the GDP is in the process of recovering and is showing signs of constant improvement. Due to the Pakistan being a developing country, the potential and appeal for local and international investment has peaked.

The figure below depicts Pakistan's travel and tourism statistics key points, it can be seen that a contribution of 5.9% of total economy was made by the tourism sector in 2019. The economy benefitted from \$852.2m through international visitors in 2019 alone, and 3,881.9 jobs were created was tourism and travel purposes. The concept of investing in tourism industry is still somewhat new to Pakistan's economy, and even with the lack of focus on tourism and travel the contributions made are substantial. It can be argued that with precautions and further steps taken to improve the tourism industry statistics, the industry can reach new heights.

Fig.3: Key points of Pakistan Tourism Industry (Macro Pakistani, 2021)

2.7. Covid-19

Covid-19 impact on global economy: the impact of covid-19 has been severe on world economies. The deadly virus has reached almost every nation in the world. Due to lockdowns in place in many countries, many people have lost their jobs and business have gone bankrupt. Unemployment is on the rise in countries shown in the table below.

Fig. 4. Global Unemployment (Source: IMF, 2021)

According to the IMF global economy has shrunk 4.4% in 2020 due to covid-19. The decline is said to be the worst one since the Great Depression of the 1930s (Jones et al, 2021). Travel industry has been hit hard by the impact of covid-19, with airlines and most countries cancelling flights and closing off their borders. New variants of the virus are being detected in various countries, which causes further delays in resuming travel activities. Throughout the covid-19 pandemic, the travel and tourism, hospitality and shopping industries have struggled and declined the most. The pharmaceutical companies have been among the winners, with their shares value reaching an all-time high (Jones et al, 2021).

2.7.1. Covid-19 impact on Pakistan

The impact of covid-19 has been just as catastrophic on Pakistani economy as any other economy in the world. The initial impact began in early 2020 when the national airline carrier PIA cancelled flights between China and Pakistan for January. By March the government had imposed stricter restrictions in place by cancelling all flights and closing borders. Covid-19 was first detected in Pakistan in February 2020 and the first lockdown was implemented in March with business and retail closed, travel restrictions

in place and people asked to stay and work from home. The lockdown officially ended in mid May due to the country struggling economically, despite the virus still not being under control. Pakistan International Airlines (PIA) ceased all international flights till July and only a few resuming in August.

Furthermore, the emerging country like Pakistan is attributed by considerable social inequality. A large part of the country live in the slum areas of the cities' outskirts where along with poor health care condition and sanitation, overcrowding is another element that it is almost impossible to implement government policy of "social distancing". A study conducted by Shrestha et al (2020) concluded that majority of Pakistani population was unable to reach clean water i.e., 17% of the total population and around 45% of the sewage produced in the country is preserved by higher authorities.

From all these discussions, it seems evident that hygiene is the key issue in the majority of the areas of Pakistan against which a strict lockdown situation could facilitate people to prevent the spread of disease. Similar to other developing countries like Latin America, the Pakistani health care system ability to enact with the epidemic crisis is extremely limited and as the pandemic placed extra pressure on the existing health care system, the government of Pakistan had to mitigate the influence of COVID-19 on the economy by adopting various measures. The primary provisions included direct and indirect tax measures, steps related to employment and to stimulate economy. Although travel to Pakistan has resumed the government has strict policies in place, where various nationalities are required to present a negative test and quarantine in hotels paid for by travellers.

Conclusion

This chapter provides a detailed account of the current situation of Pakistan's tourism industry. As Pakistan is quite an unexpected tourism destination, and is a developing

country that does not emphasise highly on tourism, the literature and information has been very limited. The information above has been used to generate research questions and objectives, and will further be used to generate questions for the survey questionnaires. Pakistan has an excellent array of tourist destinations, from mountains to temples to desert that spans hundreds of thousands of miles. Pakistan has a rich culture, as the geographical area has been invaded many times by many civilisations and kingdoms from around the world. As a country of over 200 million and many different ethnicities and languages, the country can potentially become one of the most desired tourism destination. However, the question is why is it not? And what steps can be taken to promote the country's excellent collection of natural assets.

3.Literature Review

3.1. Introduction:

This chapter entails extensive literature on many tourism related themes, firstly the chapter delves into tourism, tourism marketing and tourist satisfaction. as this research is based on destination marketing, the literature also explores destination marketing, however to determine the key factors of destination marketing, a review of how destination comes to be and what destination branding is will also be undertaken. A conceptual framework will be developed using the findings of the literature review.

3.2. Tourism

United Nations World Tourism Organisation defines tourism as “Tourism comprises the activities of persons travelling to, and staying in, places outside their usual environment for not than one consecutive year for leisure, business and other purposes” (2004). Tourism a vibrant, ever-changing, customer-focused and on of the largest industries globally, all of it’s components combined under an umbrella would be; traveling, accommodation, food and recreational services. Tourism is an evolving industry that will always be expected to grow, challenging and opportunistic for private and public sectors (Walker, 2004). It was reported by World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC) that in 2017, one in ten jobs was supported by the tourism industry, totaling 313 million jobs globally (2018). Tourism industry is significant for a number of reasons; it creates jobs, helps build a country’s positive image, improves economy and lives of local residents of a destination, increases awareness about different cultures, and encourages communication between different groups of people. Secretary General of the World Tourism Organisation emphasises on the significance of tourism, he states;

"Around the world, in countries at all development levels, many millions of jobs and businesses are dependent on a strong and thriving tourism sector. Tourism has also been a driving force in protecting natural and cultural heritage, preserving them for future generations to enjoy"

Employment created through tourism is important for developing countries such as India as it is a form for income and employment for a sizeable chunk of the population (Huybers, 2007). Choy emphasises significance of tourism by stating that it provides job to those people who would struggle to gain employment in other fields (1995). It is reiterated by Baum (2002), who states that most businesses seek people with higher levels of education and some people with lower levels of education might not secure those jobs, and tourism can become a passage for those people. Therefore, employment in the tourism industry will keep growing. Another advantage brought by tourism is the income generation that comes with employment. Vanegas (2014) states that inflow of money can reduce poverty and that opportunity is provided by tourism in various destinations. The United Nations World

Tourism Organisation (UNTWO, 2018) stresses on importance of tourism for employment, it states that tourism providers and local governments should focus on tourism industry as a means to provide employment and end poverty. Due to the immense success of tourism industry, destinations developers and tourism providers should use tourism as a tool to help less fortunate gain employment and earn stable income (Hadi et al, 2013). Contrarily, some argue that tourism industry in developing countries can use it to their advantage to get workers to work long hours for minimal money, this might discourage people to enter the industry (Weaver, 2009).

Tourism is beneficial for economy as it contributes to economic prosperity (Dwyer, 2010). Economic development as the outcome of tourism results in increased amount of spending, also referred to Gross Domestic Products (GDP). It has a positive affect on success of a tourist destination specifically in developing destinations (Aguilo, 2017). Morales et al (2004) in their study on Latin America found that there was a positive correlation among increase of visitors per capita and their economic gains. Those scholars also suggested that effects on GDP were more paramount on developing nations as compared to developed countries.

3.2.1. Tourism Marketing

Tourism marketing is a segment of marketing wherein organisations use marketing methods to promote their business and attract local and international tourists to a destination. Cities, states, hotels, resorts, and other attractions use marketing strategies to boost their business and increase tourist visits. Tourism market can prove to be costly, specially if tourism providers are looking to attract international visitors. To increase influx of tourists and inflow of cash, private organisation form partnerships with government organisations. For instance, if a destination has several attraction and activities, the whole state could be advertised as a week long holiday destination by combing advertising and

promotion efforts. Such partnerships are good for private and public sector and also visitors, as a visit to the destinations can provide tourists with a funner experience.

Tourism marketing as whole involves attracting potential visitors to a destination without having to recommend accommodation options. Sometimes the destination is so popular that marketers just need to let tourists know of the greatness of the location. An example of that scenario is the city of Las Vegas, the name itself is advertisement enough, tourism developers performed so well in promoting a destination that it is now known worldwide as a city to have a great time. To tourists looking for warm weather and beaches, Florida promises a pleasurable experience, without tourism providers having to market the state.

Tourism marketing strategies can have a remarkable effect on tourist destinations and potential tourism opportunities (Kavaratzis, 2012). Fundamentally, a tourism marketing strategy highly affects the image of a destination (Cousin, 2008). Sometimes, destination image can become politicised and the truth may be far from impartial (Jenkins & Dredge, 2003).

More importantly, tourism marketing as a policy tool directly impacts representation of tourism destinations (Cousin, 2008; Karavatzis, 2012). Therefore, destination identity and perception may become politically motivated and acquired meaning may far be from neutral (Dredge and Jenkins, 2003). As such, various interests may motivate the message put forward in destination positioning statements made in regional tourism marketing.

Marketing grew immensely after world war 2, when it became a scientific discipline in continuos growth. Practice came into place before theories, as organisation providing servces applied different approaches to marketing (Ban, 2002). As marketing grew, tourism marketing started expanding as well. One of the first works on tourism marketing was the 1968 paper 'Marketing y Turismo' by G. Schellenberg, then in 1971 Krippendorf published a paper titled 'Marketing et Tourisme', reporting importance of marketing in

tourism industry. Spain was also one of the first countries to set up a committee with the aim of making tourism the main focus. The committee dealt with tourism related issues and devising marketing strategies (Henche, 2004).

Tourism and marketing, both, are vast subjects and have been researched on extensively. Tourism marketing proved to be essential in 1970's and many scholars started investing their time in research on the subject. Krippendorf (1971) stated that marketing in tourism industry is methodical and organised execution of a business policy by visitors partaking local or international level holiday to achieve optimal satisfaction. Essentially tourism marketing is a process of providing tourism services for profits in return by tourism providers (Krippendorf, 1971). Krippendorf stresses on the significance of organising activities exclusive to tourism, at national and international level. In a similar research, Schwartz (1981) believes that tourism marketing is a process that can fulfil customer needs and wants, and maximise profits for the tourism providers.

Tourism marketing is a system of management, a tool to plan and control activities through a balanced use of available resources, as a mix of procedures providing scientific explorations of the market to alter tourism offers to tourists' want and desires (Berbecaru, 1975). The literature above provided various definitions of tourism marketing, however, they are deemed incomplete as tourism marketing entails much more than that. Gerard & Zins (1987) state that tourism marketing is a process where tourism demand is predicted and eventually satisfied by various elements; product design, physical distribution, exchange value, interaction between consumers and tourism providers in order to fulfil consumers demands. The definition brings in the marketing mix needed to fulfil tourism needs. Tourism marketing is also defined as a process through which tourism organisations categorise current and potential tourist demands, then interact with demand providers to assess tourism needs and desires in order to adjust tourism offers accordingly. This is done to best fulfil tourist demands and desires while maximising business objectives (Balaure et al, 2004). Veres (2005) states that marketers are concerned about classifying service marketing features from marketing of goods.

Tourism marketing and tourism destinations are closely interconnected as without a tourist destination, there will not be tourism marketing. Marketing destinations are a mix of complex networks that involve co-dependant organisations providing a broad range of services and products. Buhalis (2000) supposes that destinations are a combination of tourist products and services, providing tourists with a rewarding experience. Any component of a tourist destination is an asset that can be used to achieve economic gains in a destination (Gonzalez & Falcon, 2003). Developing a tourist destination is a complicated task as tourists now seek feelings and experiences and not be a subject of a tourist tour for financial gains. The main aim of any tourist destination is to entertain it's visitors and to keep them interested with products and services options (Saraga & Ispas, 2011). Federal government plays a vital role in determining international tourism infrastructure by developing suitable tourism strategy (Smith & Moulana, 2008).

Further Tourism marketing theories

The field of tourism marketing encompasses a wide range of topics. In literature from the past few decades, various strategies for promoting tourism have been described. Six key categories can be found in the most recent, state-of-the-art study of tourism marketing, with the option of expanding it to include two additional intersecting sectors (tactical marketing and performance measurement). Consumer behaviour serves as the foundation for tourism marketing, which is then followed by marketing segmentation, targeting, and positioning. Using conventional marketing management tools from non-tourism sectors, the third area can be recognised as the branding strategy and management, and the fourth as the strategic marketing and marketing idea. Marketing communication focused mostly on e-marketing, social marketing, mobile applications, and the internet is a very unique, researched, and used field in tourism marketing.

The field of tourism marketing covers a wide range of topics. Various approaches to tourism marketing can be found in literature of recent decades. The modern, up-to-date review of tourism marketing covers six main areas with the potential to expand it with two more intersectional fields: tactical marketing and performance measurement.

Consumer behaviour is the foundation of tourism marketing. Marketing segmentation, targeting, and positioning are the next steps. The third field is the branding strategy and the branding management. The fourth field is the strategic marketing and the marketing concept using the old marketing management tools from the non tourism sectors.

The very special, researched and used area of tourism marketing is marketing communication based mostly on electronic marketing, social marketing and mobile applications and the internet. Relationship marketing, Experiential marketing, and societal marketing can be summarised in the notion of sustainable tourism marketing.

In general, although tourism marketing has advanced significantly in theory and practice over the past two decades, there is still a large gap in some areas of research. The terminology used varies between research and practice, which uses tourism marketing terminology as it pleases. Important trends in tourism marketing have been taken over from other industries, such as airlines and hotel chains. There is still a gap between research and practice in the private and public (e.g., destination) sectors. Since the 1950s, the scope of marketing approaches in various areas of tourism services has been dependent on international tourism trends and the development of demand and supply shifts respectively. The travel and tourism branch has followed the industrial branches in terms of marketing and application in real life, with a time lag of around 10 – 20 years, depending on the country and sub-sector. Initially, the intentional basic marketing orientation was adopted within the airline and hotel industries, but it was not adopted quickly in the other sectors.

The question of the applicability of marketing principles to the public sector in the context of destination marketing management remains unclear. The history of tourism marketing began with ‘marketing’ focused on the production and sales of goods and services, and later shifted to the social or sustainability orientation of marketing.

One of the big questions in tourism marketing is, what is the first stimulus to sales and consumption? Is it the needs and wants of the consumer, or are there products and services offered by the tourist sub-sector and marketed by the marketer? Traditionally, marketing was defined as ‘the process of conceptualizing, pricing, promoting, and distributing ideas, goods and services to meet individual and organizational goals’. The development of markets and the new outlook on the role of marketing over the past decade can be summarised in Keefe’s (2004) definition:

“Marketing is the process by which an organization creates, communicates, and delivers value to customers” (Keefe, 2004).

This paper provides an overview of the current state of tourism marketing, focusing on the main areas studied in literature, research, and applied in practice. The main objective is to define and analyze the fundamental fields of travel & tourism marketing in the global context, with a focus on the following distinctions: the gap between theory & practice, the gap in marketing in the period up to & after the 90’s driven by ICT development, the gap between marketing in the private travel & tourism sector & the public one (e.g. destination marketing), and the trends & future prospects in travel & tourism marketing. The paper includes four working prerequisites. First, there is a gap between the implementation of general marketing theory in both the travel & tourism industry and the travel & tourism branch. Second, there has been considerable progress in theory & practice in marketing of

destinations, but the level of application of the theory in the private sector is very low (except for hospitality & aviation).

In the last ten years, there has been rapid development of concepts and approaches related to travel and tourism in the areas of social, sustainability, and relationship marketing. In addition, the massive growth of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) in the last ten years has had a significant impact on travel and tourism.

Types of Tourism Marketing and Approaches

Travel and tourism marketing is divided into the following categories and approaches:

1. Public and Private Tourism Marketing
2. Demand and Supply Tourism Marketing
3. Tourism Economy and Tourism Industry Tourism Marketing
4. Tourism Marketing by the Tourism Subsector Including Destination Marketing

Regional Approach by the Continental, National

The main fields of tourism marketing are Economic Psychology, Consumer Behaviour, Choice Modeling and Decision-Making, Service Quality and Satisfaction, Market Segmentation and Travel Patterns, Strategic Marketing, Travel Packaging, Promotions, Advertising and Imaging, and Distribution Channel and Strategic Alliances. Technological Development focuses on Distribution Channel Information Technology Systems, Multimedia, and the Possibility of CRS Implementation or the Role of Database DBM in Tourism. Communication in travel and tourism with a focus on Communication Channels, Communication Effectiveness, and Information Acquisition and Search. The above categories can be expanded from today's perspective to other areas of research and practical use. However, over the past two decades, there have been numerous research studies and practical applications of tourism marketing, with six basic areas summarised in the table

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below.

Figure 5. Themes and Sub-themes of tourism marketing. (Palatková, M, 2012)

The above areas can be complemented by two other fields: firstly, tactical marketing, which focuses on service performance and service quality; secondly, product development and distribution channels; demand models; and pricing; and thirdly, performance measurement, primarily based on measurement of effectiveness and efficiency; destination marketing management; and competitiveness.

Consumer behaviour is the central issue of tourism marketing. Due to the constant changes in economic, social, technical and other fields, the patterns of travel consumer (consumer) behaviour are constantly changing, making consumer behaviour one of the most dynamic and eclectic areas of tourism marketing. A wide range of disciplines, including psychologists, sociology, anthropologists, economists, and marketing, have been used to analyze tourist behaviour.

The fundamental shift in consumer behaviour occurred in the last decade or two as a result of significant changes in the global economy. As a result, the increasing number of tourists from former developing countries (including China, India, and Brazil) and the emerging

economies (China, India, and Vietnam) forced traditional and new destinations and private companies to re-evaluate their traditional marketing processes and tools.

The biggest change in tourism behaviour over the past 20 years has been the development and implementation of ICT in tourism marketing. Other demographic trends (such as ageing populations in developed countries), environmental trends (such as increased preference for soft travel), consumption trends (such as more short-term trips) and others present a challenge for tourism marketing around the world.

According to Leiper (1990), visitors are driven to places where they think their needs will be met. Crompton (1979), push motivating factors are seen as the key factor in understanding visitor behaviour. Pull motivating factors, on the other hand, are seen as the unique characteristics of the destination and/or the company that influence the choice of the destination, the hotel or the travel agent. Baloglu (1996) studied the relationship between push and pull motivations, which were later used in various studies mainly focused on the choice of destination or tourist product (Matzler (2003), Correia (Oom do Valle) and Moço (2007), Pesonen (Komppula), Kronenberg and Peters (2011).

Once the destination choice is complete, push and pull motivations are linked to specific destinations. In some cases, the tourism motivations can be a barrier to the loyalty to the destination or company choice. Some consumers like novelty, change and a new experience.

The motivations of tourists are influenced by their personality traits (pleasure-seekers, impulsives, self-confident, people-oriented and others) and by their psychology.

Plog (2001) defines two personality profiles:

Psychocentric (loyalty) with greater loyalty and

Alocentric (voluntourism) with reduced loyalty.

The two personality profiles show different behaviour patterns when it comes to tourism. Depending on the psychological and motivation characteristics of tourist, different “travel style” can be observed (e.g. Bieger (2002) and Laesser (2002)). Huang (2009) completed the literature review of travel motivation and proposed two scenarios from a practical point of view:

Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory;

Plog's allocentrism and psychocentrism model.

Research has demonstrated that managers' understanding of travellers' internal psychological needs has advanced in the development of tourist products. Motivations have become the foundation of various consumer models in tourism marketing. Studies have looked at the push (internal) vs. pull (external) motivations in terms of repeat visits, pay-per-visit, emotional attachment, and expectations and satisfaction in various groups of visitors (Rao and Sieben, 1992), Tian-Cole & Crompton, 2003, Bigne et al., Fuchs & M. & Weiermair K., 2003), among others (Aschauer, 2010). These studies demonstrate the importance of good service quality in increasing the likelihood of repeat visits. The perception of services quality influences expectations and motivations. Emotional connection to the destination can play a significant role in consumer behaviour, e.g. in the repeat visitors segment (Iwasaki & Havitz, 1998).

Consumers satisfaction is closely linked to profitability, although there are exceptions (e.g. Gurau & Ranchod 2002). Generally, there is little research on consumer satisfaction, loyalty, and profitability, both in destination marketing and in private companies marketing.

According to Alegre & Juaneda (2006), two opposite effects can be seen in a destination. First, repeat visitors make more efficient choices and spend less. Second, repeat visitors are more willing to pay surcharges.

The research should be focused on the effectiveness and efficiency of marketing budget in relation to the options mentioned, as well as non-monetary cost and risk attitude.

The loyalty research was researched in various studies, predominantly as the loyalty to a destination (Baloglu, 2001; Beaman, Huan and Kozak, 2002; Fyall, Callod and Edwards, 2003; Pyo, Song and Chang, 1998). From marketing point of view, repeated visitors have been considered to be highly desirable because of lower marketing costs (Oppermann, 2000), secondly a return indicates one's satisfaction and thirdly, thanks to the inertial attitude of repeaters the likelihood to return is higher (Oppermann, 1998). The relationship between customer loyalty and price sensitivity has been studied by the following authors: Krishnamurti & Papatla, (2003), Keane & Wernerfelt, (1991), Alegre & Juaneda, (2006). The loyalty of repeat visitors to a destination from both an economic and non-economic perspective has been studied using three different economic theory models:

There is a strong focus on cross-cultural differences in tourism marketing and their impact on consumer behaviour. Pizam et al. (1995) found that 18 of the 20 behavioural characteristics were significantly different among the four nationalities of Japanese, French, Italian and American tourists. Yadav et al. (2010) looked at pilgrimage tourism to Lotus temple (India) and concluded that the satisfaction level is dependent on the perception of social-cultural factors. Dolnicar et al. (2003) and the study of the ethnic or immigrants' minorities (Chen and Uysal, 2003) showed the role of ethnic factors and their impact on vacation styles. Kale (1991) emphasizes the role of the four cultural dimensions of Hofstede and provides a framework for evaluating cross-cultural communication effectiveness. Culture specific tools and messages must be applied from the marketing communication perspective.

Market Segmentation, Targeting, Positioning

The traditional segmentation of demand based on demographic, social, if available, and other criteria is being challenged by the more advanced segmentation that has been

developed in recent decades. The traditional segmentation is still valid, but there are gaps in research in particular market segments.

As the population ages in developed countries, there are also changes in the travel behaviour of the senior population. For example, Möller (2007) looked at how the travel behaviour of seniors in Austria changed as they entered retirement age and how this affected tourism. They found that leisure and travel had a huge impact on the respondents' lives. Travel behaviour did not change significantly after entering retirement age, but respondents preferred to spend more time in the country and travel outside of peak season. The study highlights the limitations of the "entering retirement" segmentation criteria.

Moschis et al. (2003) emphasise the need for additional study on the aged customer in relation to the use of financial incentives in this market. In the Swiss vacation rental industry, Sund and Boksberger (2007) sought to pinpoint the fundamental distinctions between senior and non-senior travellers. Except for the fact that pre-seniors are more willing to pay for vacation rentals than seniors, domestic travel is more common among seniors, and technology use is less common among seniors, there were no notable differences between seniors' and non-seniors preferences.

The use of information and communication technologies, emotional attachments to a place or business, and senior client loyalty can all be viewed as potential research areas. Gonzáles et al. (2009) conducted study on the use of a cognitive age of over 55 as a segmentation factor. Cluster analysis's findings demonstrated the significance of psychographic and psychological criteria and the diminished significance of "cognitive age" as a segmentation factor.

The demographic, geographic, behavioural, and psychographic approaches are the most often used segmentation criteria (Tsiotsou, 2006). The future method of segmenting demand appears to be the mixture of different segmentation methodologies (Tsiotsou and Vasioti, 2006). In their 2009 study, Sudbury and Simcock created a multivariate segmentation model for the senior market and identified five clusters that varied greatly

from one another in terms of both consumer behaviour and a number of other characteristics.

Psychographic and psychological factors make up the majority of the clusters. The identification of important market segments, such as baby boomers or generation Y, short-break travel, or even one-day trips, will be a key component of future tourism marketing requirements. The problem for future tourism marketing is determining which factors are important in segmenting tourists and how to combine them. It is highly valued when segmentation approaches and findings are applied in practical.

Brand strategy and brand management

The first theoretical ideas applying branding theory and practise from non-tourism branches to the tourism branch were published at the end of the 1990s (Gnoth, 1998; Ritchie and Ritchie, 1998), and Morgan et al. (2004) dealt with the results and management repercussions of these theoretical ideas. Since the rivalry in the tourism sector has gotten more intense, there has been a demand for branding research, and difference based on branding has been seen as a useful strategy for distinction. Simeon claims that "a brand is a consistent group of characters, images, or emotions that consumers recall or experience when they think of a specific symbol, product, service, organisation, or location." Simeon (2006) stated 464.

Tourism hotspots developed into national brands, such as Canada (Hudson and Ritchie, 2009). Saraniemi (2010) provided a description of the various procedures and actions taken by the national tourist agencies with the intention of creating a national destination brand. The research study compiled the branding strategies and found that the productbound branding strategies (Burmann et al., 2009) aren't really different from image-building methods. According to Keller (2008), there are four processes that should be followed in order to develop and manage a strategic brand: identify and establish brand positioning;

plan and execute brand management campaigns; monitor and analyse brand performance (measurement); and develop and maintain sustainable brand equity.

With an emphasis on the consumer decision-making process and consumer behaviour, the destination image can be observed through a variety of disciplines, such as sociology, anthropology, geography, semiotics, or marketing (Gallarza et al., 2002; Peters et al., 2006; Shani and Wang, 2011; Tasci, 2011). The development of the destination brand identity, the positioning of the destination brand, and the calculation of brand equity measurement and tracking are the three core research streams in destination branding that Pike (2009) defined.

The phrase "represents the image" refers to how many ideas, opinions, and perceptions an individual or group has about a particular thing. The item could be a person, place, brand, business, or product. (1991; Barich and Kotler). The pictures are knowledge structures "that can be used as mental shortcuts for processing information in decision-making processes" (Kotler & Gertner, 2002). Destination pictures set a destination apart from its rivals and help to position it in the market (Echtner and Ritchie, 1993). Scot et al. (2011) analyse the connection between national branding and nation-building from the perspective of positioning the destination in the global tourism industry and highlight the function of branding as a tool for both competitiveness and self-affirmation.

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According to Aaker and Joachimsthaler (2000), "brand identity, as opposed to brand image, expresses what the organisation wants the brand to stand for. There are numerous different branding models that can be applied (Kotler, 2000; Upshaw, 1995, and many more), but their application must be customised for each location or business. In their 2010 study, Dinnie et al. looked at the various stakeholders' roles in nation branding initiatives and the rollout of integrated marketing communication in the ASEAN region. The study identified seven crucial factors for inter-organizational coordination, including the target market, the sector, the organization's domicile, the mode, and how to formulate a strategy.

How to describe the conceptual branding model for a destination in all of its complexity, especially at the national level and the brand hierarchy, presents a difficult problem for future research. The requirement to describe the role of various elements impacting destination image and its perception, such as economic, political, weather, people, inherited names, or perception of locations, is fairly strong given that the tourist destination image is very complex, multidisciplinary, and always changing. The role of the mass media in the development of brand identities is a specific area for future research.

Strategic marketing and marketing concept

In tourism strategic marketing, the strategic analytical tools are the first thing to be examined. In general, tourism makes inadequate use of strategic marketing management techniques. Benchmarking, portfolio analysis, strategic map, balanced scorecard, value chain analysis, and SWOT analysis are among the approaches used in tourism marketing. For strategic decision-making and planning, the outcomes of the use of strategic instruments are crucial. The decision and subsequent performance measurement may be simpler at the company (micro) level than at the destination (macro), where the system of indicators to track the effects, destination competitiveness, or performance is fairly challenging.

When it comes to destination marketing management in particular, it can be challenging to distinguish between strategic tourism marketing and issues with tourism management and

policy. De Carlo et al. (2008) developed the balanced scorecard model to evaluate the success of the destination using the strategy map technique as a foundation. Based on data from the city of Turin, the important aspects of strategy assessment were determined using a qualitative methodology. The hierarchy of strategy assessment, which takes into account the balanced scorecard concept was anticipated by Evans (2005) for the global hotel sector in Northern England. Evans noted that many hoteliers employed aspects of the BSC model's four dimensions, though oftentimes they did so subconsciously and without a sophisticated point of view. The balanced scorecard model is becoming increasingly important as a useful performance assessment tool, according to Sainaghi's (2010) analysis of performance measurement in the hotel business. Min et al. (2008) conducted more study on Korean luxury hotels using the balanced scorecard in tourism marketing with the goal of developing a balanced scorecard model for evaluating the relative effectiveness of Korean luxury hotels and for establishing their performance criteria.

Kozak (2001), Kozak and Rimmington (1998), or Fuchs and Weiermair (2004) used benchmarking as a strategic tool to evaluate tourist satisfaction in a destination, to assess the attractiveness of the destination and its relationships to the performance of small hospitality businesses, or to obtain a set of indicators to measure the visitors' satisfaction in a destination. Laimer and Weiss (2009) used portfolio analysis to gather information for policymakers in the Austrian tourism sector. Based on lodging records for more than 60 markets during a 35-year period, the tourism flows were examined.

Yilmaz and Bititci (2006) employed the value chain analysis as a management and performance measuring tool. The concept of studying the tourism sector as a value chain that benefits many stakeholders in measurable terms of efficacy and efficiency is very novel in the field of tourism marketing. Although managing and measuring the value chain is important for tourism marketing, the proposed framework presents significant difficulties for practitioners and researchers. Sharma and Christie (2010) continued their examination of the Mozambique hotel industry's value chain in terms of economic development and poverty reduction.

They portrayed the key impediments to value development as being low management and labour productivity, excessive taxes, import levies, and the expense of complying with legal requirements. A venue, event, operator, and many others can all have their strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats identified using the SWOT method (Weber, 1999; Karadakis et al., 2010; Tew et al., 2008).

Palatková (2011) offered the 7 S McKinsey methodology for putting a destination marketing strategy into practise using the example of the Czech Republic. According to Russell and Faulkner (2004), Pratt (2010), Butler (2006), and Garay (2011), the approach of TALC (Tourism Area Life Cycle), which was evolved from the PLC (Product Life Cycle), was commonly employed, particularly in the destination setting. Tourism marketing has not yet completely embraced the use of popular marketing management techniques like the Ansoff matrix, VRIO, SPACE, and others. Since the 1990s, there has been a significant expansion in the body of literature and research on strategic marketing (management), including tourism planning with a primary focus on destination planning.

Bieger (2005), Luft (2005), Gunn (1994), Jamal and Getz (1995), or Pearce (2000), to mention a few, are representative of the research that focuses primarily on the macro level (destination level). The problem is how to put the macro goals into practise, translate them into micro goals for the business, and monitor them. In the tourism marketing literature, strategic marketing planning is typically more or less centred on the destination level without any connections to specific stakeholders.

Traditional and new communication tools (e-marketing)

In the 1990s, researchers and industry professionals focused on information and communication technologies (ICT) and their application in the tourism industry. The problems for theory and practise of tourism marketing are adoption and e-business in the areas of C2C communication, e-marketing, and e-word-of-mouth marketing. Schertler (1994) investigated the function of information technology from the perspective of strategic management. The literature later has a variety of methods to ICT application in

tourism, although the pace of ICT development is faster than that of researchers' effort. ICT facilitated communication between various stakeholders and aided in the growth of travel and tourism (Buhalis and Law, 2008). In the tourism sub-segments, the use of ICT in distribution and communication channels has grown significantly (Reino et al., 2011; Dwivedi et al., 2009; Sirirak et al., 2011).

Ip et al. (2011) found that training, security, reservations, revenue management, marketing, guest services, as well as strategic and operational management were the seven areas where The hospitality sector uses ICT the most frequently.

The development of information and communication technology (ICT) has led to significant changes in communication patterns since the 1990s. Niininen et al. (2007) claim that there are three ways in which the web environment has empowered consumers: first, the visitor is better informed thanks to independent reports available on the web; second, the power of e-word-of-mouth communication; and third, the communication between the consumers and companies changed towards the personalised or even tailored form.

CRM can be compared to the consumer centric marketing (CCM), which is a more sophisticated marketing philosophy. The CRM (customer relationship management) in tourism as developed by Varey (2004) or Daniel et al. (2003) serves as the foundation for the CCM. According to Maney et al. (2002), the CCM idea is "the discipline of capturing and deploying consumer insights to enhance marketing effectiveness and better serve those consumers who are brand's best prospects."

Since it entails using the internet and other interactive technologies to foster communication between the business and customers, e-marketing can be regarded as one of the primary components of tourism marketing (Coviello et al., 2001). By giving customers access to information and giving businesses information on consumers, Brodie et al. (2007) highlighted the exceptional position of e-marketing. Although its function in e-marketing is increasingly widespread, the internet has traditionally been seen as the

primary tool. The web can be utilised for data gathering and analysis, communication with and among consumers, identification and tracking of customers, and management support (Wang et al., 2000).

The topic of the function of travel agents and even tour operators in the current and future tourism business is raised by the growing use of the internet in tourist marketing. Wynne et al. (2001)'s investigation into the South African tourism business was one of the first studies in this area. The research study put special attention on distribution and communication while focusing on the role of intermediaries in the value chain and the advantages and opportunities brought about by internet marketing.

The planned and evaluated intermediary profile was seen from the perspective of the electronic value chain. In a 2004 study, Vrana and Zafiroopoulos examined how Greek travel agencies felt about internet technology. Although a very limited number of transactions were carried out online, Greek travel agents used the internet to facilitate marketing efforts and complete online services. The biggest barriers to more intense internet marketing were the impression of unease and the custom of direct social contact.

Social media's influence on tourism marketing has become crucial. Social networking (like Facebook), social bookmarking (like ratings and tags), collaborative authoring (like wikis), and syndication (like RSS feeds) are all made feasible by social media and related technologies (Dawson, 2007; O'Reilly, 2005). Through the use of social media, the position of tourist intermediaries has undergone significant shift (Buhalis and Law, 2008). The direct consumer contact provided by social media for the travel and tourist sector increases productivity (Tse, 2003). The social networks are considered by Hogg (2010) and Pantano et al. (2010) to be the primary instrument for making travel decisions.

Di Pietro et al. (2012) conducted research on how social networks can influence travel decisions in terms of media for destination promotion and competitive advantage. In the study, the TAM (Technology Acceptance Model) was used. The TAM highlighted social networks and electronic word-of-mouth as playing a crucial influence. There is a lot of

room for research to be used in practise because it does not fully address how consumers access social networks, how they behave there, or how social networks affect their decision-making.

The focus of future research will be on how C2C communication functions in tourism and how it may be impacted and quantified. The mobile application for visitors has increased in popularity as a result of the enormous growth in mobile device applications over the past ten years. Context-aware applications have the benefit of better catering to visitor needs. The mobile applications frequently lack agreement on how to define context and fail to comprehend the needs of users.

The TILES (temporal, identity, location, environmental, and social) model was projected by Meng-Yoke Tan et al. (2009) to describe and categorise five significant types and features linked to each of the examined mobile applications for tourism. The TILES model was created to help understand the context in which users of the information need to use it. The network of customers (visitors) based on mobile devices was envisioned by Tatiopoulos and Boutsinas (2010) as an intelligent social networking process backed by other e-commerce activities. The C2C communication trend and its increasing significance are reflected in the model.

Strategic problems for tourism marketing in the future Following the discussion on marketing in other non-tourism industries, there were discussions on marketing in the tourism sector. Researchers and practitioners alike examined the effectiveness and viability of the new methods and concepts of tourism marketing. One of the fundamental pillars of tourist marketing may be seen in Riege and Perry's (2000) proposal to concentrate on three strategic approaches in the tourism industry. The consumer-oriented approach, competitor-oriented approach, and trade-oriented approach make up the platform of three approaches; as a result, the demand and supply picture as well as the competition environment are given.

The discussion on tourism and tourism marketing became centred around marketing orientation itself and its effects. The literature focusing on a specific sub-sector and tourism

services is less prevalent than the literature on destination marketing orientation. Only four studies in the field of travel and tourism services, all of which were concentrated solely on the hotel industry, had a marketing emphasis, according to Tsiotsou (2010). It is necessary to conduct more research in this area as well as the broad extent of the tourism sub-sector (tour operators, travel agencies, convention bureaux, convention centres, resorts, rent-a-car businesses, and others). The consumer is typically the research's primary emphasis in studies. The emergence of the idea of customer relationship marketing is the inevitable outcome.

Customer relationship marketing is a helpful strategy to increase customer loyalty, improve financial indicators, and promote sustainability (Shoemaker and Bowen, 2003). Although the CRM can be a useful marketing tool, there hasn't been much advancement in either theory or practise. The general interest in CRM/e-CRM has increased over the past decade, but Kevork and Vrechopoulos (2009) also noted that there is a "...great need and demand from researchers to have clear and full knowledge at both a general and abstract level as well as numerical information (metrics) about all the e-CRM related research area categories and sub-categories." (Vrechopoulos and Kevork, 2009).

Relationship marketing for the travel industry is typically considered a research field that is still in its early stages. The most significant relationship marketing theorists, in the opinion of Tsiotsou and Ratten (2010), are those who studied the resource exchange theory in Moaris and Zillifro's (2003) work, rough set theory in Au and Law's (2002) work, or the application of neural networks (Tsaur et al., 2002). Sui and Baloglu (2003) examined the patronage behaviour of casino club members, while Kim et al. (2006) looked at consumer happiness as a result of loyalty. These are only two examples of practical research with a focus on the tourist sector. Global integration has largely remained a concept.

Palmer (2010) conducted a critical analysis of customer experience management and concluded that while the concept of CEM (customer experience management) has been

implemented as a higher level of traditional CRM, the practical realisation of inter-functional integration has more closely resembled an idea than a reality.

The CRM and/or CEM research and applications appear to cover a wide range of topics, including consumer intents, word-of-mouth marketing, and customer value. The "white place" in the future should be filled in areas like self-expression, service personality, tourism involvement in the loyalty value chain research, and its financial and practical implications in the private and public sectors (primarily destination).

In tourism marketing, the idea of experience marketing has grown significantly. Today, it is essential to customise the goods and services, so academics and practitioners can look forward to using experiential marketing in tourism marketing. The hospitality industry (e.g. Williams, 2006) or natural and historical settings (e.g. Schanzel and McIntosh, 2000) are where the advancements in experiential tourist marketing are most obvious. The characteristics of the tourism experience and how they relate to strategic and tactical marketing require more study.

The idea of sustainability marketing follows naturally from the growth of sustainable (travel and tourism). As it focuses on people (including visitors and locals), sustainable marketing "... extends the theory of marketing into ensuring ecological, social (equity and equality), and economical balance in time and space" (Nkamnebe, 2011:218). Agbonifoh et al. (2007) state that "the (classical) marketing consists of individual and organisational (as well as societal) activities designed to facilitate and expedite exchanges so as to achieve the goals of the producer/seller (society) by sensing and satisfying consumers' (societies') needs (and wants)."

Although it is possible to define sustainable marketing in theory, doing it in practise is highly challenging. According to Belz's definition of sustainability marketing, it entails "... building and maintaining sustainable relationship with customers, the social environment, and the natural environment" (Belz, 2005:2). Sustainable marketing is inextricably linked to the idea of producing value for customers, society, and the environment (Elkinton, 1999). The state sector, commercial businesses, locals, and tourists visiting the location all participate in the sustainable marketing industry. Sirgy and Don-Jin (1996) focused on how to develop socially conscious marketing goals using a quality-of-life strategy. Setting marketing goals affects how stakeholders behave, how processes are sustainable, and how sustainability goals are attained.

Societal marketing can be characterised as being a very close idea to the previously discussed sustainability marketing. Aiming for society benefits rather than just financial gains for the private sector, the concept of societal (social) marketing first surfaced 30 years ago. Collaboration with clients (visitors) and partners is the foundation of the definition of social marketing. In accordance with Kotler and Armstrong, societal marketing is a development of the production, selling, and consumer orientation that takes into account not only the satisfaction of the customer but also expands it in the direction of "society's well-being" (Kotler and Armstrong, 1990). According to Jamrozny (2007), societal marketing is typically seen as "complex" marketing and a promising future trend.

3.2.2. Tourism Marketing Mix

The performance of a tourist operator will be determined by the efficiency of which they manage the resources available to them and how willing they are to adapt to the changing environment. Any organisation whether public or private should focus heavily on a highly concentrated analysis of marketing mix specific to tourism industry, as an instrument in tourism marketing theory operationalisation. Without a focused and consecutive research on tourists products and services and consumer behaviours, a tourist provider can not provide products and services that are worth customers' time and money; therefore,

offering no value for money. Tourism marketing mix consists of price, product, promotion, physical processes and evidence, people, and distribution. Hence the detailed literature places distinct attention to the concept of tourism product. It is argued that the most significant elements of a national tourism products are the natural and cultural heritage of the destination (location, environment, scenery, recreational attractions, national reserves, cultural and heritage values, language, friendliness, flora and fauna, arts and history, and many more), tourism infrastructure (accommodation quality, food, entertainment, tourist transport system, facilities and amenities, etc) and general infrastructure of the destination (road, trade, local culture, and political and economic development) (Shellenberg, 1965). Krippendorf (1987) suggests that tourism products refer to a combination of tangible and intangible components offered for consumption, these should bring some remunerations to the consumers for satisfaction. Tourism product is the main component of tourism marketing (Stancioiu, 2005). Tourism research focuses on destination development since it is an essential part of tourism product. In recent year, destinations have been a subject of researchers interests. In those researchers, special attention has been paid to tourist destination image. Postelnicu (1997) states that the tourism image should be designed by ensuring that; the message is clear and easily understandable, provokes interest in potential consumers, and lastly be visible through intellectual forms of communication.

Apart from product, price is a fundamental element of a tourism marketing strategy. Sabo-Bucur (2006) states that price is a variable of the marketing mix which is neither completely exogenous or completely endogenous. A tourism product priced appropriately through an appropriate channel is extremely significant in taking advantage of the tourism potential. The tourism marketing mix elements discussed above will be unsuccessful without the fourth element; promotion. Promotion enables customer to know about the products and services being offered by a tourism provider. This can be achieved through various methods, written and oral, and direct and indirect information (Hollier & Lanquar, 1993). The approaches to promotions of tourism products and services could be paid advertisements, sales promotions, travel fairs and exhibitions. Since tourism product can't

be experienced before being bought, it is essential that promotional activities paint an accurate and enticing picture of the product in order to portray an honest picture of the products (Nita, 2008). Word of mouth marketing is said to be the most effective way of marketing a destination (Chambers & Lewis, 2000). Tourist operators should be highly creative and have a shock value to display their promotional messages (Nedelea, 2003). At the same time, it is argued that without good quality products, a good image isn't of much use (Ban, 2007). Tourism workers can have a major impact on perceptions of tourism product quality. People are a part of extended tourism marketing mix, as tourist activities require human resources (locals and tour guides), those enable functionality of other elements of the product. Human resources grow as the demands of customers increase, therefore, the development of tourism activities within an organisation depends highly on how human resources are utilised (Minciu, 2010).

Kotler (1994) states that the idea of marketing mix is that the market offers itself as one variable and it needs to be considered together with other marketing variables. To increase the chances of achieving success in a business, the essential elements of marketing mix need to be synchronised, and thus, marketers should consider a comprehensive combination of components associated with the offerings of the market. McCarthy (1960) details the 4 P's; price, place, product and promotion as follows;

Product: marketing is mainly performed for profit gaining purposes and therefore, customer preferences are only considered if there is a likelihood of a consumer's ability to pay. These values lack concern for people who cannot afford such a holiday. The product feature, of the marketing mix, to accomplish sustainable tourism revolves around creating products that are sustainable in nature. For instance;

- Holiday packages that offer public transport rather than use of private hires
- Go on conservation holidays
- Low-key rural community based holidays

Avoid product that do not support sustainable tourism

- Hunting holidays
- Visit to places with low environmental standards where tourism development is harming the local community and their natural resources (Swarbrooke, 1999)

Place: Place refers to the physical location of a destination, it is a location where marketing campaigns will be carried out (Batra, 2006). Place can also be referred to as a channel through which information is gathered to distribute the message. For instance, if a decision had been made to release a code of conduct to tourists, cooperation of mediators (tour operators, travel agents) is required to spread the message (Dinan, 2000). Therefore, as Swarsbrooke (1999) suggests, that it is better to encourage direct selling as this will result in better value for customers. If an agent or operator is used, it is essential to make sure that the product sold is sold ethically and has not created unrealistic expectations for tourists.

Promotion: Promotion factor of the marketing mix refers to the promotion efforts that are made by an organisation to attract customers. businesses use a range of tactics to promote their products and services. The promotional material should be concise in spreading the message. Marketing pollution is when there is an over-excess of promotional material regarding destinations, it makes those places look less attractive. For instance, advertisements on buses, taxis, billboards, tv, newspapers and etc create physical pollution, which is not a good image for a destination or organisation. In recent years, there has been a trend to create advertising campaigns that produce a shock effect (Weaver & Opperman, 2000). Tourist destinations should be promoted sustainably, mediums such as social media and brochures should suffice. It is essential that the organisation promoting their products and services do not create unrealistic expectations that cannot be met.

People:

Price: Price factor of the marketing mix comprises of the prices that tourists are charged at any stage of tourism experience, prices often include promotions and discounts. Swarsbrooke (1999) states that pricing in tourism industry stresses on low cost experiences to gain a large number of customers, which in turn will result in high levels of profit. Normally, public sector does not emphasises on profits although it is highly influential in for-profit organisations (Benefield & Beeton, 2002).

3.3. Tourist Satisfaction

Tourism industry plays a vital role in the economy of a developing country just as it plays a vital role in the economy of a developed country. Vanhove states that the very definition of tourism has changed over the last few decades as it now includes dynamic and static elements as well as economic consequences; these elements entail temporary travel, staying in a destination away from work and home, and facilities and services provided by those destinations. UNTWO state in their take on tourism that tourists are travellers who want to stay in destinations that are different to their usual surroundings, for longer than a day and less than one year for either leisure, work and anything else that is not related to any activity for financial gains (2003). Cronin and Brody (2000) suggest that customer satisfaction has garnered a lot of attention due to its ability to influence consumer behaviour and their retention. Customer satisfaction is a broad term and has been defined in many different forms; from affective and cognitive approaches to another that suggest the hoarding and specific character of a transaction (Knie-Anderson et al, 2004). Anderson et al (1994) state that satisfaction is affected by factors; expectations, price, and perceived quality of products and services. Cultural aspect of a destination and personalities of visitors are significant in achieving tourist satisfaction (Jinhuh, 2002). Jin Huh suggested that a visitor's background such as their race, gender, marital and employment status as well as socioeconomic situation should be taken into consideration. It has been reiterated

by various researchers that customer satisfaction evaluation is essential in improving a products' or service quality, that will ultimately lead to an efficient competitive advantage (Sun and Shergill, 2005).

It is well established that customer satisfaction is one of the most important factor of an organisation's success, there is somewhat of a perplexicity in the definition of satisfaction and how does one government go about achieving it. For instance, in a study conducted on Spanish tourists concluded that demographics and cultural characteristics play a vital role in decision making regarding travels. It was noted in the study that the income and education level of the decision maker in the families made a significant difference (Pou & Alegre, 2002). In a study conducted by Prideaux and Master on Taiwanese tourists, it was determined that characteristics such as age, gender and occupation affected the level of customer satisfaction (2000). Cultural characteristics have a significant influence of customer satisfaction levels.

Another aspect of customer satisfaction is customer complain behaviour. Customers from individualistic cultures (Western) are more likely to voice their dissatisfaction than customers from collectivist (Eastern; Pakistan, India etc) cultures (McClure & Liu, 2001). Opperman suggested that destination experience can significantly influence satisfaction levels (1996). Another research highlighted that previous visits to specific destinations affected tourists perceptions of visiting similar destinations, for instance a neighbouring country. Tourist attitudes are affected by various factors, some of them are the culture and the environment. Different backgrounds such as age, ethnicity and income play a vital role in customer expectations and perception (Arweiler & Danaher, 1998; Lawton, 1998). In a 2004 study on the role of internet on travel operators and agencies, Wang et al (2004) reveal that some tourists were still using travel agencies, however, most tourists agreed that more information can be found on the internet. Tourists' search for information can be predicted as commonucation between the tourist, tourism information and the internet. Many recent studies suggest that tourists look for information on the internet for various reasons and on various decision-making stages.

Practically speaking, in the context of destinations, satisfaction can be impacted by various factors such as accommodation, food, shopping facilities, recreational opportunities, accessibility levels, local culture, scenery, historical representation, environment, facilities and amenities, communication and interaction, and value for money (Qu & Chi, 2008). In some studies on tourists attraction, safety, price, accessibility, and in some cases employees too, were found to have impacted tourist satisfaction levels (Herting & Spath, 2008). Whereas in research regarding hospitality industry, factors such as hygiene, food and menu diversity, convenience, facilities and value for money were found to have impacted tourist satisfaction (Jang & Liu, 2008).

Repeat tourism is a subject that has been researched well in the past (Stylos et al, 2017). Repeat tourism is reported to cost less in the long-term as compared to reliance on first time tourists, and therefore, the sustainability of a destination relies significantly on revisiting tourists (Um et al, 2006). Since repeat tourism is of high importance, studies conducted on factors pertaining tourists' intention to revisit and consumer behaviour have shown that, a positive destination experience can play a vital role in determination to repeat the visit (Nunkoo, 2018). Similar empirical studies in the past have also demonstrated that visitors' experience satisfaction from a destination are a substantial factor in their intention to repeat the visit to the destination (Petrick & Choo, 2014; Norman et al, 2001).

Fornell (1992) proposed that the level of satisfaction experienced by a tourist from the tourism provider, the more the chances of tourist using the same provider. Although there has been a considerable amount of progress made in understanding of satisfaction with many aspects of a destination and tourists' revisit intentions, there is a need for better understanding of a destination characteristics that establish destination satisfaction.

Tourism experience is made of many independent components, some tangible and some intangible, therefore tourist satisfaction could be considered as cumulative factor of consumer experience. The concept of tourist satisfaction could be explained at at least three different levels; overall satisfaction, component satisfaction, and products and service

satisfaction. the third could be described as tourists satisfaction with regards to individual product and service experiences dispensed by an organisation in the product supply-chain. For instance, satisfaction with tourist providers is an example of products and service level satisfaction. Component level satisfaction entails results achieved from all satisfaction deriving from products and services within a given element of tourism. for instance, it is the cumulation of satisfaction achieved from amenities, service providers, restaurants etc in a hotel. Lastly, total satisfaction refers to all of the above mentioned satisfaction levels combined that were experienced by the visitor. Hence, satisfaction of a tourist experience can be created by the sum of total satisfaction gained through the individual variables of all services and products that make up a holiday (Pizam, 1994). Hughes (1989) stated that it is essential to observe that nature of an experience is normally outside the direct impact of destination developers because activities of businesses and individuals could influence the destination experience of a tourist. Tourist satisfaction is a highly variable concept, wherein not every tourist gains the same level of satisfaction at the same destination.

A vast amount of literature is dedicated to the positive relationship between service quality and satisfaction (Kasiri *et al.*, 2017; Kassim and Asiah Abdullah, 2010). Han and Hyun (2015) analyzed a conceptual model of impact of quality, satisfaction, trust and price reasonableness in the medical tourism industry and found that both perceived medical quality and perceived service quality critically influence satisfaction. Han and Hyun (2017) explored the relationships between overall restaurant image, image congruence and satisfaction with the quality of the physical environment, service and food, with the intention of revisiting hospitality management, and they stressed that all quality dimensions are associated with satisfaction. Recently, in the context of sports tourism, there is a growing body of evidence that shows event quality predicts tourist satisfaction. Jeong *et al.* (2019) investigated the relationships between event quality, tourist satisfaction, place attachment and behavioral intentions, and emphasized that positive perception of event quality is related to the formation of satisfaction.

Tourists often search for information on the Internet before going on a trip (Pan and Fesenmaier, 2006), and the amount of TGC has grown dramatically (Llodrà-Riera *et al.*, 2015). Recent research has shown that tourists also rely on TGC for tourism knowledge and status seeking (Liu *et al.*, 2018). There are different presentations of TGC, such as text, photos and videos. Travel blogs are one of the most commonly used sources published by tourists, who describe travel activities and express feelings or attitudes about a specific destination (Pühringer and Taylor, 2008; Li and Wang, 2011). Volo (2010) provides a systematic way to classify TGC: “consumer to consumer” (C2C), “business to consumer” (B2C), “business to business” (B2B) and “government to consumer” (G2C). More specifically, “consumer to consumer” (C2C) commonly refers to user-generated or TGC, with sharing tourism experiences, communicating with family and friends and creating electronic word-of-mouth. “Business to Consumer” (B2C) is also regarded as corporate blogs, to communicate companies' offerings to foster relationships with customers. This B2C content is generated in-house or by professional bloggers. “Business to Business” (B2B) represents facilitating networking opportunities for tourism businesses, through which stakeholders may communicate industry trends, technological developments, research findings or marketing tips. “Government to Consumer” (G2C) reflects that content is created by NTOs/DMOs to communicate with their target markets, and/or generated in-house or by professional bloggers. Since the purpose of this study is to understand tourists' perceptions of DI, the focus of the investigation will be on “consumer to consumer” content.

Compared with traditional channels, TGC has several advantages in information storage, spread and search efficiency. It can be shared and consumed anytime and anywhere by tourists all over the world, which can help to shape an online DI (Banyai and Glover, 2012). Recent research reveals that user-generated content may be more valuable for assessing customer needs and developing products compared with conventional methods such as interviews and focus groups (Timoshenko and Hauser, 2019). Researchers and organisations can employ text-mining tools to identify frequent words, topics and subtopics

to uncover the major reasons why customers assign lower/higher ratings to a restaurant's image, such as taste, environment and service (Jia, 2018). Moreover, research has shown that consumers perceive that TGC can provide more reliable information than the content provided by destination marketers or official tourism organisations (María Munar, 2011). According to Litvin *et al.* (2008), TGC has the advantage of the spread of electronic word-of-mouth, and it affects tourists' travel intentions. Pan *et al.* (2007) support this by indicating that TGC's rich, original and authentic information affects tourists' decisions.

With the growth of TGC, tourists not only receive information but also create and share information, thereby empowering them to co-construct a DI, which actively influences DI formation (Beerli and Martin, 2004). Volo's (2010) research highlights how people are attracted when browsing social media websites and receiving information, stimulating their motivation to travel to a particular destination, with the online DI built into this process. Compared to traditional processes, an online DI is built on two-way communication through Web 2.0 technology. Both sides are empowered to build the DI and introduce more complicated questions about a destination to tailor and frame the image. Therefore, online DI has gained increasing attention for its effect on tourist behaviour, destination choice and the reputation of the destination (Mak, 2017).

3.4. Marketing

3.4.1. An Introduction to Marketing

Marketing plays a significant role in any business and without a marketing department a business is deemed to fall apart. There are numerous ways a business can market itself and almost every business in today's world spend a heft amount to spread their message across. However, word of mouth marketing is probably the oldest form of marketing and has been around since humans started doing business. It is the most trusted form of marketing as in many instances it is done without any expectation for a reward in return. Thus, it is vital

for companies to invest heavily on this particular form of marketing and ensure that every aspect of their business speaks for itself.

Many businesses are faced with continuous changes, various challenges, fierce competition, and are highly expected to be accountable and reliable and they rely on their capability to prove their relevance and value to survive, for that purpose marketing is a highly essential tool (Harrison and Shaw, 2004, pp. 397). To realise the significance of marketing, one must recognise the concept of marketing.

To define marketing, it appears that there are a myriad of definitions, however most of those definitions emphasise mainly on the profit making aspect of marketing. This is because most formal definitions of marketing have typically been based on profitable side of an exchange, due to the focus being on the product not the consumer. According to existing literature, currently there is a lack in definitions of marketing for non-profit organisations and a revised definition is highly likely to overcome the complications of the service industry (Wilkie and Moore, 2007).

Marketing originated because industries needed marketing techniques to link their products and services with potential customers (Welch, 2006). Since then the growth of marketing has been evolutionary, and Massingham & Lancaster (2001) say that “there is not single, universal agreed definition”. Marketing is a global phenomenon used by for-profit and non-profit organisations to achieve its business goals (Garoufallou et al, 2013). Kotler (1972) indicates that marketing is an efficient and effective method of an exchange relationship between an organisation and its consumers. Armstrong and Kotler’s definition of marketing is “the process by which companies create value for customers and build strong customer relationships in order to capture value from customers in return” (2014).

Fig 6. Marketing Process Model (Source: Armstrong, 2012)

The figure above depicts the process of marketing, it is a five-tiered model for organisations to follow. The first step is to gain an understanding of the potential consumers and the marketplace, the second step is to design a strategy to attract consumers, the third step is to create value for customers, fourth is structuring strong ties with consumers, and the last step is to gain value for a business from consumers. According to Kotler and Armstrong, this process of five steps followed by a business will result in high sales, high profits, equity, and consumer loyalty (2012).

According to American Marketing Association, marketing is “the activity, set of institutions, and processes for creating, communicating, delivering, and exchanging offerings that have value for customers, clients, partners, and society at large” (2013). Martin and Hague (2013) state that an organisation could concentrate on increasing, shares, sales, and profits by marketing and therefore, can improve and enhance customer loyalty, brand awareness and reduce risks to a business. Marketing is being used in all sectors of business, both profit and non-profit. There are many different ways marketing can be utilised to achieve its financial and corporate goals, such as; social media marketing and word of mouth marketing (Koontz, 2014). The main aim of marketing is to offer customer satisfaction and retention. Welch (2006) suggest that marketing is a philosophical concept wherein an organisation emphasises on consumers rather than their products. Marketing is

often associated with just the promotion of products and services, however, it is a much vast subject and promotion is only one element of marketing (Appel et al, 2020).

3.4.2. Marketing Theories and Models:

As stated above, marketing is a mature and vast subject area which comprises of various theories and models. To sell products and services, organisation require marketing plans and approaches. Some of the most commonly used marketing theories and methods will be discussed in this section of the research.

3.4.2.1. Web-based Marketing

Marketing is a broad subject, there are many different marketing theories and methods. One of the most important one, in today's world, is web-based marketing. The internet has revolutionised the field of marketing, now a business can convey their marketing message to consumers that are thousands of miles away. Magazines, newspapers, tv and radio can all be found on the internet easily and are accessible anywhere with internet facilities. A report by Statistica stated that there were almost 4.6 billion people using internet actively, covering almost 60% of the total world population (Johnson, 2021). The numbers of internet users are increasing everyday, it has almost doubled since 2012 when 2.4 billion people were reported to have actively used the internet (Narkiniemi, 2013).

The growth of the internet has been astonishing since it's inception 30 years ago in 1991. By the millennium of 2000, there were 361 million people globally with internet access and since then the number has increased by 92% (Internet World Stats, 2020). Due to being the most populous continent, Asia has the highest number of internet users with 2.6 billion user actively using the internet.

Web 2.0:

According to Garder's survey (2013), the top priority in digital marketing investment will be to improve commerce experiences through social marketing, content creation and management and mobile marketing. Key findings also revealed that a companies' marketing success relies mostly on their website, social marketing, and digital advertising, which are all parts of digital marketing. In addition, savings made by using digital marketing can be reinvested elsewhere. Normally, companies spend 10 percent of their revenue on marketing and 2.4 percent on digital marketing, which will increase to 9 percent in the future. (Garder 2013).

The two tiers of the world wide web are referred to as Web 1.0 and Web 2.0. Web 1.0 is where users can read and is static whereas Web 2.0 can loosely be described as the section of web where users can interact with other users and generate their own content. O'Reilly and Musser (2006) define web 2.0 as "a set of economic, social and technology trends that collectively form the basis for the next generation of the internet --- a more mature, distinctive medium characterized by user participation, openness and network effects".

3.4.2.2. Social Media

Newhagen & Rafaeli (1996) stated that the internet provided users with interconnections, customisation options and immense resources of information, which provides for a tailored search experience and content to its users. Werthner and Klein (1999) predicted that the world wide web will become one of the most efficient and effective way for tourists to find information online. Although, the sources on the web and social media are extensive, it has been noted that people tend to lean towards information that is provided by other users' first hand experience, making it the most influential source of information in decision making of potential customers (Crotts, 1999). Nevertheless, concerns have been noted regarding overload of information that is available on the internet, which could make it

complicated for users to look for the correct information that is relevant to their specific needs and wants (Radosevich, 1997; Mintel, 2014). Pan et al (2007) believe that the web allows users to communicate on online platforms which is similar to word-of-mouth, which inspires potential consumers.

Social media, aside from its popularity as a tool to share content and make connections with billions of other users, has become an excellent tool for tourism, wherein 1) potential visitors/tourists look for other people's experiences of a destination due to the experiential nature of tourism products and services (Litvin et al, 2008), mainly to lessen uncertainty, 2) social media stories that enable users to have a virtual experience with a certain destination (Gretzel et al, 2006). Social media plays a vital role in planning of a tour as a vast information source. According to Chen and Tan (2012) at times online information, on a new destination, travel blogs are considered to be more accurate than any other source. Aرسال et al (2010) state that 31% of Lonely Planet travel blogs influenced its members travelling plans. social media advances with every passing day, however, at the same consumers expectations and behaviours change as well. Reasons could be changes in lifestyle and opinions, preferring shorter holidays, and dearching for best possible value for money deals have carved out another species of tourism consumers; more individualistic, mature, informed and more independent (Poon, 1993).

A study conducted by Neilson revealed that people spend the most amount of time on social media than any other avenue on the web. According to the research, 20% of the time was spend on PC (personal computer), whereas 30% was spent on mobile phones. Other electronic gadgets such as tablets and e-readers were also used extensively for accessing social media.

Social media is an excellent tool for people to share and express feelings, ideas and thoughts with other users. It also enables people connect with others, like people have been for centuries. The benefit, however, of social media communication is that it has removed

time constraints and spatial issues that were present before the inception of the internet, social media has also provided people with platforms to share content, and has provided such ease of access and easy navigation through it that anyone can easily learn to share and connect with other people. (Fotis, 2015).

Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) define social media as “social media is a group of internet-based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of web 2.0, and that allow the creation and exchange of user generated content”. Some of the most popular platforms of social media are Facebook, Instagram, Youtube, Twitter, Snapchat, and TikTok. As depicted in the figure below, percentage of people using social media actively on a daily basis has grown significantly in 2019 as compared to 2018. Facebook dominates the daily social media usage, followed by Instagram and Snapchat.

Fig 7. Daily Social Media Usage (Source: Broadband Research, 2021)

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Social Media Statistics: in a market research conducted in 2019, it was revealed that almost 80% of marketers use Facebook Ads. It isn't a surprise considering Facebook, as a social networking site, has the largest number of active users as compared to any other social media platform. 47% of marketing performed globally for travel and tourism is digital advertising. 81% of travellers state that it is significant for travel organisations to provide

customised and personalised experiences. 74% of travellers used social media while travelling to destinations, this could imply using content sharing platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter and Snachat to document their trip or to generally gather information about nearby products and offers. 97 % of millennials stated that they share photos and videos of their experience while travelling through destinations. 75% friends and acquaintances engage in travel related content shared by their friends and family. 43% of respondents stated that they will cancel their travel plans if they weren't sure that they will be able to access social media platform of their preference, to share photos and videos. With regards to experiential travelling, a considerably high percentage (67%) of high income earning travellers stated that they would prefer to spend their money recreational activities rather than flashy and luxurious hotels and dining experiences. A substantial (40%) of travellers stated that they leave reviews after every single (Steve, 2019).

Online users including businesses and organizations are increasingly subscribing to different social networks services (SNSs), including Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, Twitter and LinkedIn, among others. They are creating social media pages and groups to reach larger audiences. SNSs allow them to raise awareness about products, services and causes. They enable them to share online content including textual information, images, videos and hyperlink.

At the same time, individuals can use them to engage in two-way conversations with their followers, who may be consumers and prospects. Therefore, social media subscribers are expected to dedicate their time to look after their account, to disseminate promotional content and to respond to online users in a timely manner. The utilization of SNSs has radically influenced the style of online communications and has altered the relationships among marketplace stakeholders, between the businesses and their consumers as well as among customers and prospects.

For instance, tourism marketers disseminate information about their travel services as well as on their destinations' attractions. They may usually feature a good selection of high-resolution images and videos through the Internet. Very often, they are including testimonials about tourist experiences. In many cases, online users are accessing and reading consumer reviews and ratings before choosing which places to visit, to stay or to eat.

The information that is presented in SNSs can lure social media subscribers to engage in online and offline word-of-mouth publicity with other individuals. Moreover, the attractiveness and appeal of interactive communications can have an impact on the individuals' attitudes towards destinations and on their intentions to visit destinations.

Today, a number of tourism businesses and destination marketing organizations (DMOs) are benefiting from the digital transformation of social media. SNSs are connecting social media subscribers (that may include prospective tourists) to interactive websites and to other links that display promotional content and information on various destinations. They promote tourist attractions, points of interest as well as their amenities. The real time conversation capabilities of the digital media can encourage online users to engage with other online users in public domains. They could even motivate them to travel and to book their itineraries and hotel accommodation.

A relevant review from the marketing literature suggests that there are a number of studies that investigated the individuals' perceptions on the use of interactive websites like social media. Many researchers reported that online users are experiencing their dynamic engagement facilities.

SNSs facilitate instantaneous multi-directional flows of information. They enable interactive communications that are conspicuous with a continuous exchange of information, immediacy, responsiveness and user control functions such as participation and timely feedback. DMOs and destination marketers are using these media to respond to online users to assist them in their queries, in real-time. They are also utilizing social media

to engage in online conversations with prospective tourists and to encourage their followers to share their user-generated content.

Past research explored the online users' perceptions and attitudes on the use of social media for destination marketing. In many cases, commentators reported that SNSs enable synchronous communications, concurrent engagement and facilitate real-time conversations that are central to the concept of interactivity, and can affect the individuals' attitudes, and intentions to use them. Some academic authors sought to understand their impact on the individuals' intentions and behaviors, including on their word-of mouth activities.

In this light, the researchers put forward a research model that hypothesizes that the attractiveness of the online content and the interactive capabilities of social media groups can have significant effects on the individuals' attitudes, intentions to use them and social facilitation behaviours. This study differentiates itself from previous theoretical underpinnings. To the best of the authors' knowledge, there are no other studies in academia that have integrated the same measures that were used in this research.

Notwithstanding, for the time being, there are limited studies in academia that shed light on the antecedents of social facilitation behaviors through interactive channels or via offline settings. Therefore, this research addresses this gap in the literature. This contribution clarifies that SNSs that can ultimately foster positive social facilitation behaviors. It adds value to the relevant academic literature that is focused on interactive social media content. In sum, it postulates that social media communications compel subscribers to engage with appealing content (by using a number of emojis to indicate their reactions and/or by cross posting) as well as with other individuals including group administrators and other followers, who are involved in online conversations.

Digital marketing has been investigated by previous studies such as Chaffey(2011), Yasmin et al (2015), Waghmare (2012), Gangeshwer (2013), Kumar and Jincy(2017) and

Lies(2019). Yasminnet al. (2015) conducted a research which was on the effectiveness of digital marketing in the challenging age. The study used correlation analysis and found that the elements of digital marketing such as online marketing and social media marketing are highly positively correlated to sales increase.

Yasmin et al. (2015) highlighted that there are many advantages that digital marketing can bring to customers which are: stay updated with products or services, greater engagement, clear information about products and services, easy comparison with others, 24/7 shopping, share content of the products or services, apparent pricing and enables instant purchase. According to Yasmin et al. (2015), digital marketing has seven elements which are online advertising, e-mail marketing, social media marketing, text messaging, affiliate marketing, search engine optimization and pay per click.

Bang and Roos (2014) examined digital marketing by concentrating on digital marketing strategy with manufacturing industries using a qualitative approach and found that small- and medium-sized companies mostly use homepage as a digital channel.

In 2018, Bala and Verma did a critical review of digital marketing to identify current and future trends in marketing for India. The study found that there is a radical change toward digitalization whereby consumers are looking and searching more on internet to find best deals. Furthermore, Bala and Verma (2018) argued that knowing which social media sites a company's target market utilizes is another key factor in guaranteeing that online marketing will be successful. Other scholars investigated social media marketing and found that in tourism particularly in winery, most owners recognize the social, economic and emotional benefits of social media but not using its full potential because of barriers like time-consuming nature of social media (Canovi and Pucciarelli, 2019).

The internet penetration rate (% population) in Africa by June 30, 2019 indicated 39.8 percent which is 525,148,631 users compared to 4,514,400 users in 2000 with Facebook subscription of 204,304,118 in December 2018 (Internet World Stats, 2019). In addition, 525,148,631 internet users in Africa represent 11.9 percent of the world's internet users. On the one hand, the world total average penetration rate is 57.3 percent which is 4,422,494,622 users and 2,199,428,570 Facebook subscribers in December (Internet World Stats, 2019).

Digital statistics by Digital Odyssey (2019) show that one of the top digital marketing trends in Nigeria for 2019 is 17m active mobile social users implying potential business opportunities to explore customers with mobile marketing using mobile advertising since 50 percent of Nigeria's population use smartphones. Past studies have mentioned that mobile technology allows consumers to access hotel websites in a variety of ways and through a variety of devices (Murphy et al., 2016; Smith, 2017; Ukpabi and Karjaluoto, 2017) emphasized on the need to improve load times to capture potential customers who access hotel websites so that the time to load hotel websites is not long. In general, 80 percent of Africans use mobile phones (The Global Digital Report, 2019).

Similarly, further literature on digital marketing continues to be connected to the concept of SME in the study by (Pradhan et al, (2018) which was done in India. Pradhan et al, (2018) advocated that there is a need to conduct research to investigate the opportunities created by digital marketing. Therefore, in view of the recommendations by Pradhan et al, (2018) this study contributes to expanding literature on digital marketing by exploring digital marketing in relation to tourism with a focus on opportunities for Pakistan. In exploring digital marketing in relation to tourism, this study specifically examined social media marketing in relation to tourist arrivals.

3.4.3. Marketing of Destination

This part of the literature review will delve into several of the destination theories. In order to understand the concept of destination marketing, it is important to understand the meaning of destination and its development process.

3.4.3.1. Destination

Destination is a common word, used widely used in the fields of tourism, planning and development and marketing. It can be found in various avenues, specifically, in the context of tourism in several dimensions and regional stages.

For instance, as Framke (2001) explains, a static destination exists in relation to a person's stay in a specific location, whereas dynamic destinations is a reason for a holiday and is thus linked to networks in the tourism industry. Geogulas (2001) describes destination as *"Tourism as an industry occurs at destination areas with different natural and/or man-made features, which attract non local visitors (or tourists) for a variety of activities"*. He goes on to link it with Cohen's (1974) tourist research stating certain tourists with certain demands, shape the destination. Medlik and Burkart (1974) define destination as "this geographical unit visited by a tourist may be a self contained centre, a village or a town or a city, a district or a region, an island, a country or a continent". As per their definition, a geographical element can be described as a tourist destination. A tourist destination defined geographically can provide appropriate focus on investigation of the tourist effort and its impact and importance. The significance of a tourist destination can be measure through the following three factors; **accessibility**, **attractions** and **facilities**, which can be characterised as tourist talents of a destination. Baerenholdt (2001) states that transport, infrastructure, attractions, amenities, and tourism organisations must be established at a destination.

Morrison and Mill (1992) state that they think of destinations as a part of the tourism process. They define destination as "at a destination there is a mix of independent elements". The elements are different and independent, as in order to create a satisfying

tourist experience, all elements must be present. A destination is made up of various elements; infrastructure, transport, facilities, recreational opportunities and attraction. Morrison and Mill (1992) do not mention anything regarding the geographical aspects of the destination, neither about the behaviour of tourists at location. Cooper et al (1993) define destination as “the destination represents the *raison d’être* for tourism; it is the reason for travelling, and the attractions at the destination generate the visit”. Therefore, certain qualities in a tourist destination make visitors want to visit the destinations, and generates supply and demand, which results in change in a destinations’ structure and sometimes character, and the change is the aim for development planning (Lubbe, 2003). Another definition of tourist destination is that of Jensen(1993), “the definition of a tourist destination is a geographical area, which contains landscape and cultural characteristics and which is in the position to offer a tourism product”. Jensen et al focus on the geographical aspect of a destination, which makes visitors visit it and satisfy their touristic desires, and therefore, the visitor is only seen as a consumer. In 1997, Jensen et al defined the destination as “a system consisting of three resource bases: the attraction base, the facility base and the market base”. In 2001 Jensen defined the concept of destination as a tool to inspect a tourists’ demands in depth, as a potential reason to make changes at destinations and so develop a dynamic destination. Jensen concludes by saying that “it is characteristic for the tourism sector that firms creating economic and job effects are part of a bigger totality”. Jensen’s extensive research based on destinations provides a great understanding of the dynamics resulted by tourist demands for the possible resource based opportunities, and therefore the providers are able to create new enticing products.

Sociologically a destination could be defined as “a tourist attraction is an empirical relationship between a tourist, site and a market” (MacCannell, 1976). MacCannell sfurther adds “the touristic value of a modern community lies in the way it organises social, historical, cultural and natural elements into a steam of impression”. He implies that a tourist destination could easily be judged by how well it is preserved by the local community. Additionally “ distinctive local attraction contains (just behind, beside or

embedded in the parts presented to the tourists) working offices, shops, services and facilities: often an entire urban structure is operating behind its touristic front". MacCannell further states that "functioning establishments figure prominently as tourist attraction. Commercial, industrial and business establishments are also basic features of social regions, or they are the first among the elements from which the regions are composed". Although MacCannell does not specifically classify geographical locations, he does imply that features of a destination are the charms of spatial and social procedure. The process is explained as being structural and is not perceived by actions of individuals. "Places come into being through practice, and not just narratives" states Roadman (1992). Tourist networks comprise a collection of several factors such as people, places and products that are bound by a connection. Roadman further states that "an identical of the various spatial networks through which places become diversely constituted advances a progressive notion where places are conceived as 'processes' rather than 'essences'". A place can have many identities and are positioned where various activities take place and a diverse group of people go through on different transport routes (Taji, 2005). Here it is important to mention that Meethan (2001) states "yet the important point here is not so much the physical patterns or typologies of spatial development that can be identified, that is treating space as an abstract and neutral category, but the way in which these spatial patterns interrelate with socio-cultural values and perceptions" as well as "the resort areas developed as a consequence of modernity, and are linked to the process of urbanisation and industrialisation. And the creation of both mass markets and consumption". Therefore, tourist space is viewed as a social production and tourism space as consumption space, wherein all attraction and services are related to tourist wants and demands (Hazbun, 2004).

Agarwal (1992) defines tourist destination as "a mosaic of a variety of products with different lifecycle". Agues & Goncalves (1998) stated that a tourist destination is distinguished from other destination by its cultural, historical, physical and ethnographical characteristics. According to them "a destination must be able to develop one or more of its tourism attractions such as culture, sun and beach, and it would then allow itself to be

considered a composite products". Therefore, a destination is able to individualise and create its own unique identity by promoting and offering a diverse range of services. Additionally, diversity of services and products of a tourist destination allows it to progress in the tourism industry and attract new audience (Taji, 2005).

Due to the success of applying the concept destination in the industrial sector, academics started to dig deeper into the theories of marketing in respect to the needs and wants of tourists and to determine the significance of the destination concept to the demands of tourists through marketing services concerning tourists (Butler, 1980; Alan and Wong, 2004). There has been a rise in usage of services destination marketing which has settled well within the services marketing community.

Destinations must follow four key principles in order to gain competitive advantage; environment should be put before anything else, tourism should be made a chief sector, distribution channels should be strengthened, and creation of a vibrant private sector (Poon, 1993).

Image matter a lot for tourism destinations, it is essential to maintain a positive image. For instance, due to the slanted reputation of Middle Eastern people, the tourism figures declined by 50% in some of the markets. Chon (1991) states that a robust marketing strategy should focus on promoting a safe and positive image of the tourist destinations. Also, people are important resources in tourism marketing policy and it is essential to introduce diversification opportunities to ensure betterment of the destinations (Douglas, 1994). Sirakya (1996) and Laws (1995) have made their contributions to categorise the key components of a destination. Some of those components are infrastructure, transport, culture, environment, costs, recreation and entertainment, architecture and hotels. It is noted that each destination can have different characteristics. The image of a destination (also country) is one of the most significant aspect in determining the success of its tourist

destinations, it is likely that welcoming and friendly locals with high level of literacy will portray a safe and secure image of the country (Dimanche, 2003).

3.4.3.2. Destination Development

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Fig 8. Tourism Development Process (Source: Parikshat et al, 2016)

To be able to construct a conceptual framework for this study, we will have to briefly look into theories of tourism destination development. This step is essential in order to study foundation of the destinations being discussed. The process of development on a tourist destination reflects highly on the brand image of the place.

The image above depicts the process of tourism destination development to tourist destination brand image. There are many steps that need to be taken in order to make a

tourists' experience successful. The development of a tourist destination is categorised in phases (Laws, 1995). 'pre-tourism phase' can be categorised into two sub phases. In the first sub phase, the destination is visited mostly for visiting friends and family or for business. In the second sub-phase, tourism destination providers/developers begin to study trends such as tourists' behaviours in order to attract them to come back, for the attractions that the destinations provide. Changes are made to accommodate the tourists and offer them a memorable experience, this results in development of 'tourism management phase'. The tourism developers and marketers predict the needs and wants of potential tourists and try to come up with appropriate tourism services and products to satisfy their desires and needs. Additionally, the local government authority notices the increase in resident population as the job opportunities and business prospects increase as a result of tourism potential. The influx in residents may lead to changes within the community and may even cause friction with local job seeking people. The overall change in the nature of the destination attracts different types of visitors at different development phases. (Laws, 1995)

Baud-Bovey and Lawson in 1977 developed a tourist development plan which they called Products Analysis Sequence for Outdoor Leisure Procedure (Baud-Bovey & Lawson 1998). Godfrey and Clarke (2000) suggested a 3 step scheme to allow for tourism development. Firstly, marketers and tourism developers are to identify the tourism resources available, secondly; the types of tourists that will be targeted and lastly, both developers and marketers have to come up with strategies to reach out to their target audience to achieve desired results.

Goeldner, McIntosh and Ritchie divided the process of destination development into four phases; a definitional, an analytical, an operational and an implementation phase. Sharpley (2002) described development as "the continuous and positive change in the economic, social, political and cultural dimensions of the human condition, guided by the principle of freedom of choice and limited by the capacity of the environment to sustain such change". This highlights that when developing a destination it needs to be acknowledged that the

process is heavily layered. Thus, the developers should look at not only the economic aspects of tourism but also at social, political and cultural aspects.

As Schluter (1998) states tourism isn't only beneficial for economy but also for the development of the destination. To become a successful destination, the infrastructure and facilities need to be improved constantly. For tourism providers, capable staff recruitment and retention plays a key role in keeping the businesses afloat. Furthermore, tourism providers and developers need to promote the destination to create a positive image of that attracts target audience. Baloglu and McCleary (1999) state that if information provided to market the destination is plenty, it will contribute greatly in shaping a positive image of the destination. They also state that word-of-mouth marketing is the best way in creating a destination image in the minds of potential tourists and, therefore, providing a positive experience to tourists is essential to keep the chain moving.

3.4.3.3. Destination Image

Destination image can be defined as “impressions of a place or perceptions of an area” (Echtner & Ritchie, 2003). Definitions of destination image have been proposed by many authors since the early works of Boulding (1956) and Martineau (1958), who suggested that human behavior is susceptible to perceived image rather than an objective reality. Destination image can be viewed as a compilation of beliefs, ideas, expectations and impressions accumulated as a result of evaluations of individual attributes at a destination (Crompton, 1979; Dichter, 1985; Kim and Richardson, 2003). Recent researchers appear to concur destination image has two major components, that is, cognitive and affective image (Greaves and Skinner, 2010). Cognitive image represents the beliefs or knowledge a tourist holds of the characteristics and attributes of a destination (Govers *et al.*, 2007; Pike and Ryan, 2004; Zhang *et al.*, 2014), whereas affective image refers to feelings or emotional responses conjured by a destination (Baloglu and Brinberg, 1997; Baloglu and

McCleary, 1999). Accordingly, overall image can be constructed by combining these two factors (Frías *et al.*, 2008).

Some attempts have been made to address the relationship between event quality and destination image. For example, Moon *et al.* (2011) examined the theoretical relationship between event quality at an international sporting event and destination image, and argued event quality perceptions, particularly of intangible factors, contributes to forming positive destination image. Moon *et al.* (2013) tested links between event quality, perceived value and behavioral intention, and confirmed event quality is associated with destination image.

Likewise, Tosun *et al.* (2015) indicated that destination service quality has a positive and significant effect on the perception of the destination's affective image.

Since tourism industry has seen a significant growth in recent times, it has paved way for short term movements of tourists and visitors away from their homes. This practice of tourism has had highly positive impacts, wherein it has helped create jobs and allowed for foreign exchange to develop the country economically (Hall *et al.*, 2014). The tourist destinations tend to invest capital in aid of promoting local culture and history and improve infrastructure, technology and research to further develop the region (Tello *et al.*, 2010). Lopez *et al.* (2015) suggest that the investment helps in generating value for consumers and provides tourist satisfaction and eventually helps in further development of the destination. Tourists and visitors, visiting a destination, expect their stay to be distinctive and pleasurable and for that purpose it is significant to research the tourist market, as a developing economic activity and essential to investigate the needs and wants of the tourists (Garcia, 2006). The perception of the image and image of a destination to a visitor is etched into the destinations brand value, and thus becomes a characteristic of development, economically and marketing, with the latter generating a positive perception in the minds of visitors, which is then transformed in the interest in tourist demands that have led to various studies being undertaken aiding in behavioural models development (Radu & Dobrescu, 2014).

Gunn (1972) was one of the first scholar to shed light on the subject of image formation, his research he explored two dimensions of the image formation process; the “induced image” and the “organic image”,. The latter is assumed to be one that forms from uncontrollable and non commercial sources such as friends and family opinions, newspapers, news, and other reports. Whereas the induced image is one generated through commercial efforts, such as marketing strategies of organisations to promote destinations (Gartner, 2007).

3.4.3.4. Destination Personality:

Destination Personality can be described as brand personality in the context of tourism (Baloglu & Usakli, 2011). Ekinici & Hosany (2006) *define destination personality as "the set of personality traits associated with a destination"*. Destination personality is a considerably new feature within tourism marketing research, destination image has been under investigation since the 1970s. Destination Personality is widely accepted as a vital element in affecting tourists' intentions (Baloglu & Usakli, 2011). Baloglu & Usakli state that it can be assumed that destination personality can have a positive influence on tourists intentions to repeat their visit and recommend the destination to their friends and family. Another study by Suphellen & Helgenson (2004) concluded that brand personality had positive influence on customer's intention to visit and revisit.

Destination features and high tourism takings are correlated through biodiversity of the destination, it is reported to have influenced the economic growth in the destination. Although not directly affected, it was noted that the natural characteristics of a destination (scenery, greenery, wildlife etc) were contributing factors towards higher spending levels, specifically from inbound tourism (Vietze & Freytag, 2005). Therefore, it is essential to maintain the features of a destination. David (2011) states that maintaining and protecting the biodiversity of a destination ensures future tourism sustainability.

Mass tourism has it's pros and cons, influx of tourists can prove to be harmful for a destination but at the same time helpful in generating a steady income from those tourists.

(Alun et al, 2011). Destinations that are heavily developed are normally able to recover from damages caused to tourism facilities as inflow of cash enables them to invest in those destinations (Telfer & Sharpley, 2015). This might not be possible for destinations in developing countries, as there might be a shortage of funds and also tourism protection might not be on the governments agenda (Hawkins, 2006).

3.4.3.5. Marketing of Destinations

Marketing of a destination is a significantly new field within tourism marketing. Marketing destination emerged from improved marketing processes models including the prediction of marketing phenomenon (Sawhney, 1998).

Crompton (1992) mentions “Each destination offers a variety of tourism products and services to attract visitors and each tourist has an opportunity to choose from a set of destinations”. factors such as income, age, distance, cost, risk and intentions may have an affect on destination choice. Destination references and characteristics can be matched with specific demographic profiles of tourists. For instance, escape relacing group entails destinations with opportunities for water sports, upbeat nightlife, ample shopping opportunities, and other entertainment options (Moscardo, 1996).

Crouch and Ritchie (1999) developed a destination planning model titled destination competitiveness model. The model demonstrations comparative and competitive advantage, wherein comparative advantage entails destination factor endowments, and competitive advantage presents a destinations capability to use it’s resources efficeiently over a long period of time. A successful destination offers high levels of customer service and excellent facilities, accommodation and entertainment opportunities with the destinations unique culture. Destination development has to have some important features to attract international interest to the location, those features depened upon a specific location. Branding is a powerful tool within marketing to deal with rivalry and substituatability (Dimanche, 2003). Therefore, Alan (2003) suggests that research on

destination development shows that businesses need to categorise destinations that can be promoted through marketing strategies.

Globalisation has made travelling internationally accessible to people all over the world. Tourism destinations are becoming highly competitive. Tourism providers and organisations are keen to attract tourists and explorers from every segment and therefore, employ a variety of marketing tools and adopt branding initiatives such as catchy taglines and eye catching logos (Pike & Ryan, 2004). Tourism destinations like to become distinct to gain attention of their target audience and therefore, form a Destination Personality.

According to Sriram et al (1995) “Different destination marketing strategies are used by companies which export their destination marketing to developing countries opposed to those which market their destination to developed countries”, they imply that different marketing strategies are used to target developing countries and the reason could be cultural and historical relations, or just because there is less risk of political issues. Any issues arised could be due to lack of knowledge of other markets’ needs and wants and their culture. Therefore, any organisation planning to enter into a new market should focus on research on the country’s culture and history.

Destination marketing is a marketing approach in the travel industry that involves promoting a specific location and its benefits instead of the product or service that a company offers. This could be a country, a town or city, or even a specific holiday resort or attraction. The purpose of destination marketing is to increase customer awareness of a certain destination so that they start to think about visiting, or to help them remember the location when they are ready to book a holiday. By slipping in subtle calls to action and mentions of a brand’s offering, the idea is that potential customers will decide to book a holiday to that destination through the company that is promoting it.

Destination marketing is also often used by the tourist boards of certain countries or regions as a way to try and bring more visitors to the area to boost the local economy and establish

themselves as a desirable holiday destination. The main aim of destination marketing is to make the customer aware of and interested in the target location before they arrive. You want to spark an emotional desire to see and experience the place you are offering, as this makes the likelihood of paying for a holiday much higher. One of the key benefits of destination marketing is that it tends to use an emotional hook to engage potential customers, which leads to much higher conversion rates. The whole approach is about selling the experience and benefits of a location by showing customers what their travel experience could be like if they visit, encouraging people to imagine a holiday there and planting a seed of intrigue in their minds.

Conclusion

This chapter has intended to provide a literary basis to conceptual framework for this research. The literature above will be used to identify independent and dependant variables, for instance, as per the literature above it is evident that creation of a ‘destination’ is not a simple task. Destination creators have to go through a series of stringent steps to ensure a brand is created, and due to external factors and variables occasionally destinations fail to bring those efforts to fruition. This research will address those ecternal as well as internal factors, and will also provide recommendation as to how to address those issue.

4. Chapter 4: Conceptual Framework

Introduction:

Conceptual framework refers to what is expected to be found through a research work. It draws out relevant variables and maps out the relationship between them. A conceptual framework visually illustrates the of expectated results from different variables(Muller &

Seuring, 2008). A conceptual framework is mainly used to draw up theories and arrive at a hypothesis.

In the context of tourism, the act of acknowledging the significance of satisfaction in forecasting tourist behaviour intentions, many researches have pursued to inspect into the relationship between different variables. For instance, the relationship between level of satisfaction of a tourist with a destination and their intention to repeat the visit to the destination is embedded in destination choice set theory (Crompton, 1992). Tourists tend to select destination that they think will best satisfy their wants and desires. Stylos et al (2017), argue that visitors' intention to return can also be predicted through the degree to which they believe the destination will satisfy their needs.

Even though the positive influence of satisfaction of a destination on tourists intention to repeat visit has been solid, destination experience can be tricky and complex with many elements to it (Milman and Pizam, 1993). Sureshchandar et al (2002) state that using a factor specific tactic to measure satisfaction and perceive it as a multi-dimensional concept, it is highly significant to comprehend what aspects of destination satisfaction help gather approving behaviours.

Many studies performed in the past have focused their attention on various destination satisfaction elements, such as the shuttle service (Loi et al, 2017), observed risks (Chen et al, 2017), memorable experiences (Kim et al, 2017) and public transport (Schofield and Thompson, 2007). It turns out that transport does not have a direct impact on tourists satisfaction by Schofield & Thompson (2017 and Zhang et al (2017) showed that there is some link between transport related services and tourist satisfaction.

Crompton (1992) and Cooper et al (1998) say that tourism literature emphasises the importance of both pull and push factors in shaping tourist motivations and in choosing the vacation destination. Uysal and Hagan (1993) argue that pull factors are mainly related to the attractiveness of a given destination and tangible characteristics such as: accommodation, culture and historical resources, recreation facilities and beaches. The

destination choice process might, therefore, be related to the tourist's assessment of destination attributes and their perceived utility values, while, push factors are origin-related and refer to the essential desires of the individual traveller, e.g. the desire for escape, adventure, health or prestige, rest and relaxation.

4.1. Research Variables:

The following independent research variables have been identified through literature review and a framework has been developed to demonstrate a possible link between the variables and tourist satisfaction.

No.	Label	Independent Variables
1.	V1	Favourable country image
2.	V2	Friendliness of local people
3.	V3	Recreational opportunities
4.	V4	Feeling of Personal Safety
5.	V5	Easy access to information
6.	V6	Presentation of cultural heritage
7.	V7	Value for money

Figure 9: Conceptual Framework

4.2. Hypothesis formation:

Hypothesis were formed to investigate a positive link between dependant and independant variables and desired outcome. Hypotheses will be tested through the Pearson correlation.

Country Image: Martin and Eroglu (1993) define country image as “The total of all descriptive, inferential and imfornational beliefs one has about a particular country”. Kotler, Rein and Haider define country image as “the sum of all those emotional, and aesthetic qualities such as experience, beliefs, ideas, recollections and impressions, that a person has of a place”. These definitions state that country image is formed by personal perceptions that an individual has about a country. It is likely that a social image of a country can be developed through a use of common languages and experiences. In existing marketing literature, image occurs from perceptions people hold of a place (Papadopoulus, 1993). It is highly importance to give importance to a country’s image as it forms an opinion in the minds of potential tourists and helps them decide to visit it (Hunt, 1975).

H1: Favourable country image perceived through a positive destination experience has a direct positive affect on tourist satisfaction.

Friendliness of local people: Lee (2013) states that tourism development brings about many environmental, socio-economic and socio-cultural changes to a community, some more appreciated than the others. Therefore, it is absolutely essential that they participate and provide their support in successfully sustaining of the tourism industry at the destination (Chi, et al, 2010). Destination image, to alter tourists’ perceptions, has been given much attention, whereas residents’ perceptions and understadings of the destinations have been very little consideration. Few studies exist where residents image of the destination has been analysed, however, very few studies exist where the influence of those perceptions has been investigated (Ramkissoon & Nunkoo, 2011). Local community support and goodwill is vital for the success of tourism development projects, understading of local views and opinions should be of upmost priority for the government, local

businesses and policymakers (Lee, 2013). Friendliness and welcoming nature of the local community makes tourists comfortable in a destinations specially if it's their first visit (Biran, et al 2014).

H2: Friendliness of local people perceived through a positive destination experience has a direct positive affect on tourist satisfaction.

Recreational opportunities: Recreational opportunities could include private recreations such as a holiday home, quasi public resources, public owned recreation such as public parks, theme parks, museums, sports related avenues. Cultural resources are also important as tourists like learning and experiencing different cultures, cultural recreation opportunities could be religious shrines, historical buildings and arts exhibitions (Petrosillo et al, 2007). Prey and Marcouiller (2005) concluded in their study that an amalgamation of recreational sites and natural amenities are influential in satisfying leisure-based wants and needs. Recreational opportunities could be ranging from biophysical resources to manmade facilities. Tourism resources contribute towards development of a tourism destination. It is essential for a tourist destination to have a range of recreation options to pick from as the destination with a myriad of opportunities becomes very appealing to tourists.

H3: Recreational opportunities perceived through a positive destination experience has a direct positive affect on tourist satisfaction.

Feeling of personal safety: Safety and security, in tourism context, are a particularly important topic worldwide. Providing a feeling of personal safety is an essential requirement in tourism. A tourism destination's success can often be judged by its ability to be a safe and secure location for tourists, more than economic success. Any crime, small or large, committed against foreign tourists is highly publicised in international news and has the potential to destroy a destination's reputation which could lead to a decline in number of visitors (Batra, 2011). A widely publicised incident can present a significant blow to a destination's image (Ryan, 1993). Hence, it is essential that visitors are kept safe

from crimes of any nature. Personal safety is a key element in decision making process by which a potential visitor makes their choice of travel (Pearce, 1988). It is also significant that tourists are informed pre-visit regarding potential risks to reduce distress of potential incidents (Mawby, 2000)

H4: Feeling of personal safety perceived through a positive destination experience has a direct positive effect on tourist satisfaction.

Easy access to information: Tourist choices and levels of satisfaction impacted by information needs has two conditions; local community and tourism providers need to have awareness of information needs (Gursoy and McCleary, 2004), and second is development of sustainable communication and information modes that will accomplish individual needs (Allison, 2000).

It is significant for destination managers to make tourist destinations accessible to everyone. A research states that 83% of people look for information use destination websites/social pages. However, a mere 39% of those people find information they were looking for. The better the availability of relevant information, the likely are chances of visitors making an informed decision to visit. making destination accessible through information will likely attract more visitors, repeat booking as well as word of mouth promotion (Miller et al, 2008).

H5: easy access to information perceived through a positive destination experience has a direct positive affect on tourist satisfaction.

Presentation of local culture: Culture can be one of the most importance factors for tourists when choosing a destination (Ferradeira et al, 2013). Cultural tourism is omnipresent and somewhat seems to have become omnipotent. Due to substantial interest in cultural tourism, it has been embraced by various countries globally. UNESCO promotes cultural and heritage tourism as a means to preserve world heritage sites and EU Commision supports it as a major industry on it's own(Richards, 2007). Cultural tourism

is everywhere as every country has a culture, but in this context cultural tourist refers to destinations that have a rich history and world heritage sights. Methan states that cultural tourism is different wherein it involves delving deeper into a destination's culture rather than experiencing idle leisure. One collects an in-depth knowledge of the culture in the process (2001).

H6: presentation of local culture perceived through a positive destination experience has a direct positive affect on tourist satisfaction.

Value for money: Many travelers want to visit new destinations and try out different things, and squeeze their budgets to make that possible. In a report by ABTA Travel Trends, it was revealed that holidays are a priority for UK travelers, despite wider economic issues. The report reports that 3 in 10 people planned to spend more amount, than before, in the coming years. It was also revealed that people prioritise travel over other leisures, such as movies and eating out. 70% of people studied believe that tourist providers should make sure their businesses help local people and economy (ABTA, 2018).

Tourist will choose destinations that offer the most value for their money, any destination that does not offer that will have a less chance of being visited again. All inclusive holidays are becoming common now as many people tend to think that they offer the best value for money. In tourism context, value for money refers to the price as well as the quality of the products and services provided. Good value and lower prices are important factors for tourists of today, visitors want more for less (Ronakld, 2017).

H7: value for money perceived through a positive destination experience has a positive affect on tourist satisfaction

Positive destination experience: Tourist experience seals the fate of a particular destination tourists want to see something unique and familiarise themselves with the destination so it can become memorable (Doway, 2019). Positive destination experience leads to the tourists being satisfied with their trip. As suggested in H1-H7, the independent

variables are crucial in achieving positive destination experience, and achieving positive destination experience leads to tourist satisfaction.

H8: Positive destination experience has a significant impact on tourist satisfaction.

Conclusion

This main purpose of this chapter was to introduce a framework using concepts and empirical findings from the existing literature. A conceptual framework is used to show the connection between those ideas and how they relate to the study. This chapter drew up a framework based on independent variables such as feeling of personal safety, value for money, presentation and preservation of local culture, easy access to information, recreational opportunities, friendliness of local people, and favourable country image. These independent variables when combined lead to a 'positive destination experience', which results in tourist satisfaction.

5. Chapter 5: Research Methodology

5.1. Introduction

Research in simple words can be described as a search for knowledge. Research is a process of seeking relevant information on a specific subject applying scientific and systematic ways. Research methodology can be described as process of collecting data to carry out research on a specific topic. It is used to obtain results of a given problem on a specific matter which is often referred to as a research problem. According to Redman and Mory research is a “systematised effort to gain new knowledge”.

This chapter aims to define the different types of research methodologies used in researches of this caliber and state the methods that were used in this study. To achieve the objectives that were set out earlier in the study, alternative methodologies of research are observed to select the most suitable approaches. Previous studies, field and empirical, on the subject are also relied upon to gain valid results. Various methods of research such as quantitative, qualitative and mixed method are used in the use of questions, collected data and analysis of a case study of the subjective research (Meaner, 2005; Fallon & Schofield, 2006). The empirical part of this study is conducted through a field study, applied through the use of survey questionnaires and interviews. The quantitative part of the study was achieved through the use of survey questionnaires and qualitative part was conducted through interviews to answer research questions.

This chapter lists different types of philosophical perspectives, describes different types of research methods. It also discusses types of qualitative and quantitative methods, and the hypothesis formulation process, different ways of collecting data and the empirical process of research; distribution of survey questionnaires and interview selection process.

5.2. Research Objectives

Tourism industry in Pakistan has been fluctuating in the last decades, however, it has been growing somewhat gradually and holds great potential. The goal is to help establish the reasons as to why Pakistan is not achieving steady growth in tourism sector. The research objectives are outlined below;

- 1. To investigate the relationship between destination marketing and tourist satisfaction in context of Pakistan tourism industry.**
- 2. To investigate the current destination marketing practices employed by tourism providers in Pakistan.**
- 3. To provide strategic recommendations to enhance business performance to ensure high levels of tourist satisfaction.**

5.3. Research Questions

- 1. What is the relationship between destination marketing and tourist satisfaction in the context to Pakistan tourism industry?**
- 2. What are the current destination marketing practices employed by Pakistan tourism providers?**
- 3. What strategic recommendations can be provided to enhance business performance to ensure high levels of tourist satisfaction?**

5.4. Defining the research problem:

Alan Bryman states “A research problem is a definite or clear expression [statement] about an area of concern, a condition to be improved upon, a difficulty to be eliminated, or a troubling question that exists in scholarly literature, in theory, or within existing practice that points to a need for meaningful understanding and deliberate investigation. A research problem does not state how to do something, offer a vague or broad proposition, or present a value question” (2007). Every problem requires a solution and with the help of a clear statement of problem it is easier to work out a solution.

5.5. Philosophical Approaches

5.5.1. Deductive Approach

Deductive approach to a research has been used considerably and is mostly associated with logical positivism. Deductive reasoning is commonly linked to hypothetico-deductive approach; wherein a specific hypothesis is formed based on current literature and practical knowledge. The hypothesis is then tested and if it is supported by the collected data, it is said to hold in the context. If the findings do not support the deductive approach is mostly linked to scientific research, however, it also supports other researches such as meta and systematic analysis.

Fig 10. Deductive Approach (Source: Dudovskiy, 2018)

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5.6. Research Philosophies

5.6.1. Positivism

The fundamental idea of positivism is that all reliable knowledge is based on positive information gained from observations, which implies that only analytical statements are considered true through reasoning alone. Following are the 6 rules of positivist approach; Phenomenalism; the only valid information is gained through observations, Atomism; things are read by reducing them in smaller parts, Scientific laws; science is meant to create generalised laws, Nominalism; in science, words have a single meaning and no

descriptions, Naturalism; social sciences should use the principle of natural sciences, and Facts and values; science is based on facts and not values.

Positivism pursues empirical consistencies that correlate between two variables. This allows for definite laws and predictions. Lee (1989) states that it is assumed by positivist researchers that reality is objectively given and can be defined by measurable properties independent of the observer. Positivistic researchers generally test theories in order to increase the predictive understanding of the phenomenon in question.

Positivism, as a philosophy, tends to believe that only factual knowledge that is gathered through observation is reliable. In a positivist study the role of author is limited to collection and interpretation of data, in an objective sense. Therefore, in positivist researches, the findings are quantifiable and objective. Quantifiable observations, that positivism depends upon, lead to statistical analysis. It is said of positivist studies that “as a philosophy, positivism is in accordance with the empiricist view that knowledge stems from human experience. It has an atomistic, ontological view of the world as comprising discrete, observable elements and events that interact in an observable, determined and regular manner” (Collins, 2010).

5.7. Sampling

Random sampling: Random sampling is perhaps the most common and easiest way of sampling. In random sampling each participant of of population is likely to be equally chosen as part of sampling. Preferably in random sampling a sample size of a few hundred is required in order for researcher to apply simple sampling fittingly (Saunders & Thornhill, 2012).

Purposeful Sampling: Purposeful sampling, which is also known as selective sampling, is a process of selecting participants wherein researchers rely on their own judgement when choosing interviewees to participate in their research.

Stratified sampling: If the population from which a sample is to be drawn does not constitute a homogeneous group, then stratified sampling technique is applied to obtain a representative sample. In this technique, the population is stratified into several nonoverlapping subpopulations or strata and sample items are selected from each stratum. If the items selected from each stratum is based on simple random sampling the entire procedure, first stratification and then simple random sampling, is known as stratified random sampling (Pelissier, 2008). This method of sampling will be applied when collecting quantitative data in forms of survey questionnaires. In this instance the targeted audience belongs to various countries and backgrounds therefore application of this method is essential to obtain unbiased and accurate results.

Deliberate sampling: Deliberate sampling is also known as purposive or non-probability sampling. This sampling method involves purposive or deliberate selection of particular units of the universe for constituting a sample which represents the universe. When population elements are selected for inclusion in the sample based on the ease of access, it can be called convenience sampling. Deliberate sampling was applied when conducting face to face interviews with touristic organisations. Organisations were selected on the basis of success of their business in providing successful trips to touristic areas in Pakistan to various segments of targeted audiences.

5.8. Research Types

5.8.1. Quantitative Research

Quantitative research consists use of structured questions where the response options are fixed and a number of respondents are involved. Kaplan and Duchon (1988) describe quantitative research as a statistically reliable method which is measured in number. Quantitative research is aimed at determining a relationship between one factor and another such as dependant and independent variables.

Qualitative research is an approach for exploring and understanding the meaning individuals or groups ascribe to a social or human problem. The process of research

involves emerging questions and procedures, data typically collected in the participant's setting, data analysis inductively building from particulars to general themes, and the researcher making interpretations of the meaning of the data. The final written report has a flexible structure. Those who engage in this form of inquiry support a way of looking at research that honours an inductive style, a focus on individual meaning, and the importance of rendering the complexity of a situation.

Quantitative research is an approach for testing objective theories by examining the relationship among variables. These variables, in turn, can be measured, typically on instruments, so that numbered data can be analysed using statistical procedures. The final written report has a set structure consisting of introduction, literature and theory, methods, results, and discussion. Like qualitative researchers, those who engage in this form of inquiry have assumptions about testing theories deductively, building in protections against bias, controlling for alternative explanations, and being able to generalize and replicate the findings.

- Questionnaire Design

Empirical research shows that survey method uses questionnaires to gather data. Therefore, questionnaires play a significant role in the entire process of survey method. It is highly important that all aspects of the research are executed well and a good sampling method is employed and effective planning is carried out, as well as well thought out and planned interviews with sufficient level of statistical analysis is executed. Although, if a questionnaire is not effectively designed, all of the above will not work. Simply put, if a questionnaire is poorly executed, planned and has inadequate questions, it will fail to answer research questions.

In this case, a poorly designed questionnaire will lead the researcher towards incorrect and misleading information. For that reason, many researchers and scholars stress the

importance of a well planned questionnaire design, which is based on the objectives and reason of the research being carried out. The questionnaire should reflect and address the research aims and objectives.

As mentioned by Hair et al (2008) in their study about the objectives of questionnaires, they are designed to change the information required into a set of particular investigative questions that the sample of the study is likely to answer. These questions are required to provide information regarding research questions that help attain the research objectives.

It is vital that the questionnaire be designed in a way that will encourage the respondent to happily provide requested information and willingly take part in the survey.

Markedly, this includes a trade-off or the kind of exchange between the researchers and respondents. And those who agreed to be compensated can be offered a reward by the researcher. This can include payment or any gift in return of their true opinion and time.

It is essential that the researcher conveys their appreciation to the respondents as they approach them to gather the required information for the research project, which will in turn provide valuable information needed to carry out the research process effectively. This helps in conveying researchers appreciation and importance of the study being undertaken. Below are some aspects of a well executed questionnaire;

- A) A questionnaire decreases the risk of error response, which can happen as a result of improper responses, recordings, or assessments.
- B) One essential part of the questionnaire is the structure, the below steps should be considered for an accurate and productive structure.
- The instructions given with the questionnaires state as to how to approach the respondents.

- To encourage more responses, rewards should be adequately conveyed to them. This will motivate them to carry on to the process.
- One of the most significant aspect of the whole process is the relationship between each question and the research objectives. Some scholars can be prone to add irrelevant questions that may be off putting for respondents as they can be very time consuming. This can divert attention away from the main aim of the research, which can be futile for the scholar.
- Design stage of the questionnaire should include steps for data analysis.
- Data analysis steps to include in the design phase
- Links between questions and appropriate statistical tests that can provide adequate answers to the questions
- Evaluation measure to be created in parallel with the design
- Specific research needs and focus based on data collected by other researchers/market demands
- Specific information to include at the design stage as it is necessary to review the problem and research approach as reflected in research questions/hypothesis
- Dummy tables are suggested to help cataloguing data and reflect how the data is to be evaluated
- Identify target population and their attributes clearly

Figure 11; questionnaire design process

In this study, a questionnaire was designed and administered to tourists who were undertaking tours and travel at the time of questionnaire being distributed to them. This helped them to pass their time regardless of them getting bored. The survey was self-administered and used a five-point Likert scale with a range of 1 to 5. (1 strongly disagree,

2, disagree, 3 neutral, 4 agree, 5 strongly agree). The method proposed by McDaniel and Gates was used to create the questionnaire (2004). The following is how the questionnaire was divided into groups based on the hypotheses and study objectives:

Product features

- a) Convenience
- b) The competence of employees
- c) Pricing
- d) Atmosphere and ambience
- e) Brand image, brand equity

Each question was designed to elicit answers that included the aforementioned variables. To capture the value of expressing feelings about the issues raised, closed-ended response questions were included. All of the inquiries came from secondary information and the interview tapes. According to Cooper and Schindler (2008), the questionnaire's questions can be categorised according to the following:

- f) A dichotomous system gives a sample of the population two options from which they can select one.
- g) b) Multichotomies aim to provide responders with a variety of options.
- h) A checklist is concerned with potential ideas and alternatives to the sample. c) Open ended questions required respondents to respond to the question in their own words without making any mistakes.

Although it's crucial that every question in a questionnaire aims to get the necessary data, some can also include neutral inquiries to establish rapport and give study participants something to look forward to.

A range of queries are required to gather the appropriate information in order to avoid any query that is likely to solve two difficulties at once. Scholars have harshly criticised this, saying that the researcher shouldn't use these questions since they could lead the responder astray. According to Scott and Spell (1998), it's crucial that the researcher simulates the respondent's inability to react or actively works to elicit the response.

It is advised that researchers leave leeway for participants to respond to questions with perfect accuracy or with a reasonable response. This is somewhat implausible because the responder might not be familiar with the study's topic or the study itself, and they might not have had any past experience with surveys like this one. The researcher can find individuals who possess the necessary expertise and screen those who will be employed to collect data by using filter questions. According to empirical data, researchers that provided clues to their respondents were more likely to overcome respondents' inability to respond to the questions. This thesis can apply the same methodology as earlier studies in order to implement the issues raised by the study's respondents. It is also possible that the study's participants will be unable to express their opinions clearly, making it unlikely that they would be able to explain a specific response to the question at hand. In this situation, it is advised that the researcher give the respondents a list of the available options so they can select the ones that best express their sentiments and/or their views or perceptions.

The research must make every attempt to make it as easy as feasible for participants to give the essential data during the question-design phase. The requested data must be wholly pertinent to the research context and validate the research's goal; otherwise, the respondents should be informed of this. Some study topics could be sensitive and give people the idea that their privacy and personal lives are being invaded. It is strongly advised that these inquiries go at the end of the survey rather than the beginning.

Additionally, rather than asking for a specific number, such queries should contain information in the form of ranges (Hair, 2015).

- The Development of the Questionnaire

This study draws its questions from a review of the literature that includes the numerous hypotheses that different academics have used in their individual investigations of the topic. A number of questions that may have been included in the questionnaires from the clients were also raised following the interviews. The questionnaire's opening question was designed to acclimatise the respondents and situate them inside the study's scope. This indicates that it catches their attention and is probably going to pique their curiosity for the remaining questionnaires. The following inquiries were created to satisfy the study's goals and respond to the research hypotheses that informed the investigation.

The questionnaire was formulated in accordance with the research objectives. Each research variable has its own subheading under which 4 to 8 questions are asked. The questions have been structured according to the five-point scale Lickert method, making it easy for respondents to select their answer.

On the first page, there are instructions for answering the questions. The first group of questions are demographic questions, such as gender, age of the respondent, where they live, if they are married, if they are of a certain ethnicity, why they are travelling, and how often they travel each year. These are important questions for this research, which focuses on tourist satisfaction.

Once demographic questions were out of the way, questions with research variables were listed. The variables are listed as below;

The first variable is 'country image' this variable entailed 5 questions.

The second variable is 'friendliness of local people' entailed 4 questions.

The third variable is 'recreational activities' entailed 6 questions.

The fourth variable is 'feeling of personal safety' entailed 7 questions.

The fifth variable is 'easy access to information' entailed 4 questions.

The sixth variable is 'value for money' entailed 6 questions.

The 7th variable is ‘presentation of local culture’ entailed 8 questions.

The 8th variable is ‘positive destination experience’ entailed 8 questions.

In the phase 1, customers were identified and were approached for completing the survey questionnaires by utilizing the distinction of the intercept technique i.e., they were waiting for their respective tour operators to take them on the trip. The researchers were careful as to not to impose responded on their holidays. Respondents were advised to either hand over the filled out questionnaires to the researcher there and then, or to place them in a box supplied to the tour operators. Customers' information was gathered over five days of the week, including weekdays and weekends. The whole process was administered with the help of one research assistant who helped the researcher of this study and executed the data collection process.

5.8.2. Qualitative Research

Qualitative research, on the other hand, is concerned with qualitative phenomenon, i.e., phenomena relating to or involving quality or kind. For instance, when we are interested in investigating the reasons for human behaviour (i.e., why people think or do certain things), we quite often talk of ‘Motivation Research’, an important type of qualitative research. This type of research aims at discovering the underlying motives and desires, using in depth interviews for the purpose. Other techniques of such research are word association tests, sentence completion tests, story completion tests and similar other projective techniques. Attitude or opinion research i.e., research designed to find out how people feel or what they think about a particular subject or institution is also qualitative research. Qualitative research is especially important in the behavioural sciences where the aim is to discover the underlying motives of human behaviour. Through such research we can analyse the various factors which motivate people to behave in a particular manner or which make people like or dislike a particular thing. It may be stated, however, that to apply qualitative research in practice is relatively a difficult job and therefore, while doing such research, one should seek guidance from experimental psychologists. Myers (1999)

describes qualitative research as collecting, analysing and interpreting data by observing people's actions and opinions. He goes on to state that qualitative research is defined as definitions, characteristics, concepts and description of things. Qualitative research revolves around the use of qualitative data such as interviews and observations to understand the social phenomenon. It is a widely used research method (Avison & Myers, 2002).

5.8.3. Mixed Methods

Mixed methods research is an approach to inquiry involving collecting both quantitative and qualitative data, integrating the two forms of data, and using distinct designs that may involve philosophical assumptions and theoretical frameworks. The core assumption of this form of inquiry is that the combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches provides a more complete understanding of a research problem than either approach alone.

Mixed Model Research: Mixed method research, as the name implies, is a mixture of quantitative and qualitative research approach. In that a researchers could conduct a survey and interviews (Palmerino, 1999). One of the main reasons to choose mixed model research is to gain results through both qualitative angle and quantitative angle, as this combination will leave less room for any overlapping weakness.

Case Study Research: The case study method is essentially a detailed study of a particular subject, such as a group of people or an organisation. These types of studies are mainly used in social sciences and business researchers. A case study could be positivist, interpretivist or critical, depending upon the goal of the research (Yin, 2000).

5.9. Formulation of hypothesis

In the formulation process of research hypothesis, deductive reasoning was used to determine if tourist satisfaction was dependant on a number of independant variables. There are eight hypotheses that resulted from the research objectives of this study, country image, friendliness of locals, value for money, feeling of personal safety, easy access to information, recreational opportunities, presentation of local culture and lastly, the impact of positive destination experience. The quantitative research will be analysed through SPSS while the qualitative research will be analysed using thematic analysis.

Validity and Reliability:

It is significant to ensure the validity and reliability of the collected data as it establishes that the data is replicable and sound, and the findings are accurate. If the research is not valid, then it becomes meaningless. Stringent measures were taken to ensure the research meets the validity and reliability criteria. The reliability was tested measured through the Cronbach's alpha test. The validity was measured through Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sample adequacy and Bartlett Test of sphericity.

5.10. Empirical Research Process

5.10.1. Interviews

Face to face interviews are carried in person through a rigid process and the aim is to seek answers to pre-conceived questions. Researcher could either stick to a strict list of questions or let the conversation flow to get a better understanding of the subject under investigation. The outcome largelt depends upon the interviewers capability and experiences. The reason to conduct interviews is to gain first hand knowledge of the research topic as well as to seek answers to questions that haven't been asked before.

This method of data collection involves collecting data over the phone. Telephone interviews aren't very common since the inception of social media, however, these types

of interviews can be very useful when there is a time constraint. Telephone interviews can be used as backup if there isn't sufficient data on the research subject to accomplish research objectives. After the development of research question and objectives, next step is to seek out sources being researched. Individuals from those sources are singled out and contacted to describe their experiences. The selected individuals must be explained the aim of the research and must be ready to share their true feelings (Cohen, 1992). semi-structured interviews are best suited in order to explore personal opinions regarding complex and sensitive issues and allow for further investigation and clarification (Barriball & While, 1993).

Thematic coding is a form of qualitative analysis which involves recording or identifying passages of text or images that are linked by a common theme or idea allowing you to index the text into categories and therefore establish a "framework of thematic ideas about it" (Gibbs 2007). The following data is categorised into themes, some of most common topics appearing in all the interviews were regarding the services that are provided by the participants, marketing of the services and products, distrust of the government, safety and security issues, political situation, infrastructure, and demographics.

5.10.2.Face-to-face interviews

The researcher interviewed managers/owners of tourism providers, the organisations had been successfully operating for a number of years when the interviews took place. All the organisation interviewed had conducted several successful trips to various tourist destination in Pakistan and the interviewees were highly experienced in the field. An invitation for interviews was sent out to 10 organisations in total, out of which four agreed to be interviewed. Three of the interviews were conducted face-to-face on a field visit to Pakistan and the fourth one was conducted over Skype while the researcher was in the UK. Researcher faced limitations which will be discussed towards the end. Interviews were semi-structured to ensure that an informal discussion took place rather than answers to

specific questions. The interviews were analysed using thematic analysis as explained in detail in data analysis chapter.

The main aim of conducting qualitative data in the form of interviews was to gain knowledge about the subject through the perspective of local business owners (tour operators). The benefit of talking one-to-one with the interviewees was the flow of the conversation, wherein the interviewees were able to share their first hand experiences in the field. The interviews were mainly aimed to accomplish the second research objective **“To investigate the current destination marketing practices employed by tourism providers in Pakistan”**. The decision to undertake qualitative data was made once secondary research on Pakistan’s tourism industry was undertaken and researcher struggled to find information on destination marketing practices. The answers to the questions posed by the researcher aim to provide not only up to date information on the subject, but also help in forming future recommendations.

5.10.3. The Questionnaire

Leedy suggests that a questionnaire is a commonly used tool for gathering and observing data that is beyond one’s physical reach (1997). A questionnaire could be open-ended and close-ended, both have limitations; close ended questionnaire is easy to analyse as the responses can be mathematically analysed, however, restricts participant to the options provided. On the other hand, open-ended questionnaire gives participants a chance to include additional information, making the responses detailed, which makes it difficult to computerise (Riley et al, 2000). Many of the questions in the questionnaire are based on nominal and ordinal data and some on lickert scale.

The questionnaire included demographic questions relating to participants’ age, gender, occupation, relationship status, location and ethnicity. Other questions included were regarding peoples’ interests and preferences with regards to tourism and five-point lickert scale questions to assess the satisfaction levels. the questionnaires were posted in social

media groups specifically targeted at tourists who had either visited Pakistan or were anticipating to. The questionnaire was mainly aimed at local and foreign tourists who had been to Pakistan at least once for any purpose. A total of 500 questionnaires were distributed, and 339 usable responses were used for this research. There were an overall 53 statements and the answer range was from ‘strongly agree to strongly disagree’. The questionnaire included a range of statements for each variable to ensure all variables were researched thoroughly.

5.10.4. By observation:

A researcher’s observations play a big role in working towards finding answers to questions. Observations are essential in any type of research as this provides for a second perspective. Observations are mainly useful if data collection through survey questionnaires and interviews is difficult. Although observations are useful in all types of researches as it provides access to people in real life situations. Personal observations provide context and therefore are used in this research. Personal observations were noted during the field visit to Pakistan and have since been incorporated in data analysis.

5.11. Ethical Protocol

The research was fully approved by the university postgraduate school ethics committee. All interview participants were given consent forms to sign and consented to having the interview materials used in this study. Participants were informed that they can withdraw their consent to be included any time, should they wish to do so. The interviewers were also informed that the interviews will be recorded to be analysed later by the researcher. All responses were kept safe in a password protected computer. All quantitative study participants were anonymous and were informed when distributing the surveys. All data collected was free of coercion and participants agreed to contribute with full agreement.

6. CHAPTER 6: DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

6.1. Introduction:

This chapter consists of analysis and findings collected through quantitative and qualitative data. Thematic analysis is useful in breaking down data into code and then those codes are assigned to specific themes. Qualitative data (interviews) collected were analysed through thematic analysis. Quantitative data (survey questionnaires) were analysed through SPSS software. The questionnaire was designed to achieve answers to questions raised in the conceptual framework. The conceptual framework identified dependant and independent variables and through those a strategic framework was formed. Hypotheses were suggested in line with those variables and to test each hypothesis, various questions were asked.

6.2. Quantitative Data:

Reliability Test:

Before proceeding with the analysis of the data, the reliability of the data was measured through Cronbach's Alpha test. This test measures the reliability and hence, it is not a statistical test. It is assumed that the Greater values of Alpha above 0.7 are good and indicate further procession with the analysis. The greater the value the greater is the internal consistency and ability of the items to measure the given construct. The lower values indicate low internal consistency and items are unable to measure the given construct. The following rules guide the Cronbach's Alpha.

1. The values are considered excellent if greater than 0.92.
2. The values are considered good if greater than 0.83.
3. The values are considered acceptable if greater than 0.74.
4. The values are questionable if less than 0.6.
5. The values are unacceptable if less than 0.5.

Case Processing Summary

N

%

Cases	Valid	339	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	339	100.0

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.916	53

The above table shows that the value of Cronbach's Alpha is 0.916 which reflects exceptional reliability of the instrument and all the items measure the construct showing very good internal consistency.

Reliability Statistics			
	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items	Valid
Country Image	0.609	5	100%
Friendliness of Local People	0.626	4	100%
Recreational Activities	0.721	6	100%
Feeling of Personal Safety	0.760	7	100%
Easy Access to Information	0.730	4	100%
Presentation of Local Culture	0.638	6	100%
Value for Money	0.766	8	100%
Positive Destination Experience	0.733	8	100%
Tourist Satisfaction	0.676	5	100%

The above table shows that the Cronbach's Alpha for individual variables is also greater than 0.6 which shows good internal consistency. The highest values are recorded for Value for Money, Feeling of Personal Safety, Positive Destination Experience and Easy Access to Information with the values 0.766, 0.760, 0.733 and 0.730, respectively. All the values are greater than 0.6 and show great consistency for all the variables.

Validity Test:

To measure the validity the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sample adequacy and Bartlett test of sphericity is applied. The range of values from 0 and 1 are considered for KMO test to check the validity. Those values which are near to 1 are considered best but it should not be less than 0.6. Similarly, the Bartlett's test values shall be significant to understand that the correlation matrix is the identity matrix.

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.780
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1390.607
	df	36
	Sig.	.000

It can be seen in the table that the KMO has value of 0.780 which is greater than 0.6 and it reflects that the sample is adequate and valid. In addition, the Bartlett's Test of Sphericity has the value of 0.000 which is significant indicating that the variables and their elements are significant.

Sample Characteristics and Descriptive Statistics:

Gender				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	168	49.6	49.6	49.6
Female	171	50.4	50.4	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

The above table represents the gender frequency. From the table it can be seen that the 49.6% respondents were male whereas female respondents were 50.4%.

Age (In Years)				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
21-25	96	28.3	28.3	28.3
26-30	133	39.2	39.2	67.6
31-35	77	22.7	22.7	90.3
36-40	24	7.1	7.1	97.3
41 & Above	9	2.7	2.7	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

The above table depicts the age of the respondents. The above table shows that most of the respondents i.e 39.2% respondents belonged to the age group of 26-30 years, followed by the 28.3% respondents belonging to age group of 21-25 years and 22.7% respondents belonged to the

age group of 31-35 years and a small minority belonged to the age groups of 36-40 years and 41 years and above respectively.

Place of Living				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
KP	84	24.8	24.8	24.8
Punjab	83	24.5	24.5	49.3
Baluchistan	32	9.4	9.4	58.7
Sindh	17	5.0	5.0	63.7
Abroad	123	36.3	36.3	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

The above table demonstrates the place of living/residence of the respondents. From the table it can be observed that the majority of respondents i-e 36% are living abroad whereas there is almost equal ratio of the respondents residing in KP and Punjab and amount to 25% approximately. A few respondents live in Baluchistan and Sindh, respectively.

Marital Status				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Married	130	38.3	38.3	38.3
Single	150	44.2	44.2	82.6
Others	59	17.4	17.4	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

The above table depicts the marital status of the respondents. 44.2% respondents in the survey are single whereas 38.3% respondents are married whereas 17.4% respondents opted others and did not state their status.

Ethnicity				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Asian (Pakistani)	133	39.2	39.2	39.2
White	92	27.1	27.1	66.4
Middle East	22	6.5	6.5	72.9
Others	82	24.2	24.2	97.1
Others	10	2.9	2.9	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

The respondents were asked to declare their ethnicity for the survey. It is revealed that the 39.2% respondents belonged to Asian (Pakistani) followed by the respondents belonging to White

ethnicity (27.1%), 24.2% other and minority of respondents had the ethnicity of Middle East (6.5%) and 2.9% opted others without declaring their ethnicity.

Purpose of Travel				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Leisure/Relax	275	81.1	81.1	81.1
Business	36	10.6	10.6	91.7
Visiting Friends and Family	21	6.2	6.2	97.9
Others	7	2.1	2.1	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

The respondents were asked to mention their purpose of travel. The above table reveals that the 81.1% respondents travelled for the purpose of leisure and to get relaxed followed by 10.6% respondents travelling for business purposes and 6.2% respondents travelled to meet their friends and family.

Frequency of Travel (per year)				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Once	140	41.3	41.3	41.3
Twice	135	39.8	39.8	81.1
Thrice	27	8.0	8.0	89.1
4 times and above	37	10.9	10.9	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

The above table shows the results for the frequency of travel per year of the respondents. 41.3% respondents mentioned that they travel once a year whereas 39.8% respondents said that they travel twice a year whereas a small minority i-e 10.9% respondents travel 4 times or above and only 8% respondents travel thrice a year.

I have Visited Pakistan.				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	339	100.0	100.0	100.0

Respondents were asked a general statement whether they have visited Pakistan or not. From the table above it can be seen that all respondents had visited Pakistan. Hence, the data reliability is enhanced to serve the research purposes.

Statement 1				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Disagree	11	3.2	3.2	3.2
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	45	13.3	13.3	16.5
Agree	47	13.9	13.9	30.4
Strongly Agree	236	69.6	69.6	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

The respondents were asked about their viewpoint if Pakistan is a safe country to travel or not. A vast majority (83.5%) is of the view that Pakistan is a safe country to travel whereas only 3.2% respondents said that it was not safe to travel to Pakistan.

Statement 2				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Disagree	27	8.0	8.0	8.0
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	77	22.7	22.7	30.7
Agree	36	10.6	10.6	41.3
Strongly Agree	199	58.7	58.7	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

Statement 2 was related to respondent's view if their safety is compromised or not as they move around in Pakistan. It is revealed that 69.3% respondents agreed that they feel secure, and their safety is not compromised as they move around Pakistan. On the other hand, 8% respondents felt insecure and say that their safety is compromised as they moved around Pakistan.

Statement 3				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	6	1.8	1.8	1.8
Disagree	19	5.6	5.6	7.4
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	75	22.1	22.1	29.5
Agree	85	25.1	25.1	54.6
Strongly Agree	154	45.4	45.4	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

The respondents were asked about if the tourist's safety is guaranteed in Pakistan to which 70.5% respondents agreed whereas 7.4% respondents disagreed and 22.1% respondents neither disagreed nor agreed to the statement.

Statement 4				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Disagree	10	2.9	2.9	2.9
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	91	26.8	26.8	29.8
Agree	81	23.9	23.9	53.7
Strongly Agree	157	46.3	46.3	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

The above table shows the results for statement that the safety of tourists is supported by political regime. 70.2% respondents agreed that the political regime supports tourist safety whereas 2.9% respondents disagreed. In addition, 26.8% respondents remained neutral.

Statement 5				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	1	.3	.3	.3
Disagree	9	2.7	2.7	2.9
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	96	28.3	28.3	31.3
Agree	71	20.9	20.9	52.2
Strongly Agree	162	47.8	47.8	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

This table reveals results for the government investment in protecting and attracting tourists and 68.7% respondents agreed whereas 3% respondents disagreed and 28.3% remained neutral.

Statement 6				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Disagree	23	6.8	6.8	6.8
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	32	9.4	9.4	16.2
Agree	129	38.1	38.1	54.3
Strongly Agree	155	45.7	45.7	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

For the perception regarding hospitality of the local people 83.8% respondents agreed to the hospitality of the local people whereas 16.2% disagreed. Furthermore, 38.1% respondents did not mention whether they agreed or disagreed and remained neutral.

Statement 7				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent

Strongly Disagree	6	1.8	1.8	1.8
Disagree	27	8.0	8.0	9.7
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	26	7.7	7.7	17.4
Agree	90	26.5	26.5	44.0
Strongly Agree	190	56.0	56.0	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

82.5% respondents were of the view that the local shopkeepers were kind towards them as depicted in the table above whereas 9.8% respondents did not agree. Similarly, 7.7% respondents remained neutral.

Statement 8				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Disagree	17	5.0	5.0	5.0
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	19	5.6	5.6	10.6
Agree	90	26.5	26.5	37.2
Strongly Agree	213	62.8	62.8	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

89.3% respondents believe that the staff at hotels and restaurants is friendly and welcoming whereas 5% respondents had opposing view. Similarly, 5.6% respondents remained neutral to the statement as shown in the table above.

Statement 9				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Disagree	4	1.2	1.2	1.2
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	67	19.8	19.8	20.9
Agree	77	22.7	22.7	43.7
Strongly Agree	191	56.3	56.3	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

79% respondents opined that residents are willing to aid the tourists anytime whereas 1.2% respondents have opposing view. Similarly, 19.8% respondents neither disagree nor agree with the willingness of residents to aid the tourists.

Statement 10				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	1	.3	.3	.3
Disagree	10	2.9	2.9	3.2
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	62	18.3	18.3	21.5
Agree	25	7.4	7.4	28.9
Strongly Agree	241	71.1	71.1	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

78.5% respondents believe that the recreational activities are available in variety as shown in the table whereas 3.2% respondents are not satisfied with the availability of recreational activities. Similarly, 18.3% respondents remained neutral in their responses.

Statement 11				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	11	3.2	3.2	3.2
Disagree	55	16.2	16.2	19.5
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	46	13.6	13.6	33.0
Agree	32	9.4	9.4	42.5
Strongly Agree	195	57.5	57.5	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

66.9% respondents found that the recreational activities are budget friendly whereas 19.4% respondents disagree with this. 13.6% respondents have neutral response as shown in table above.

Statement 12				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Disagree	6	1.8	1.8	1.8
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	76	22.4	22.4	24.2
Agree	19	5.6	5.6	29.8
Strongly Agree	238	70.2	70.2	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

75.8% respondents agree with the relevancy of recreational activities whereas 1.8% respondents disagree. In addition, 22.4% respondents remained neutral as shown in the table.

Statement 13				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Disagree	6	1.8	1.8	1.8
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	64	18.9	18.9	20.6
Agree	60	17.7	17.7	38.3
Strongly Agree	209	61.7	61.7	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

79.4% respondents believe that the recreational activities are very relevant to their leisure as demonstrated in the table above. Only 1.8% respondents disagree, and 18.9% respondents did not share their view by opting the choice neither disagree nor agree as seen in the table above.

Statement 14				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Disagree	43	12.7	12.7	12.7
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	51	15.0	15.0	27.7
Agree	33	9.7	9.7	37.5
Strongly Agree	212	62.5	62.5	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

This table depicts the results for the satisfaction from the recreational activities where it can be seen that majority of the respondents are satisfied whereas only a small portion of respondents that is 12.7% disagree and 15% remained neutral.

Statement 15				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	16	4.7	4.7	4.7
Disagree	71	20.9	20.9	25.7
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	60	17.7	17.7	43.4
Agree	14	4.1	4.1	47.5
Strongly Agree	178	52.5	52.5	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

56.6% respondents believe that there are enough sport facilities and activities as shown in table above whereas 25.6% disagree and 17.7% respondents remained neutral as seen in the table above.

Statement 16				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Disagree	16	4.7	4.7	4.7
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	47	13.9	13.9	18.6
Agree	45	13.3	13.3	31.9
Strongly Agree	231	68.1	68.1	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

This table shows the perception of the respondents if they feel safe and secure while they travel different destinations in Pakistan. It is seen that 81.4% agree that they feel safe and secure as they travel different tourist destinations whereas 4.7% respondents disagreed and 13.9% respondents neither disagreed nor agreed.

Statement 17				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Disagree	24	7.1	7.1	7.1
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	42	12.4	12.4	19.5
Agree	27	8.0	8.0	27.4
Strongly Agree	246	72.6	72.6	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

Statement 17 relates to the tourist's satisfaction that they are not discriminated against as a tourist. To which 80.6% respondents agreed that they were never discriminated against whereas 7.1% respondents disagreed as they were discriminated, and 12.4% respondents remained neutral.

Statement 18				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	6	1.8	1.8	1.8
Disagree	20	5.9	5.9	7.7
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	39	11.5	11.5	19.2
Agree	29	8.6	8.6	27.7
Strongly Agree	245	72.3	72.3	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

Respondents were asked to give their opinion on 5-point Likert scale whether the activities for the tourists at the tourist destinations are safe and risk free. 274 respondents agreed that the activities are safe whereas 26 respondents disagree and 39 respondents neither disagreed nor agreed.

Statement 19				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Disagree	6	1.8	1.8	1.8
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	61	18.0	18.0	19.8
Agree	66	19.5	19.5	39.2
Strongly Agree	206	60.8	60.8	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

Out of 339 respondents 272 respondents believed that their accommodation is reliable and secure whereas 6 respondents as shown in the table above for Statement 19. On the other hand, 61 respondents remained neutral and neither disagreed nor agreed.

Statement 20				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	7	2.1	2.1	2.1
Disagree	89	26.3	26.3	28.3
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	77	22.7	22.7	51.0
Agree	2	.6	.6	51.6
Strongly Agree	164	48.4	48.4	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

It can be seen in the table above that the 166 respondents believed that the local transport is safe whereas 96 respondents did not believe this and disagreed. In addition, 77 respondents remained neutral in their response.

Statement 21				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Disagree	7	2.1	2.1	2.1
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	46	13.6	13.6	15.6
Agree	46	13.6	13.6	29.2
Strongly Agree	240	70.8	70.8	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

The above statement 21 relates to the perception of respondents regarding the safety while touring destinations in daytime and 286 respondents agreed that daytime is safe and secure whereas 7 respondents disagreed, and 46 respondents remained neutral.

Statement 22				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	55	16.2	16.2	16.2
Disagree	111	32.7	32.7	49.0
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	72	21.2	21.2	70.2
Agree	13	3.8	3.8	74.0
Strongly Agree	88	26.0	26.0	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

101 respondents believed that it is safe to walk around streets at the nighttime whereas a vast majority disagrees and believe its is not safe to do so as seen in the table above. On the other side 72 respondents remained neutral.

Statement 23				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Disagree	24	7.1	7.1	7.1
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	81	23.9	23.9	31.0
Agree	45	13.3	13.3	44.2
Strongly Agree	189	55.8	55.8	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

234 respondents are of the view that the websites and social media provides the accurate information related to the tour operators and the tourist destinations as reflected in the table above. Whereas 24 respondents disagreed. Similarly, 23.9% respondents remained neutral.

Statement 24				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Disagree	20	5.9	5.9	5.9
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	79	23.3	23.3	29.2
Agree	43	12.7	12.7	41.9
Strongly Agree	197	58.1	58.1	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

Statement 24 results show that the 70% respondents believe that they have easy and quick access to different operators whereas 5.9% respondents disagree, and 23.3% respondents remained as seen in the table above.

Statement 25				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Disagree	25	7.4	7.4	7.4
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	73	21.5	21.5	28.9
Agree	31	9.1	9.1	38.1
Strongly Agree	210	61.9	61.9	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

Statement 25 shows that the 241 respondents are of the view that the services offered at the tourist destinations are clearly stated whereas 25 respondents disagreed as shown in table above. Similarly, 73 respondents remained neutral in their response.

Statement 26				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Disagree	21	6.2	6.2	6.2
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	46	13.6	13.6	19.8
Agree	49	14.5	14.5	34.2
Strongly Agree	223	65.8	65.8	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

The above table depicts that 80.3% respondents opined that the tour operators provide reliable and accurate information whereas 6.2% respondents oppose this view. Furthermore, 13.6% respondents remained neutral in their responses.

Statement 27				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	11	3.2	3.2	3.2
Agree	151	44.5	44.5	47.8
Strongly Agree	177	52.2	52.2	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

Statement 27 shows that the 328 respondents are of the view that there are various cultural attractions in Pakistan. And only 11 respondents remained neutral in their response.

Statement 28				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Disagree	1	.3	.3	.3
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	17	5.0	5.0	5.3
Agree	75	22.1	22.1	27.4
Strongly Agree	246	72.6	72.6	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

Statement 28 reveals that a vast majority of 321 believes that there are various cultural activities for tourists and only 0.3% respondents oppose this.

Statement 29				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	21	6.2	6.2	6.2
Agree	120	35.4	35.4	41.6
Strongly Agree	198	58.4	58.4	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

Statement 29 shows that 318 respondents are attracted towards local customs and they think it is nice to learn them.

Statement 30				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Disagree	52	15.3	15.3	15.3
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	52	15.3	15.3	30.7
Agree	78	23.0	23.0	53.7
Strongly Agree	157	46.3	46.3	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

A vast majority of the respondents i-e 69.3% think that variety of food options is available for the tourists whereas 15.3% respondents disagreed and 15.3% remained neutral in their response.

Statement 31				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Disagree	30	8.8	8.8	8.8
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	48	14.2	14.2	23.0
Agree	32	9.4	9.4	32.4
Strongly Agree	229	67.6	67.6	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

Statement 31 depicts that 261 respondents found it easy to communicate with local people whereas 30 respondents did not agree with this. In addition, 48 respondents remained neutral in their response.

Statement 32				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Disagree	9	2.7	2.7	2.7
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	107	31.6	31.6	34.2
Agree	64	18.9	18.9	53.1
Strongly Agree	159	46.9	46.9	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

The above table reflects the results for statement 32 where a vast majority of 223 respondents perceived that there are minimal language barriers as multilingual information is provide don the tourists spots whereas 9 respondents disagree to this and 107 respondents remained neutral in their response.

Statement 33				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	11	3.2	3.2	3.2
Disagree	46	13.6	13.6	16.8
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	80	23.6	23.6	40.4
Agree	19	5.6	5.6	46.0
Strongly Agree	183	54.0	54.0	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

Statement 33 reveals that 59.6% respondents believe that justifiable money is charged by the tour operators for the services offered whereas 16.8% respondents disagree and 23.6% respondents remained neutral to this.

Statement 34				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	6	1.8	1.8	1.8
Disagree	18	5.3	5.3	7.1
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	105	31.0	31.0	38.1
Agree	41	12.1	12.1	50.1
Strongly Agree	169	49.9	49.9	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

210 respondents comprising of vast majority believe that the services level at their accommodation was worth the money charged whereas 24 respondents disagreed to this as reflected in the table above for statement 34.

Statement 35				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	17	5.0	5.0	5.0
Disagree	19	5.6	5.6	10.6
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	45	13.3	13.3	23.9
Agree	42	12.4	12.4	36.3
Strongly Agree	216	63.7	63.7	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

Statement 35 results illustrate that the 258 respondents found the transport costs affordable whereas 36 respondents disagree and found it expensive. Furthermore, 45 respondents remained neutral in their response.

Statement 36				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	11	3.2	3.2	3.2
Disagree	89	26.3	26.3	29.5
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	59	17.4	17.4	46.9
Agree	40	11.8	11.8	58.7
Strongly Agree	140	41.3	41.3	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

Statement 36 reveals that the 180 respondents found the ticket pricing affordable at the tourist destinations whereas 100 respondents disagreed, and 59 respondents remained neutral in their response.

Statement 37				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	25	7.4	7.4	7.4
Disagree	49	14.5	14.5	21.8
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	52	15.3	15.3	37.2
Agree	36	10.6	10.6	47.8
Strongly Agree	177	52.2	52.2	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

The table above shows that the 62.8% respondents are of the view that the local food quality is affordable whereas 21.9% respondents disagreed, and 15.3% respondents did not show any response by remaining neutral.

Statement 38				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Disagree	37	10.9	10.9	10.9
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	78	23.0	23.0	33.9
Agree	33	9.7	9.7	43.7
Strongly Agree	191	56.3	56.3	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

66% respondents opined that the facilities offered at the tourist venues are worth the money whereas 10.9% respondents disagree, and 23% respondents remained neutral as depicted in the table above.

Statement 39				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	29	8.6	8.6	8.6
Disagree	87	25.7	25.7	34.2
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	112	33.0	33.0	67.3
Agree	38	11.2	11.2	78.5
Strongly Agree	73	21.5	21.5	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

34.3% respondents disagree that the pricing level of souvenirs and gifts is good as depicted in the table above whereas on the other hand, 32.7% respondents believe that the prices are good. In addition, 33% respondents remained neutral.

Statement 40				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Disagree	18	5.3	5.3	5.3
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	71	20.9	20.9	26.3
Agree	48	14.2	14.2	40.4
Strongly Agree	202	59.6	59.6	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

This table reflects the results for the perception of the respondents regarding the overall value for money is justified or not. 73.8% respondents believe that the overall value is justified whereas 5.3% respondents disagree. Similarly, 20.9% respondents remained neutral.

Statement 41				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	17	5.0	5.0	5.0
Disagree	59	17.4	17.4	22.4
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	114	33.6	33.6	56.0
Agree	15	4.4	4.4	60.5
Strongly Agree	134	39.5	39.5	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

This table demonstrates results for the respect of natural environment at the tourist destinations to which 43.9% respondents agreed that the natural environment is respected whereas 22.4% respondents disagreed. 33.6% respondents neither disagreed nor agreed to the statement.

Statement 42				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	8	2.4	2.4	2.4
Disagree	28	8.3	8.3	10.6
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	48	14.2	14.2	24.8
Agree	42	12.4	12.4	37.2
Strongly Agree	213	62.8	62.8	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

This table shows the results for the easy accessibility to the destinations. 75.2% respondents agreed that the destinations could be reached easily whereas 10.7% respondents disagree. In addition, 14.2% respondents do not hold any answer to the statement.

Statement 43				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Disagree	81	23.9	23.9	23.9
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	95	28.0	28.0	51.9
Agree	20	5.9	5.9	57.8
Strongly Agree	143	42.2	42.2	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

The above table reveals the perception of tourists for the parking space availability at the tourist destination. It is found that the 48.1% respondents opined that there is parking space available whereas 23.9% respondents disagree. Similarly, 28% respondents did not say about their perception.

Statement 44				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Disagree	10	2.9	2.9	2.9
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	92	27.1	27.1	30.1
Agree	7	2.1	2.1	32.2
Strongly Agree	230	67.8	67.8	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

The above table reveals the result for the facilities quality at the tourist destinations. It is clear that 69.9% respondents believe that the quality of facilities is good whereas 2.9% respondents oppose this. Similarly, 27.1% neither disagree nor agree regarding the quality of facilities at the destinations.

Statement 45				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	1	.3	.3	.3
Disagree	2	.6	.6	.9
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	36	10.6	10.6	11.5
Agree	47	13.9	13.9	25.4
Strongly Agree	253	74.6	74.6	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

To check the perception of the respondents regarding the directional signs whether they are accurate or not was asked from the respondents. The recorded results declare that 88.5% agreed that the signs are accurate whereas 0.9% respondents disagreed. Furthermore, 24.5% respondents remained neutral to the statement.

Statement 46				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	1	.3	.3	.3
Disagree	44	13.0	13.0	13.3
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	119	35.1	35.1	48.4
Agree	15	4.4	4.4	52.8
Strongly Agree	160	47.2	47.2	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

This table demonstrates the results to record the perception of the tourists whether the tourist destinations are neat and clean or not? The results show that the 51.6% respondents believe that the destinations are neat and clean where 13.3% respondents disagree along with 35.1% respondents neither disagree nor agree and remained neutral to the statement.

Statement 47				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	8	2.4	2.4	2.4
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	79	23.3	23.3	25.7
Agree	23	6.8	6.8	32.4
Strongly Agree	229	67.6	67.6	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

This table reveals the results for the climatic conditions at the tourist destinations as per their perception whether it is good or not. The table shows that the 74.4% respondents are of the view that the climatic conditions are good whereas 2.4% oppose this and 23.3% respondents were neutral and neither supported nor opposed the statement.

Statement 48				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Disagree	5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	6	1.8	1.8	3.2
Agree	124	36.6	36.6	39.8
Strongly Agree	204	60.2	60.2	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

This table reveals the results about the diversity of cultural/ historical attractions. The respondents' results show that the 96.8% respondents believe that there is diversity of attractions whereas 1.5% respondents disagreed followed by 1.8% respondents neutral response.

Statement 49				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Disagree	5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	19	5.6	5.6	7.1
Agree	86	25.4	25.4	32.4
Strongly Agree	229	67.6	67.6	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

The table above shows the result for the respondent's perception of whether staying in the tourist destination was valuable or not. The table describes that the 92% respondents agreed whereas 1.5% respondents disagreed. Similarly, 5.6% respondents remained neutral and did not declare their opinion.

Statement 50				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	24	7.1	7.1	7.1
Agree	80	23.6	23.6	30.7
Strongly Agree	235	69.3	69.3	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

This table shows the results for the statement if the respondents gained any knowledge and experience in their respective tourist destination. It is revealed that 92.9% respondents agreed whereas 7.1% respondents remained neutral and did not declare if they gained any knowledge or experience or not.

Statement 51				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	13	3.8	3.8	3.8
Agree	99	29.2	29.2	33.0
Strongly Agree	227	67.0	67.0	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

Respondents were asked if they were pleased that they chose Pakistan as their holiday destination and the results are depicted in the table above which shows that the 96.2% agreed and showed their

pleasure whereas only 3.8% neither disagreed nor agreed and remained neutral in recording their answer.

Statement 52				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	8	2.4	2.4	2.4
Agree	100	29.5	29.5	31.9
Strongly Agree	231	68.1	68.1	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

Respondents were asked about their satisfaction from the different places that they toured in Pakistan. The results are displayed in the table above which shows that 97.6% respondents were satisfied whereas 2.4% respondents neither disagreed nor agreed and hence chose to remain neutral.

Statement 53				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Neither Disagree Nor Agree	14	4.1	4.1	4.1
Agree	218	64.3	64.3	68.4
Strongly Agree	107	31.6	31.6	100.0
Total	339	100.0	100.0	

Respondents were asked if they would recommend visiting Pakistan and explore it to others to which 95% respondents agreed whereas only 4.1% respondents neither disagreed nor agreed.

Normality of Data

The data was also tested to check the normality through the test of Skewness and Kurtosis, standard deviation and min and max. The results are shown in the table below which represents all the statements used in the questionnaire built on 5-point Likert Scale. It can be seen in the table that the range of min and max is appropriate reflecting the data normality. The value of standard deviation is also very low for all the statements which indicates that the value lie closely to the mean making the dispersion of the data less. The acceptable range for Skewness and Kurtosis is +/-3 and the values fall within the range which reflects that the distribution of data is normal.

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Statement 1	339	2.00	5.00	4.4985	.84396	-1.481	.132	.971	.264
Statement 2	339	2.00	5.00	4.2006	1.04678	-.829	.132	-.833	.264
Statement 3	339	1.00	5.00	4.0678	1.02835	-.843	.132	-.084	.264
Statement 4	339	2.00	5.00	4.1357	.91302	-.507	.132	-1.089	.264
Statement 5	339	1.00	5.00	4.1327	.93743	-.549	.132	-.951	.264
Statement 6	339	2.00	5.00	4.2271	.87960	-1.063	.132	.465	.264
Statement 7	339	1.00	5.00	4.2714	1.02200	-1.417	.132	1.191	.264
Statement 8	339	2.00	5.00	4.4720	.81496	-1.625	.132	2.060	.264
Statement 9	339	2.00	5.00	4.3422	.83260	-.836	.132	-.679	.264
Statement 10	339	1.00	5.00	4.4602	.91051	-1.372	.132	.536	.264
Statement 11	339	1.00	5.00	4.0177	1.28705	-.862	.132	-.772	.264
Statement 12	339	2.00	5.00	4.4425	.89646	-1.140	.132	-.386	.264
Statement 13	339	2.00	5.00	4.3923	.85107	-1.022	.132	-.346	.264
Statement 14	339	2.00	5.00	4.2212	1.11261	-1.003	.132	-.593	.264
Statement 15	339	1.00	5.00	3.7876	1.38751	-.517	.132	-1.321	.264
Statement 16	339	2.00	5.00	4.4484	.90011	-1.399	.132	.666	.264
Statement 17	339	2.00	5.00	4.4602	.96110	-1.515	.132	.828	.264
Statement 18	339	1.00	5.00	4.4366	1.02251	-1.690	.132	1.749	.264
Statement 19	339	2.00	5.00	4.3923	.84058	-1.025	.132	-.280	.264
Statement 20	339	1.00	5.00	3.6696	1.35764	-.219	.132	-1.629	.264

Statement 21	339	2.00	5.00	4.5310	.80388	-1.493	.132	.977	.264
Statement 22	339	1.00	5.00	2.9056	1.43186	.368	.132	-1.227	.264
Statement 23	339	2.00	5.00	4.1770	1.02539	-.758	.132	-.898	.264
Statement 24	339	2.00	5.00	4.2301	1.00008	-.832	.132	-.784	.264
Statement 25	339	2.00	5.00	4.2566	1.03299	-.935	.132	-.661	.264
Statement 26	339	2.00	5.00	4.3982	.94092	-1.322	.132	.435	.264
Statement 27	339	3.00	5.00	4.4897	.56189	-.513	.132	-.765	.264
Statement 28	339	2.00	5.00	4.6696	.58329	-1.677	.132	2.200	.264
Statement 29	339	3.00	5.00	4.5221	.61197	-.903	.132	-.193	.264
Statement 30	339	2.00	5.00	4.0029	1.11073	-.683	.132	-.960	.264
Statement 31	339	2.00	5.00	4.3569	1.02312	-1.260	.132	.074	.264
Statement 32	339	2.00	5.00	4.1003	.93989	-.395	.132	-1.344	.264
Statement 33	339	1.00	5.00	3.9351	1.26931	-.663	.132	-.987	.264
Statement 34	339	1.00	5.00	4.0295	1.08746	-.642	.132	-.704	.264
Statement 35	339	1.00	5.00	4.2419	1.17942	-1.426	.132	.921	.264
Statement 36	339	1.00	5.00	3.6165	1.33694	-.266	.132	-1.476	.264
Statement 37	339	1.00	5.00	3.8584	1.37948	-.757	.132	-.879	.264
Statement 38	339	2.00	5.00	4.1150	1.10474	-.719	.132	-1.049	.264
Statement 39	339	1.00	5.00	3.1150	1.25046	.183	.132	-.982	.264
Statement 40	339	2.00	5.00	4.2802	.97054	-.938	.132	-.543	.264
Statement 41	339	1.00	5.00	3.5605	1.30033	-.174	.132	-1.270	.264
Statement 42	339	1.00	5.00	4.2507	1.11960	-1.270	.132	.417	.264

Statement 43	339	2.00	5.00	3.6637	1.24471	-.091	.132	-1.653	.264
Statement 44	339	2.00	5.00	4.3481	.97442	-.937	.132	-.857	.264
Statement 45	339	1.00	5.00	4.6195	.72142	-1.851	.132	2.817	.264
Statement 46	339	1.00	5.00	3.8525	1.16231	-.256	.132	-1.501	.264
Statement 47	339	1.00	5.00	4.3717	.99283	-1.383	.132	1.157	.264
Statement 48	339	2.00	5.00	4.5546	.60993	-1.430	.132	2.799	.264
Statement 49	339	2.00	5.00	4.5900	.66619	-1.662	.132	2.528	.264
Statement 50	339	3.00	5.00	4.6224	.61459	-1.399	.132	.838	.264
Statement 51	339	3.00	5.00	4.6313	.55712	-1.204	.132	.474	.264
Statement 52	339	3.00	5.00	4.6578	.52259	-1.161	.132	.297	.264
Statement 53	339	3.00	5.00	4.2743	.53151	.147	.132	-.467	.264
Valid N (listwise)	339								

Assumptions for Pearson Correlation:

Multicollinearity:

To measure the multi-collinearity test of Variance Inflation Factor and Tolerance is applied. The independence of the variables is reflected if the values are greater than 1 and less than 10 and the values for tolerance must be greater than 0.10 for independency of variables. The table below shows the VIF and Tolerance values for all the variables and it can be seen that all the values fall within the range.

Model	Coefficients ^a		
	Collinearity Statistics		
	Tolerance	VIF	
1			
	Country Image	.756	1.322
	Friendliness of Local People	.790	1.266
	Recreational Activities	.415	2.411
	Feeling of Personal Safety	.518	1.931
	Easy Access to Information	.647	1.545
	Presentation of Local Culture	.792	1.263
	Value for Money	.548	1.824

a. Dependent Variable: Tourists Satisfaction

Normal Distribution of Data:

The normal distribution of data is another important assumption which is fulfilled as shown in the figure below where the data distribution is normal.

Fig 12. Normal Distribution of data

Homoscedasticity of Variables:

The scattering and distribution of data is reflected in the homoscedasticity. There should be homogenous data scattering as presented in the figure below for the current data set.

Hypothesis Testing:

The hypotheses are tested through application of Pearson Correlation.

The first Hypothesis is:

H1: Favourable country image perceived through a positive destination experience has a direct positive affect on tourist satisfaction.

The table below presents the Pearson Correlation Statistics for favorable country image, positive destination experience and tourist satisfaction. It can be seen that favorable image is positively correlated with the positive destination experience with the value of 0.339 and the relation is significant at p value of 0.000 which is less than 0.01. Similarly, the positive destination experience is positively correlated with the tourist satisfaction and exhibit a strong linear relationship with the significant value of 0.000 less than 0.01. As the favorable country image and positive destination are positively correlated along with the positive correlation between the positive destination experience and tourist satisfaction. Therefore, it is inferred that favorable country image perceived through positive destination experience has a direct positive effect on tourist satisfaction. This proves the first hypothesis H1.

		Correlations		
		Favorable Country Image	Positive Destination Experience	Tourists Satisfaction
Favorable Country Image	Pearson Correlation	1	.339**	.478**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	339	339	339
Positive Destination Experience	Pearson Correlation	.339**	1	.555**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	339	339	339
Tourists Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.478**	.555**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	339	339	339

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The second hypothesis is:

H2: Friendliness of local people perceived through a positive destination experience has a direct positive affect on tourist satisfaction.

The table below presents the Pearson Correlation Statistics for Friendliness of Local People, positive destination experience and tourist satisfaction. It can be seen that friendliness of local people is negatively correlated with the positive destination experience with the value of -0.121 and the relation is insignificant at p value of 0.066 which is greater than 0.05. Similarly, the positive destination experience is positively correlated with the tourist satisfaction and exhibit a strong linear relationship with the significant value of 0.000 less than 0.01. As the friendliness of local people and positive destination experience are negatively correlated with insignificant relationship. Therefore, it is inferred that friendliness of local people perceived through positive destination experience has no direct positive effect on tourist satisfaction. Therefore, this hypothesis is rejected.

		Correlations		
		Friendliness of Local People	Positive Destination Experience	Tourists Satisfaction
Friendliness of Local People	Pearson Correlation	1	-.121*	.289**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.066	.000
	N	339	339	339
Positive Destination Experience	Pearson Correlation	-.121*	1	.555**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.066		.000
	N	339	339	339
Tourists Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.289**	.555**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	339	339	339

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The third hypothesis is:

H3: Recreational opportunities perceived through a positive destination experience has a direct positive affect on tourist satisfaction.

The table below presents the Pearson Correlation Statistics for recreational activities, positive destination experience and tourist satisfaction. It can be seen that recreational activities is positively correlated with the positive destination experience with the value of 0.498 and the relation is significant at p value of 0.000 which is less than 0.01. Similarly, the positive destination experience is positively correlated with the tourist satisfaction and exhibit a strong linear relationship with the significant value of 0.000 less than 0.01. As the recreational activities and positive destination are positively correlated along with the positive correlation between the positive destination experience and tourist satisfaction. Therefore, it is inferred that recreational activities perceived through positive destination experience has a direct positive effect on tourist satisfaction. This proves the third hypothesis H3.

		Correlations		
		Recreational Activities	Positive Destination Experience	Tourists Satisfaction
Recreational Activities	Pearson Correlation	1	.498**	.541**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	339	339	339
Positive Destination Experience	Pearson Correlation	.498**	1	.555**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	339	339	339
Tourists Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.541**	.555**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	339	339	339

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The fourth hypothesis is:

H4: Feeling of personal safety perceived through a positive destination experience has a direct positive effect on tourist satisfaction.

The table below presents the Pearson Correlation Statistics for feelings of personal safety, positive destination experience and tourist satisfaction. It can be seen that feelings of personal safety is positively correlated with the positive destination experience with the value of 0.444 and the relation is significant at p value of 0.000 which is less than 0.01. Similarly, the positive destination experience is positively correlated with the tourist satisfaction and exhibit a strong linear relationship with the significant value of 0.000 less than 0.01. As the feelings of personal safety and positive destination are positively correlated along with the positive correlation between the positive destination experience and tourist satisfaction. Therefore, it is inferred that feelings of personal safety perceived through positive destination experience has a direct positive effect on tourist satisfaction. This proves the fourth hypothesis H4.

		Correlations		
		Feeling of Personal Safety	Positive Destination Experience	Tourists Satisfaction
Feeling of Personal Safety	Pearson	1	.444**	.515**
	Correlation			
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	339	339	339
Positive Destination Experience	Pearson	.444**	1	.555**
	Correlation			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	339	339	339
Tourists Satisfaction	Pearson	.515**	.555**	1
	Correlation			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	339	339	339

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The fifth hypothesis is:

H5: Easy access to information perceived through a positive destination experience has a direct positive affect on tourist satisfaction.

The table below presents the Pearson Correlation Statistics for easy access to information, positive destination experience and tourist satisfaction. It can be seen that easy access to information is positively correlated with the positive destination experience with the value of 0.540 and the relation is significant at p value of 0.000 which is less than 0.01. Similarly, the positive destination experience is positively correlated with the tourist satisfaction and exhibit a strong linear relationship with the significant value of 0.000 less than 0.01. As the easy access to information and positive destination are positively correlated along with the positive correlation between the positive destination experience and tourist satisfaction. Therefore, it is inferred that easy access to information perceived through positive destination experience has a direct positive effect on tourist satisfaction. This proves the fifth hypothesis H5.

		Correlations		
		Easy Access to Information	Positive Destination Experience	Tourists Satisfaction
Easy Access to Information	Pearson Correlation	1	.540**	.509**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	339	339	339
Positive Destination Experience	Pearson Correlation	.540**	1	.555**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	339	339	339
Tourists Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.509**	.555**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	339	339	339

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The sixth hypothesis is:

H6: Presentation of local culture perceived through a positive destination experience has a direct positive affect on tourist satisfaction.

The table below presents the Pearson Correlation Statistics for Presentation of local culture, positive destination experience and tourist satisfaction. It can be seen that presentation of local culture is positively correlated with the positive destination experience with the value of 0.514 and the relation is significant at p value of 0.000 which is less than 0.01. Similarly, the positive destination experience is positively correlated with the tourist satisfaction and exhibit a strong linear relationship with the significant value of 0.000 less than 0.01. As the presentation of local culture and positive destination are positively correlated along with the positive correlation between the positive destination experience and tourist satisfaction. Therefore, it is inferred that presentation of local culture perceived through positive destination experience has a direct positive effect on tourist satisfaction. This proves the sixth hypothesis H6.

		Correlations		
		Presentation of Local Culture	Positive Destination Experience	Tourists Satisfaction
Presentation of Local Culture	Pearson Correlation	1	.514**	.677**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	339	339	339
Positive Destination Experience	Pearson Correlation	.514**	1	.555**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	339	339	339
Tourists Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.677**	.555**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	339	339	339

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The seventh hypothesis is:

H7: Value for money perceived through a positive destination experience has a positive affect on tourist satisfaction.

The table below presents the Pearson Correlation Statistics for value for money, positive destination experience and tourist satisfaction. It can be seen that value for money is positively correlated with the positive destination experience with the value of 0.559 and the relation is significant at p value of 0.000 which is less than 0.01. Similarly, the positive destination experience is positively correlated with the tourist satisfaction and exhibit a strong linear relationship with the significant value of 0.000 less than 0.01. As the value for money and positive destination are positively correlated along with the positive correlation between the positive destination experience and tourist satisfaction. Therefore, it is inferred that value for money perceived through positive destination experience has a direct positive effect on tourist satisfaction. This proves the seventh hypothesis H7.

		Correlations		
		Value for Money	Positive Destination Experience	Tourists Satisfaction
Value for Money	Pearson Correlation	1	.559**	.461**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	339	339	339
Positive Destination Experience	Pearson Correlation	.559**	1	.555**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	339	339	339
Tourists Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.461**	.555**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	339	339	339

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The eighth hypothesis is:

H8: Positive destination experience has a significant impact on tourist satisfaction.

The table below presents the Pearson Correlation Statistics for positive destination experience and tourist satisfaction. It can be seen that the positive destination experience is positively correlated with the tourist satisfaction with the value of 0.555 and exhibit a strong linear relationship with the significant value of 0.000 less than 0.01. Therefore, it is inferred that positive destination experience has a direct positive effect on tourist satisfaction. This proves the eighth hypothesis H8.

Correlations			
		Positive Destination Experience	Tourists Satisfaction
Positive Destination Experience	Pearson Correlation	1	.555**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	339	339
Tourists Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.555**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	339	339

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

6.3. Analysis

The above findings indicate that favourable country image does have a positive affect on tourist satisfaction, therefore, it is significant for marketers to focus on bringing about a positive image of Pakistan forward. Pakistan's image is still very much the same as it was the last decade, and that is because no efforts have been put to portray any other image by any government of Pakistan. Many people who do their own research before visiting a country can contact people within the country and find important information for their trip, and then make a decision. Unfortunately, many people still rely on mainstream media for information. Tourism decision makers and providers should take steps to ensure a positive image of Pakistan is cultivated in international media. Local tour operators should must also take action to ensure they do their part in reaching out to the wider target audience.

Feeling of personal safety has a positive impact on tourist satisfaction as approved by hypothesis 4, which implies that tourists who were surveyed felt they were safe for the duration of their stay in Pakistan. As Pakistan is a developing country and has faced security issues in the past, it is essential that visitors feel they are safe to holiday in the country. Most of the responses received were from tourists based within the Northern areas of Pakistan, it is a well-known fact that the Northern areas are some of the safest areas in Pakistan. Due to low level of crime and very minimal risk of any terror activities, and the scenery and adventure activities offered by these local destinations, the tourist satisfaction level is bound to be high. Northern areas such as Kalam, Swat Valley, Hunza Valley, Lake Saiful Muluk, Chitral, and Deosai National Park provide immense pleasure for not only international visitors but also for local tourists from within Pakistan. The destinations mentioned above coupled with a sense of feeling safe and secure, make Pakistan an ideal holiday destination. The questionnaire depicted that 83% of the people surveyed agreed that they felt safe, however, more than 10% people said they felt unsafe moving around from one destination to another.

Recreational activities are an essential ingredient to having a satisfied customer, tour operators need to organise recreational activities that can be catered to people of all ages and backgrounds. Easy access to information is not always possible since the internet is still a privilege for many, specially for those in developing country. This can make it difficult for potential tourists to gain information, which can put people off of visiting a particular destination they might be interested in. Tour operators need to reach out to people more so they can relay information needed to make an informed decision. It is essential that tour operators and destination providers find a way to make information easily accessible as it has a positive affect on tourist satisfaction.

Presentation of local culture has a positive impact on tourist satisfaction, which implies that destination providers should ensure that the local cultural and heritage sites are well-preserved. Value for money is an essential element of day-to-day life, people like to get their money's worth in every aspect. It is the same as wanting to get the best value for money possible for a holiday, therefore it is essential that tour operators provide good products and services for minimal price, this can be done to ensure a customer base is built and once there is a decent customer base and a cash cow, the pricing can change. Friendliness of local people does not have a positive impact on tourist satisfaction, hypothesis 3 was rejected which implies that many people are not caring of attitudes of local people as long as they get a feeling of personal safety and the best value for money for their trips. When all the needs and wants are met, customers are satisfied as positive destination experience has a significant impact on tourist satisfaction. it is recommended that local destination providers along with local tourism businesses ensure they follow the strategic framework recommended above to ensure not only tourist satisfaction, but also to gain tourist loyalty as well as word-of-mouth marketing.

6.4. Qualitative Data:

6.4.1. Thematic Analysis

Potential contributors were contacted mainly by email and through social media, some telephone calls were made as well. All participants contacted worked for or owned tourism providing organisations and had a social media presence, which was crucial for this study. Participants were not offered any incentives and they took part in the study as a gesture of goodwill. Four participants were interviewed for this research, three interviews took place in Pakistan and one took place over Skype. Tourism services providers chosen were based in Lahore, Islamabad and Rawalpindi. These organisations were contacted through telephone and social media and appointments were made for the interview process. Before beginning formal interviews, verbal consent was taken and consent forms were signed as well. All participants were co-operative and agreed to have the discussion and their opinions mentioned in the research.

To address gaps in existing literature, this research focuses on identifying themes within the participant knowledge, this will provide the author further room for investigation on this subject. For this reason, thematic analysis is best suited for qualitative data analysis. There has been some criticism of use of thematic analysis in the past due to lack of proper guidance to researchers using this method. However, thematic analysis is an excellent method of analysing qualitative data and validity of this research is of utmost importance, therefore, a clear, concise and transparent methodology has been applied. Findings are discussed by strong themes, and some quotations are provided to catch the right essence of data gathered.

Thematic analysis has been in use as a qualitative data analysis tool since the 1970, it was developed by Gerald Holton. Braun & Clark have defined thematic analysis as a “distinctive method with a clearly outlined set of procedures in social science” (2013). Thematic analysis helps researchers in identifying patterns and themes within data collected to answer a specific research question. Braun & Clark have done significant research on thematic analysis and have stated that it is an excellent method of analysing any type of qualitative analysis including interviews, qualitative surveys, and also focus groups. By using thematic analysis method, a researcher is able to apprehend complicated, chaotic and conflicting affairs that prevail in the world. Braun & Clark state that this method is detailed but exciting as well as challenging (2013) as qualitative research can identify patterns and trends arising from the collected data

and in doing so, the researcher can make their contributions to exiting literature. This data analysis method enables the researcher to identify commonly recognized patterns and relationships to meaningfully answer the research questions of the study. According to Braun and Clarke (2013), this method involves seven steps: transcription, reading and familiarization, coding, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes, and finalizing the analysis. The next sections of the example provide hands-on experience on how a researcher could engage in those steps in the thematic analysis.

There are several steps through which a research must go through to obtain a clear and accurate thematic analysis. The data collected from all interviews was initially transcribed, during this process initial impressions and ideas were jotted down as these are considered significant in the analysis process (Riessman, 1993). To ensure accuracy, recordings were listened to several times and transcriptions read several times too. thematic coding refers to a method of qualitative data analysis which consists of identifying certain passage of transcript that are linked through a collective idea, that allows text to be organised into categories (Gibbs, 2007). The next phase was coding; wherein codes were generated from the transcribed data, these codes were generated as a link to research question. The third section consisted of generating themes, the themes will combine a large portion of codes and bind them into each theme to then be analysed. All codes identified initially were incorporated into a theme. Any themes that did not have enough data were deleted. Once the themes had been refined, another attempt at coding took place to ensure no significant codes were missed. After the finalisation of themes, the next step took place which involved explaining and naming themes as each theme was to be identified clearly for a clearer analysis. The final stage was to involve direct quotations from the transcript to present a coherent example of point being discussed.

6.4.1.1. Services

Tour operators offer a range of services; tangible and intangible to their customers. All four interviewees stated that they provide all-in-one service to their customers; from transport to accommodation to organising tours. Services provided by these four organisations are: scheduling, arranging accommodation, organising activities, organising incoming and outgoing transport and everything else that a tourist might require. The most significant services of all if customer services, due to the diverse nature of customers tour operators have to be on constant beck and call of customers

regardless of the time and day. Most of the tour operators are entrepreneurs and started with a small team.

Interviewee 1: Salman Hassan	Pakistan Tours Ltd
Interviewee 2: Sajid Ali	100 Adventures Travel
Interviewee 3: Saqib Awan	Crossroad Adventure
Interviewee 4: Salar Siddiqui	Hunza Guides Pakistan Tours

Fig. 14: interviewee list

“what we sell if our service, our product is service” Salman Hassan

Accommodation services include organising hotel stays, there are many different types of accommodations offered by tour operators. Some of them include tents, igloos as well as motels. The best way to find a safe and secure accommodation is to contact a reliable tour operator. Participants state that they have informal, and some formal, contract with accommodation providers.

“my company provides tangible and intangible services, we arrange accommodation, transport, recreational activities, food and anything else that is requested by visitors, it’s like a one-stop shop.” Salman Hassan

Transport is also included in most holiday packages. There can be many types of transports dependant on the level of package the tourists choose. Transport can include flights, bus, train and private hire taxis. Due to the infrastructure of Pakistan, tourists might have to change the mode of transport depending on their destination. For instance, to get to destinations such as Lake Saiful Maluk, Hunza Valley and mountainous regions (Karakoram, Nanga Parbat), special high powered jeeps are required due to rough road conditions. New highways have been built in the last two decades which has made commuting easier and safer, however, there are stretches of road that are extremely narrow and can only be driven by highly experienced local drivers. Thus it is crucial that transport is chosen through the right avenues. Scheduling is a task mainly left to

tour organisers, some destinations after dark tend to become unsafe to be in, therefore, tourist providers plan the schedule accordingly.

“The roads in some deep Northern destinations (Chitral, Hunza) can be narrow and dangerous, this is enough to put some people off, however, can also be a adventure of a lifetime for some. To cross such roads, we have to have drivers specifically experiences in driving in such conditions. We are responsible for our customers’ safety and wellbeing so we have to ensure we offer the best possible service” Sajid Ali

One thing that Pakistan isn’t short of is activities for everyone. Participants state that adventure tourism has grown exceedingly in the last decade, people from all over Pakistan take breaks to feel the adrenaline rush that some of these activities bring about. Some of the most popular sports activities include; jetskiing in Khanpur Dam, Skiing in Malam Jabba, Rafting in Swat River, Polo Festival in Shandur, Paragliding, Canoeing and Kayaking in various rivers, Cycling from Hunza to China, Rock Climbing in Lady Finger Peak and mountaineering expeditions in the K2 peaks. According to participants, this is a short list of activities, there are many others in different locations. With activities like these comes an enormous responsibility on part of tour organisers, wherein they have to ensure all tourists’ safety and wellbeing.

“ there are so many activities in destinations that a whole month isn’t enough to experience them all. Every location has its unique characteristics and offers a range of activities. Apart from sceneries and greenery, various adverterous activities are highly sought after. From water rafting to parasailing to jet skiing to mountain excursions, the list is endless. Foreign tourists find these activities cheaper compared to many other countries and this gives us a competitive advantage” Salar Siddiqui

Other services include helping foreign tourists with visa applications. Pakistan provides an on-arrival visa to a very small number of nationalities and many tourists, specifically from Western countries, have to apply for visa well in advance. It is stated on the

government website that most visit visa applications take 5-7 working days to be processed, however participants state that in their experience most visa applications take longer than that, some could even take months. Visit visa applicants also need to provide a No Objection Certificate (NOC) if they wish to visit certain regions such as Gilgit Baltistan, Kashmir and some areas that near the Line of Control. Prime Minister Imran Khan officially abolished the NOC requirement for GB and Kashmir, however participants state that it takes a long time for new official orders to reach the implementing officers in restricted regions. Many tourists are still being asked for it, thus it is a wise choice to have one ready.

“With the right guidance, visit visa for foreign tourists won’t take long in most cases, however there can be unexpected delays” Salar Siddiqui

“Sometimes authorities will delay applications without a reason and that causes frustrations for not only us but also the visitors. I feel like NOC is a waste of time, visa should be straightforward considering how bad tourism industry has suffered and lack of international tourists” Salar Siddiqui

6.4.1.2. Marketing

Social Media: Different forms of business to consumer marketing are used by these organisations. In today’s world the most viable and effective way to market products is through social media. Social media is used by over 4.5 billion people globally, which is almost half of the world’s population. Social media platforms such as Facebook and Instagram have proven to be a very successful method to engage with existing customer base, reach new ones and promote products according to customers’ desires. Almost 90% of marketers believe that social media is very significant to their marketing strategy and 73% of marketers firmly believe that social media marketing is highly effective for their organisations.

Yet another common theme between the four organisations interviewed was that they all rely heavily on social media marketing, specifically Facebook adverts. The

interviewees state that Facebook ads have proven to be very fruitful for their business and they have all set aside a small budget for those adverts that run all year round. This is because Facebook ads are targeted to potential consumers based on their location, demography and interests. Ads can be geared toward a specific target audience as Facebook gives businesses options to specify their audience. One of the participants shared their daily and monthly facebook ads cost, which is 600-700 PKR and nearly 40,000-50,000 pkr a month after adding extras and add-ons.

“Facebook adverts are detailed and communication is easier than any other online platform. Facebook links us to potential customers. People in Pakistan prefer to use facebook over any other medium of social media and, for that reason, it is the best mode of advertising.” Saqib Awan

“I find that Facebook adverts work best for my organisation since I am able to connect with potential customers anywhere and everywhere, anytime. I have to set aside a monthly budget but that isn't so much of an issue since a successful single trip can bring a lot of profit” Saqib Awan

Instagram is also used as a secondary to Facebook for advertisement purposes. Instagram has a clear outlay which is good for tourism providers as they can post enticing photos of their products, it gives users a high amount of exposure through the use of hashtags, followers and level of activity. Out of the four, three of these organisations extensively use Instagram to post pictures and videos of the main tourist locations (mainly Hunza Valley, the Himalayas, Kalash Valley). They also use paid advertisement on the photo sharing platform and make use of the hashtag option. Instagram has a large number of travel bloggers on Instagram and many have a large following. Another way to gain exposure and spread the word is to offer free products or services to bloggers with a large following in return for their reviews and mentions of the business on their profiles. Interviewees state that although the organisations have their own profiles on Instagram, it is very useful to have influencers mention their

businesses. Just like facebook, Instagram also offers businesses to specify their target audience so the ads are displayed to a certain set of people.

“Instagram is also an excellent options to display visual images, it is a preferred way of younger people since they like posting pictures and stories. One of the biggest sources of advertisement is through bloggers who have a large following, freebies offered by us can be paid back through testimonials and reviews of our business” Sadiq Awan

Word of mouth: Word of mouth maketing is when a business takes certain actions to get it’s consumers to speak to other about their products or services. Word of mouth marketing is when a satisfied consumer recommends their business to others, it is a free marketing technique performed by consumers spontaneously on behalf of a business. Since it is a free form of marketing, and there is little to no effort required for the business, it is a highly valuable trait to gain. Word of mouth can be triggered by a number of things; exceptional customer service, gifts with purchases or general satisfaction with products or services. Since the inception of internet, word of mouth marketing has become simpler as anything shared online has the potential to reach thousand of users in a short amount of time. It is a chain marketing strategy, wherein it does not stop with one consumer recommendation, it could go on from one person to another, so on and so forth. With every mention, word of mouth carries an exponential potential of growth.

A Neilson report stated that 92% of people highly trust word of mouth and referrals from people they know. Participants state that they rely on word of mouth marketing and friends and family referrals after social media advertising. People tend to go with suggestions provided by their close ones and thus providing a satisfactory experience for customers is substantial to businesses. One participant stated that it isn’t just the consumers who spread the words but also fellow tour operators, who can refer tourists

to other businesses if they're themselves unable to provide the requested services/products. Participants believe that tourism organisation community is heavily connected so people do not hesitate to share their customers if absolutely necessary.

"I am convinced that word of mouth and family and friends recommendations are the best source of marketing for businesses like ours, specially in a country like Pakistan. People in Pakistan tend to follow their family and friends' recommendations more than any reviews and testimonials online and for that reason we have to ensure the service we provide is optimal no matter the cost" Salar Siddiqui

"My business relies heavily on friends and family recommendation, since many people still do not have access to internet so they ask around for recommendations." Saqib Awan

"Word of mouth is just as important as social media marketing, the advantage is that it is free whereas social media marketing can cost a lot of money." Salman Hassan

The main mode of communication between the businesses and customers is through social media. Many of these organisations have Facebook pages, which let customers post comments, pictures and reviews, as well as private message the organisation. Customers who do not have access to internet, reply on telephone calls. Interviewees stated that they are always available for any queries their customers might have and hence are open to answering them any time of the day.

"we have a strong presence on social media and rely on it heavily to stay in touch with our customers, it is also a cheaper way to communicate. Communication, specially with international customers, can be expensive if we rely on phone calls so we try and do it through social media as much as possible" Salman Hassan

"my business is open to customers 24/7, I have emphasised from day one to answer all enquiries regardless of the nature of the enquiry. I have built a reputation on Facebook

travel groups, specifically for Pakistan, as someone people could refer to for help with enquiries such as transport, visa applications, NOC certificates” Salman Hassan

Travel Fairs : According to the interview data, all four of the participants at some point sent a representative of their organisation to travel event. 3 participants make regular visits to universities and deliver seminars, on tourism and also find opportunity to advertise their business. As mentioned above, university and college students are one of the biggest customers of these businesses. One participant stated that they have, to this date, made several trips to foreign countries (Malaysia and Indonesia) to attend travel events to promote Pakistan and their businesses. One of the most common theme found in all 4 interviews was that all participants were driven by their commitment to change Pakistan’s image to the world. Pakistan’s image has been severely blemished ever since the ominous events of 9/11 happened and worsened over the next decade as religious terrorism grew on certain parts of the country. As a result of this, tourism went into deep decline and the image of the country became really gloomy. Pakistan became to be known as an extreme theocratic nation which unwelcomes people from outside the country. This couldn’t be further from the truth since despite being in a political and religious turmoil, Pakistan welcomed millions of refugees from neighbouring Afghanistan. Despite the negative image and being deterred, some people decide to travel to see for themselves and have left happy and surprised by how much there is to offer in Pakistan. And for that purpose, the participants, as citizens of Pakistan, believe some responsibility to change the country’s image lies with them. 2 participants stated that they have other part-time and full-time jobs and entered tourism industry purely because they felt a sense of patriotism as well as to spread happiness through travel.

“I want to change Pakistan’s image in the world” Saqib Awan

“I want more people to come to Pakistan to experience our wonderful country and it’s diversity” Salar Siddiqui

“I travel to universities a lot and have seminars to advertise and raise awareness. I have been asked to present lectures, since the tourism industry in Pakistan is not mature yet. I go to universities since students are one of our biggest customers and we provide various packages aimed for them,” Salman Hassan

“I have been to Malaysia thrice and Indonesia once to attend several travel fairs because those two countries have become my biggest markets. My business has seen a huge increase in interest from Malaysian and Indonesian tourists. I have had success in recruiting tourists from those travel fairs on a small scale” Saqib Awan

Travel Bloggers: Travel blogging has become majorly prevalent since the start of the 21st century and with access to the internet all around the world, blogging has become easy and popular. Travel bloggers are individuals who travel around the world while collecting material (photos, souvenirs) to write about their experiences. Depends on the level of their following, they can earn money. Most bloggers do it due to their interest in travelling, many places and destinations offer free accommodation to bloggers in exchange of exposure. Recently there has been an immense interest in exploring Pakistan within the travel bloggers community. British Backpackers Society ranked Pakistan the top adventure destination for 2018 after traveling and experiencing the country extensively (Fox, 2018). When asked about impact of foreign travel bloggers, the responses received were in harmony. For instance, one of the participant stated that foreign travel bloggers, with a large number of social media following, have portrayed Pakistan in a positive light.

“I believe that foreign travel bloggers have made a difference on some small level and we are seeing some interest from foreign tourists” Sajid Ali

“Although I believe it is good publicity for Pakistan, foreign bloggers can only do so much. Government should be at the core of promoting Pakistan’s image, it shouldn’t be expected from travel bloggers only” Sajid Ali

There are pros and cons to how foreign travel bloggers portray Pakistan. Since the new government came into power in 2018, the security situation has improved even further. Pakistani Prime Minister is heavily invested in making inbound foreign tourism a priority. Due to improved security situation, there has been an influx in foreign travel bloggers, specifically young bloggers from Europe. Some of those bloggers are sponsored by tourism organisations and some even by some government agencies and thus present a 100% positive image of Pakistan. Many NGO's, women's rights organisations as well as some tourists foreign tourists have raised their concerns over this. Concerns are that those bloggers may not present the ground realities since they have had a sponsored trip and thus have had a pampered experience. Many local and international tourists have been harassed by local authorities and locals, which isn't highly reported in the media. Many foreign travellers, specifically those who look foreign, get perks like free food, accommodation and transport due to the welcoming nature of Pakistanis.

Pakistan was colonised for a very long time and that has left a big impact on the mindset of the people. The social media coverage that Pakistan has received recently with regards to tourism has been mainly from the point of view of Western White influencers and it can be said with certainty that not everybody will have the same fun experience. When asked participants if people in Pakistan are still influenced with colonialism by white people, respondents stated that it is somewhat true that people tend to shower white travelers with compliments, praises and gifts whereas the same cannot be said for travelers of colour. However, participants also believe that locals welcome all foreign travelers despite their ethnic backgrounds, it's just a fact that white people are treated more royally than any other ethnicity. Alex Reynolds, a foreign renowned travel blogger in Pakistan, has raised all of the above concerns and stated that she had been shunned from speaking at one of the events due to the negative tone of her statements. Despite it all, travel bloggers have proved fruitful in promoting Pakistan to an extent. Participants believe that foreign travel bloggers with a large following are essential in putting Pakistan out there for others to see and anticipate travelling there.

Reynold states that she believes the solution to this issue is to promote transparency rather than only promoting a positive account of tourist experience in Pakistan.

“Unfortunately a Pakistan traveler will not have the same pampered experience as that of their white counterparts, it is witnessed on a regular basis” Sajid Ali

Participants state that many foreign travelers document every aspect of their trip, which is helpful in portraying a positive image of Pakistan. Many tourists who’ve been to Pakistan from abroad have received a superior level of hospitality and are surprised by the fact that sometimes they don’t even have to pay for things such as food and transport.

“Pakistan is home to some of the most friendliest and most welcoming people, and offers everything an explorer is looking for. Some foreign bloggers who’ve travelled through Pakistan have been provided with free accommodation and food throughout their trip, which was an alien concept to them. I believe it is due to the fact that Pakistanis aren’t accustomed to seeing foreign people in the country and go above and beyond to please them” Salman Hassan

Looking at the data analysed, it can be concluded that the main mode of marketing for tour operators is social media. Facebook, specifically, is the top choice for paid advertisements. Pakistan has the 11th highest number of Facebook users worldwide, with 40 million people subscribed to the social media site (Statista, 2021). Globally, Facebook has 1.7 billion daily active users, highest number of any social media platform (Baker, 2020). The high number of Facebook users makes it a seamless platform to advertise business products and services. In some instances, Instagram has also been used for advertising purposes. However, Instagram falls pale in comparison to Facebook, as it has 6.6 million active users as compared to Facebook’s 40 million (NapoleanCat, 2020). The second best marketing tool was word-of-mouth (recommendations), people tend to trust their friends and family when looking for

products and services. this works out greatly for organisation as this marketing activity does not cost them anything yet attracts customers.

6.4.1.3. Concerns

Distrust of Government: Corruption in Pakistan is a widespread and long-standing issue. Despite, many efforts being made to curb the high level of corruption, there is almost no evidence anything has changed. Pakistan's political history has been plagued by bureaucracy, corruption, election rigging and military involvement. According to Transparency Index, Pakistan ranked 124th out of 180 in Corruption Perceptions Index and scored 31/100. Bribing and corruption are illegal, however, it is still rampant in all institutions and sectors. According to a 2020 Preport on corruption on Pakistan, Judicial system, Police, Public Services, Land Administration, Tax Administration, Public Procurement, Legislation, and Civil Society are all ranked at high risk of corruption (Risk and compliance Portal). In a 2008 survey of 4000 Pakistani, it was revealed that almost half of the participants had to pay a bribe to access healthcare (Urban.org).

Participants in this study reveal that they do not trust the government to make any improvements. In fact, they state that in their opinion, the government is to blame for a host of issues the tourism industry faces currently. All participants believe that Pakistani media and Pakistani government have the power to change the perception of Pakistan internationally but have not done anything to address this issue. One participant states that. Unlike the public, the media isn't as motivated to help change Pakistan's image. As mentioned above in marketing section that tv adverts are very costly and not every business in the field can afford it, tv channels aren't willing to advertise small tourism businesses free of charge.

“Media isn't receptive just like the government. They aren't concerned with improving the image of Pakistan or improving essentials such as facilities and infrastructure.

Only through tourism we can improve Pakistan's image” Sajid Ali

One participant states that they had to cancel a 125 people trip to Kashmir region due to a political sit-in as all routes going in and out of Lahore city were closed off. The participant then had to pay customers back as well as bare the cost of the booking and ended up paying a hefty amount. Participant states that they believe that not only does this hurt their business financially but also affects their credibility as consumers in Pakistan can be highly demanding and not very understanding.

“Our politics has been unstable at times and highly unpredictable” Saqib Awan

“My business suffers most because of the political environment” Saqib Awan

Security: All participants seem to be in harmony regarding the security situation of Pakistan. It was noted that all participants were confident that people from every country, race and gender could explore Pakistan (except Balochistan; which is closed to foreign travellers) without any threat to their life. Women are also safe travelling solo, however, it would be beneficial to have a travel partner since some villages and towns tend to be on a conservative side. Participants state that all parts of Pakistan are accessible except a small number of areas due to internal security policies and threats. Balochistan has active state separatists movement, sectarian disagreement makes it an unsafe region to travel. Pakistani tourists can travel to Balochistan freely, foreign tourists are restricted and will be sent away if found near the border.

“Samar Khan and Mehwish Akhlaq have explored Pakistan solo on their bicycles”

Punjab: Punjab is considered a safe and secure region for tourists of all background and nationalities. The province is known for its rich cultural heritage, colourful art and is a sacred region for a lot of religions. Participants in this research are in agreement that Punjab is a considerably safe location for foreign tourists to visit. Recently, there has

been an influx of tourists for religious purposes as Pakistan government opened doors to Sikhs and Hindus from neighbouring countries.

“Lahore is a landmine for cultural heritage, specially architecture from the Mughal era, which fascinates many. One thing I have observed in my years in this business is that, Pakistani tourists tend to prefer destinations with natural scenery and greenery, over historical places such as Lahore. Whereas, foreign tourists want to explore the centuries old magnificent architecture. For instance, Walled city of Lahore (smaller Lahore) has 8 gates that were built over a period of time in the Mughal era, along with Lahore Fort, Badshahi Mosque and Gurdwara Dera Sahib display a vast portion of Lahore’s history. Lahore is the capital city of the Punjab province and one of the most progressive one in Pakistan. It is very a safe and open place to visit for tourists from everywhere” Salar Siddiqui

Khyber Pukhtunkhwa: Khyber Pukhtunkhwa previously known as North-West Frontier Province and now commonly known as KPK, is one of the four provinces of Pakistan. It is home to ethnic Pashtun and many Afghan refugees. It borders Afghanistan, due to which some of the areas are not considered safe. However, tourist attractions such as Naran, Kaghan, Swat Valley, Lake Saiful Maluk, Malam Jabba and Chitral are well-known and generally safe for all tourists. Many tour operators operate in this area and have made successful tours happen. These areas are some of the biggest attractions in Pakistan.

“Some areas of KPK region were unsafe when terrorism was active in some areas of Pakistan. The army has taken out several operations and I can confidently say that KPK is a secure region. If it wasn’t safe, I wouldn’t be running successful tours” Salar Siddiqui

Sindh: Karachi is the capital city of Sindh and the most populous city of Pakistan. It is situated on Arabian Sea and is home to two main seaports of Pakistan; the Port of

Karachi and Port Bin Qasim. Karachi airport is also one of the busiest airports of Pakistan. Karachi has a very diverse population, many people from all parts of Pakistan settle in and visit Karachi for business reasons, Karachi has long been known for its cuisine. Karachi as well as Lahore have areas designated for street and restaurant food; known as Food Street, which attracts many tourists.

“Karachi is a highly populated city, with the focus mainly on business, shopping and food. Although Karachi has a beach and is the official seaport of Pakistan, it does not have many tourist attractions. However, a few miles away from Karachi is Makli, an archeological marvel dating back hundreds of years is a sight to be enjoyed and receives much deserved attention. I can’t reiterate enough on how safe 90% of areas in Pakistan are, Sindh included” Sajid Ali

Balochistan: Balochistan was deemed unsafe by all participants and it was concluded that they avoid organising any tours to the region due to many security threats. However, participants state that they believe that, Balochistan due to its size and many landmine, will make for an excellent tourist destination. Places of tourism interest in Balochistan are many, for instance; Gwadar is the world’s deepest seaport and is a major part of CPEC expansion with China. Gwadar port is predicted to be the ‘next Dubai’ and it is also predicted that once the CPEC project is operational, Gwadar Port could end up changing the entire equilibrium of the Indian Ocean. Hingol National Park is the largest national park in Pakistan, it covers a large area and isn’t too far from Karachi. Hingol Park consists of 6 ecosystems along with a desert and several plains, giving it a very unique position among worldwide national parks. Sacred Hindu temple is located in the middle of Hingol National Park and attracts over 250,000 devotees for Hindu Yatra.

“Balochistan is the biggest province in the country but is unsafe currently due the security issues. Pakistanis can travel to the province but foreigners are not allowed in Balochistan and if a foreign citizen tried to cross the border they will be sent back. Unfortunately kidnapping is a problem in Balochistan and even some Pakistanis aren’t

safe in most of the areas. If a foreign citizen wishes to visit Balochistan, it can be arranged through a special request, however they will have to travel with a fleet of army personnel, which many people might not be comfortable with. Therefore, Balochistan isn't quite open for tourism currently. However with governments plans in partnership with China, CPEC project could prove to be fruitful and might end up changing the situation, however it is uncertain” Saqib Awan

Balochistan is considered unsafe due to tribal conflicts and political unrest, LOC is deemed risky due to Pakistan's tumultuous relationship with India and Afghan-Pakistan border is unsafe due to militant activity in Afghanistan. The rest of Pakistan is considered fairly safe and has been free of any major threats (terrorism, political rallies/sit-ins) since the new government came into power in 2018.

“Line of Control (LOC) that borders India with Pakistan can be risky at times due to the volatile nature of the relationship between the two countries so we recommend tourists not to go close to that location. Pakistan-Afghan border is another risky location. Pakista itself is a safe place, however, due to the sour relationship with some of the neighbouring countries, some unfortunate evenst have taken place which has taken a toll on Pakistan's reputation as a safe country.” Sajid Ali

Gilgit-Baltistan (GB): Gilgit Baltistan is a region in Pakistan administered Kashmir, it is highly popular due to it's scenic beauty and natural landmarks. One of the most famous area in GB is the Hunza Valley, which has become the most visited destination in Pakistan in the last decade. K2 Mountains, Deosai National Park, Attabad Lake, Khunjerab National Park, Karakoram Highway, Altit Fort and Cold Desert of Skardu are some of the most popular and mesmerising destinations. GB is considered one of most safest regions in Pakistan to travel to, it is also reported to be amond one of the most peaceful places in the world due to low crime rates and low population rates.

“Gilgit Baltistan is a piece of heaven on earth, it does not only have the scenery and nature but also the most friendliest, welcoming and peaceful locals. Deosai National Park is a destination that poets write poems about, it is absolutely stunning. GB is probably the most visited destination in Pakistan, I take tours to Hunza Valley on a regular basis, most of the national tourists want to visit Hunza Valley due to its incomparable natural beauty but also because of the diversity of cultures. GB is safe destination with very open and friendly locals” Sajid Ali

Participants state their goal is to show people everything Pakistan has to offer and give tourists a memorable experience. It was stated that although there is a low threat of terrorism, the only security concerns is in Balochistan. Balochistan is embroiled with tribal conflicts and separatist movements which make it unsafe for tourists to visit the region. Foreign tourists are officially banned from visiting any part of Balochistan, even domestic tourists are advised to avoid the region since there is a high likelihood of kidnappings.

Kund Malir is a beach located within Hingol National Park, it is considered one of the most beautiful beaches in the world. However, due to lack of facilities it has not been visited too often. There are many beaches in Balochistan that desire to be frequented and appreciated but due to lack of exposure and the delicate security situation of the Balochistan region, those destinations stay unacknowledged.

“Hingol National Park has the potential to make Pakistan one of the most popular countries in the world for tourism. Its beauty is endless and if sufficient investments are made, tourism figures will skyrocket” Saqib Awan

Infrastructure and Accessibility: Participants believe that lack of robust infrastructure in parts of Pakistan is highly damaging to the tourism industry. For instance, there aren't solid roads to get to many destinations.

Accessibility can be a hindrance for people with disabilities, most destinations in Pakistan are not accessible for people with mobility issues. This leads to a loss in tourists with special needs, many major tourist destinations in the world are adopting ways to include people of all stature.

“Many destinations have accessibility issues for people with physical disabilities. Destinations specially in the Northern areas, where infrastructure is lacking currently are the most underdeveloped regions. Considerably developed locations such as Lahore are slowly adopting measures to make destinations accessible, however we still have a long way to go” Salar Siddiqui

Pakistan is a developing country, which means that a high percentage of the population has no access to the internet. As of mid 2020, a 40.95% of Pakistanis use and have access to the internet, which means that almost 60% of the population has no internet access. Participants mentioned that there are still a small number of underdeveloped tourist destinations that lack internet access and telephone network which is a major setback and a disadvantage to those destinations.

One of the participant mentions that anyone organising tours takes responsibility to ensure that tourists are safe and are provided with anything that they need. In some remote areas, in case of a medical emergency, hospitals can be quite far away and it can be quite difficult to find doctors nearby. Participants state they feel that taking female tourists along on tours is also a responsibility in a considerably conservative country like Pakistan.

“Pakistan has been known to be unsafe for women at times and taking female only groups can sometimes feel like a big responsibility. However, since these tours are becoming normal, they have been noticeably safe” Salman Hassan

One participant claims that domestic tourists are more demanding than foreign tourists. Local tourists are more prone to litter and leave a mess which can leave a bad impression

of Pakistan as a whole to any foreign visitors. It was stated by another participant that local tourists demand more for very little money, participants have experiences that foreign tourists feel mesmerised by the natural majesty of Pakistan and are grateful for every service provided.

*“Pakistani people will buy designer clothes and shoes but will argue with us to reduce the price and expect a first class service”*Saqib Awan

Due to its location, Pakistan is highly prone to natural disasters and have suffered \$18 billion in losses due to those natural disasters. Kashmir 2005 earthquake and 2010 floods are just a couple of instances where Pakistan a great financial and human loss. It is reported that nearly 3 million Pakistanis suffer from natural disasters (Khan, 2017). Participants state that in case of electricity loss or a natural disaster, they have to be prepared with a contingency plan. If something puts a stop to activities, tour arrangers have to be prepared to entertain guests.

*“We have to be prepared for anything, in any circumstance. If we do not provide worthwhile entertainment, they will not come back to us”*Salman Hassan

Information: As mentioned above, a few areas in Pakistan still do not have telecom and internet facilities and since most of the business nowadays advertise their products and services online, it can be challenging to reach those people. Even though more than half of the population cannot access the internet, well over 87 million have access to it. Information is hard to find and for foreign tourists who have no links (friends, acquaintances) have no one to guide them.

“Information gathering with regards to tourism in Pakistan can be challenging since the information on the internet is not adequate or is out of date. The tourism council has barely done anything to improve information channels. As tour operators we have to keep ourselves and our employees up-to-date on the goings of the industry as people will come to us for information. This has enabled us to network with other similar

businesses as that way circulation of information will be easier. I think the government should built proper information platforms for activities relating tourism” Salman Hassan

Participants state that the field of tourism can be lucrative financially. Profit margins are big, if a tour has been successful participants can expect to make 50,000-100,000 PKR in profits, depending on the size of the tour.

“all tour operators at some point, have been disrupted by political activities in Pakistan and have to bear the financial loss. Financial loss can be made up in upcoming tours, but the benefits of being in this industry outweigh any financial loss” Sajid Ali

6.4.1.4. Demographics:

Three of the participants interviewed reported similar demographics; 99% domestic customers and 1% foreign customers. Female and male ratio is half and half. Occupation wise a large majority of tourists are university and college students. One participant stated that their organisation arranges corporate tours and will soon branch into providing political tours. Participants stated that they have put less effort into recruiting international tourists due to complicated visa and vetting procedure, foreign tourists are required to satisfy Pakistan immigration requirement as to the reason to their visit.

“International tourists have to pass a few hurdles to get through the immigration process, whereas domestic do not. It is easier and financially feasible to organise tours for local tourists”

“I solely focus on national tourists since in the last decade the demand and interest in tourism has peaked, I believe there are two reasons for that; social media and internet have made people aware of the amazing destinations we have in Pakistan and people want to explore that. Secondly, holidays in Pakistan are considerably cheaper than international holidays where people have to show a hefty amount of bank balance to be

able to get a visa, since Pakistani passport holders can visit a handful countries visa free. Poverty is a major issue and due to low literacy rate unemployment is rife and people are always looking for cheaper ways of entertainment. With regards to international tourists, the government has made the procedure somewhat complicated, normally visa applications are processed within 2 weeks but some take months. I think complicated visa procedures put people off of visiting a country to some level. We have a big market in Pakistan with local tourists so our business thrives” Salman Hassan

Fourth participant report their demographics to be 90% international tourists and 10% local tourists. From those 90% international customers, 70% are from Malaysia and 30% from Europe. Participant states that they went into this business with the intention of bringing foreign tourists to Pakistan. Their main demographic is tourists from Malaysia, Indonesia, England and Canada. They have a strong social media presence and a large following and offer free advice to any potential tourists to the country. They cater to every gender, race, nationality and profession. This interviewee stated that, if provided with right information and documents, foreign tourists will not face any issues getting a visa to Pakistan. However, tourists will need to find the right avenue to arrange for effective help.

“Malaysia is a big market for my business, I have been to Malaysia twice to attend travel events and promote Pakistan. In my experience profit margins have been higher when dealing with foreign tourists as compared to Pakistani tourists and foreign tourists are flexible and less demanding. For a lot of reasons I decided to cater mainly to foreign tourists, I have always been bothered by how Pakistan and Pakistanis are perceived internationally so I wanted to make my contributions in changing that. Being CEO of a tourism company has given me opportunity to make positive contributions to local people in destinations, tourism industry of Pakistan and an excellent opportunity to make Pakistan a memorable travel experience for many international tourists, many of whom have already expressed interest in revisiting Pakistan to explore other gems of our country. Due to the Covid-19 pandemic, Pakistan government closed off borders in February till August, business from international tourists went quiet and during that

time I tried to focus on national tourists and started exploring that option. As soon as lockdown was over, we started offering affordable packages to locals, which kept the business going. Unfortunately our biggest market is Malaysian tourists and Malaysia has closed off their borders and restricted international holidays so we've had to change routes and explore other international markets” Saqib Awan

Conclusion

The qualitative analysis undertaken above has highlighted a myriad of issues, many tour operators still have reservations about marketing their organisations to foreign tourists. Their main concerns were the elongated visa process, which has been rectified by the government recently with the introduction of visa-on-arrival and e-visa for over 150 countries. However, there seems to be still some hesitation on part of tour operators as foreign tourists are still a rare sight in Pakistan, with exception to Gilgit Baltistan region which has accustomed itself well to the influx of foreign tourists. Gilgit Baltistan and some Northern areas, mainly due to the mountain peaks, see tourists on a regular basis as many mountaineers from all over the world visit the region to climb peaks. It can be assumed that tourism providers are concerned about the cost to them of providing security to foreign looking people, one of the interviewees expressed their dislike as they claimed some foreign tourists were being stopped and interrogated by local Police officials despite being low-key. This can put people off of visiting Pakistan as most countries across the globe do not bother people visiting the country. The statistics indicated that tourist figures were going up just before the Covid-19 pandemic, however, due to the fatal nature of the virus lockdowns were put in place to control the spread of the virus. This affected not only tourism based businesses but also local restaurants and markets suffered severe financial consequences. The economy has started to pick up and businesses have opened their gates to customers once again. The interview analysis findings indicated that the issues faced by travel providers/tour operators are more or less the same, which means there is a strong need for change on

a higher level. The demographics of participants were similar, except one of the participants invested highly in reaching out to international tourists and the others focused on national tourists. One of the main concerns highlighted in the interviews was the image of the country; the visitors who have been to Pakistan have had a completely different experience to what the media suggests visit to Pakistan would be like. However, there are many issues plaguing the tourism industry of Pakistan and minute attention is being paid to those issues. Due to corruption in government sectors, the money put aside for tourism is seldom invested in the industry. Although many highways have been built in the last 3 decades, many tourist destinations still lack proper roads and transport. Infrastructure has been an issue for many decades and continues to do so. Political issues have also led to them incurring financial losses, however, the situation seems to have calmed down since PTI government that was elected in 2018. Some interviewees believe that overall situation of security and infrastructure will change with the development of CPEC, a project between China and Pakistan to build convenient route for trade.

7. Chapter 7: Conclusion and Recommendations

7.1. Introduction:

This chapter provides the conclusion to the thesis. It discusses the conclusions made on the all the three objectives of the research. The contributions made to knowledge literature and practice have all been discussed in the chapter. The thesis makes eight (8) main recommendations and expresses the need for future research in the subject and topic area.

7.2. Conclusion

It is highly recommended that tourist providers organise recreational activities to engage tourists. A trip without recreational activities feels incomplete and therefore it is very significant that extra activities are introduced. Tourist providers should actively aid foreign tourists with visa applications, as Pakistan is a developing country and is still fairly unknown as a destination, and the visa process can create hassle sometimes.

From the analysis it is evident that people who travelled to Pakistan are of various ethnic backgrounds, and have been to Pakistan for pleasure. If tourist satisfaction is achieved, those tourists can tell their friends and family, which is essentially word-of-mouth marketing. Word-of-mouth marketing is one of the oldest and most efficient marketing tools to have existed till this day, people tend to believe real-life experiences over reviews/other marketing tools. Providing value for money is highly significant as affordable accommodation and facilities can attract tourists from all financial backgrounds, many people flock to Bali Indonesia as it is one of the cheapest exotic destinations to travel to. Bali provides tourists with excellent beaches, food, nice scenery and excellent facilities as it is an established tourist destination.

Provided there is awareness and policy on the part of stakeholders to promote the culture of tourism, tourism can easily become a multi-billion dollar industry in Pakistan. A country's image and reputation is judged on the basis of its capacity to provide basic facilities to tourists, particularly foreigners. If neighbouring countries such as India and China can make more than \$20 billion from tourism and various EU countries such as France, Switzerland, Italy, Greece and the UK can fetch several hundred billion dollars from tourism, why cannot Pakistan, a country blessed with enviable natural beauty? Recently ousted Prime Minister of Pakistan Imran Khan stated that if Switzerland can earn a hefty amount through tourism, Pakistan can also make significant steps to attract tourists. Pakistan has similar scenery, if not better, to

Switzerland and also has a very rich culture to compliment the exquisite scenery. However, it should be noted that passing such statement only will not bring about any change unless practical steps are taken to create a culture of tourism which would in turn require a change in mindset of local people, tour operators, hotels and officials attached with the ministry of tourism.

Tourism culture can include four major components, the attitudes and behaviour of those who are supposed to provide guidance and facilities to tourists. Secondly, adherence to hygiene and cleanliness at restuarants, eateries, washroom and hotels at tourist spots. Unfortunately, with a few exceptions, there is a lack iof hygiene and cleanliness, which creates a back impression for both local and foreign tourists. Third, availability of affordable accommodation and food is essential for creating a culture of toruism in Pakistan. unfortunately, currentky there are no regulations on part of concerned authorities to prevent hotel owners who take advantage of the situation and charge excessive amount from the tourists. Fourth, the absence of tourism culture in Pakistan can be attributed to the corruption and inefficiency of tourism departments in various provinces of the country who lack proper

It is true that because of the reigning pandemic since early 2020, tourist industry all over the world has suffered but such a crisis should have been used as an opportunity by formulating short- and long-term policies to train those who are related to the tourism industry. In 2020 and early 2021, tourist places in Pakistan were closed and only reopened during the summer of 2021. The rush in tourist destinations during the summer of 2021 is unprecedented which led to the shortage of accommodation and overcharging of hotel accommodation.

Pakistan is blessed with beautiful tourists as well as historical and religious sites where tourists from abroad visit in large numbers. The north of Pakistan is known for its peaks, glaciers, lakes and forests where not only homegrown tourism can flourish but millions of tourists from abroad can also be attracted. Likewise, the historical sites of Texila and Mohenjo Daro can be a big draw for foreign tourists. The deserts of Tharparkar in Sindh and Cholistan in Punjab, as well as the coast of Pakistan, particularly in Balochistan, also have the potential to attract local and foreign tourists in large numbers.

If the government and other stakeholders are interested in promoting tourist industry and homegrown tourism, they must make sure that adequate facilities are provided. Policy decisions to promote the culture of tourism must take into account three major requirements.

First, the major tourist destinations like Swat, Naran, Gilgit, Hunza and Skardu must be monitored by the respective tourist departments and ministries that tourists visiting such places are provided with best facilities at affordable prices. Acts of cheating and overcharging for accommodation and meals must be eradicated. It seems, ‘tourist mafias’ in collaboration with officials deny tourists opportunities to enjoy their holidays.

Second, it is a matter of shame that the government of Khyber-Pakhtunkhwa has utterly failed to improve tourist infrastructure including roads. For instance, Naran is a major tourist spot and tourists who visit that place make sure that they also go to the legendary lake Saiful Muluk. But, it is shocking that there is no road from Naran to that lake and tourists are left at the mercy of ‘jeep mafia’ who subvert efforts to construct a good quality road. It is unfortunate that the PTI which has been in power in K-P since 2013 has failed to deal with the ‘jeep mafia’ and construct a road to lake Saiful Muluk which can save thousands of tourists from the torture of inhuman travel through rocks and stones. If the ‘jeep mafia’ of Naran subverts the construction of road from Naran to that lake, where is the writ of the K-P government? The provincial government must provide hygienic conditions to tourists along with affordable hotels but it has been observed that unlike tall claims on the part of the PTI government, the reality on the ground is different. There is a nexus between hotel mafia and the government which results into the exploitation of tourists. The K-P government must implement its policy decision to promote local and foreign tourism instead of being involved in corruption with ‘jeep and hotel mafia’. There are other destinations in Swat and Kaghan-Naran where one can observe pathetic condition of roads and poor tourist infrastructure.

Third, if the government projects that Pakistan will earn Re1 trillion from tourism by 2025, in that case hectic efforts should be made both at federal and provincial levels to create the culture of tourism by taking measures which have been highlighted above. When there was civil war going on in Sri Lanka from 1983 till 2009 and foreign tourism

plummeted, the government encouraged local tourism which tried to bridge the gap in income from foreign tourism. Pakistan needs to promote homegrown tourism and take practical steps to provide safety, security, better hygienic, infrastructure and accommodation facilities so that both local and foreign tourists can be pulled in.

Research objectives conclusion:

1. Objective 1; to investigate the relationship between destination marketing and tourist satisfaction in context of Pakistan tourism industry.

The relationship between destination marketing and tourists satisfaction is complex. What we see on social media is seldom a true portrayal of anything. Any foreign tourists who comes to Pakistan with the expectation set by the advertisements is pleasantly surprised with the natural beauty, heritage sites, local culture and food, however, in many cases face difficulties in moving around within the country. Destination marketing is one of the best ways to reach out to target consumer, however, that is just the beginning. The experience itself is the main event, if the experience in any way is negative, the marketing of any destination fails to succeed in their mission. Although, the responses received were mainly positive, some responses did reflect a need for change in terms of infrastructure and local policies. There is however a very strong link between destination marketing and tourist satisfaction, if a destination is marketed through proper channels and somewhat realistic, it is highly likely that any tourist will leave the destination attaining satisfaction.

2. Objective 2; to investigate the current marketing practices employed by tourism providers in Pakistan.

The main source of this objective was through qualitative data in form of interviews of several tourism business owners. The main conclusion drawn from their responses is that the most common type of marketing tool is social media marketing. Social media marketing platforms such as Facebook, Instagram and in some cases Twitter have been

essential in diverting tourists to these businesses. The said businesses have also employed use of advertising on search engine; such as Google as the first platform of any exploration is by the use of search engines. The interviewees stated that another effective tool of marketing was word-of-mouth, since the current customer base of these business is predominantly local tourists from different regions of Pakistan, and although the use of internet is increasing at a rapid rate, there are some segments that are not yet on any social media platform, or use the internet at all. For such customers, word-of-mouth has been the main source of knowing about potential businesses that can cater their needs and wants. The interviewees also mentioned that, to increase their international customers, they are exploring different ways to reach out to a larger customer base. For instance, taking part in tourism related events all over the world has helped spread the potential of tourism in Pakistan. In many ways, due to the negative portrayal of Pakistan, the international news has hindered the rise in number of international tourists, and this is due to the fact that outside Pakistan people consider the whole region to be unsafe. They are not aware of the different types of tourism the country has to offer, and in most cases when Pakistan is brought about in conversations, people tend to think it consists of deserts and slums. The most effective way to advertise and encourage tourism seems to be through social media, therefore, it is essential that businesses incorporate outreach policies to get the word out.

3. To provide strategic recommendations to enhance business performance to ensure high levels of tourist satisfaction.

Considering the differences between local and foreign tourists, the most effective way to drive tourist figures is to come up with strategies to preserve the local culture, but also welcome foreign tourists with an open mind. The conservative nature of the local culture can offend people due to the fear of offending locals and therefore facing harsh consequences. Tourism providers, that includes federal and regional government bodies as well as local businesses, need to work together on building a positive image. The safest region by far is Hunza Valley and surrounding areas, and those areas consist of mountain peaks, rivers, beaches, national parks, should be the top priority of the

government. Once tourism is a constant in those regions, the government can begin to work on other regions.

7.3. Recommendations:

Pakistan's tourism industry has massive potential to become the next best tourist destination, considering plans to create employment opportunities, improvement in infrastructure, preservation of valuable local cultural heritage, build more capacity, and project a positive image of Pakistan to the outside world. Comprehensive reforms will be needed make these goals come to fruition and seize the opportunities and revenue tourism can generate for local people, and local and national economy. The recommendations provided below are general recommendations, that are aimed at local and federal government, as well as tourist businesses.

1. Tourism Vision and Implementation Mechanisms: Tourism is a constant phenomenon for people and governments. The changing nature of its forms and pace make the monitoring of structures and impact more important. The apparatus must be assembled on a vision and complementary mechanisms of command and control.

2. National Policy-Driven Plan

a. Promotion of this industry centres on the ability to understand and anticipate the emerging global trends and risks, suitably adapt policies, and accelerate sustainable models. Process and planning in this regard must remain subservient to the policy, besides providing strategic roadmap for stakeholders.

b. Tourism is a devolved subject. Organizations and officials involved in the industry often face administrative obstructions, such as the cumbersome procedure for getting no objection certificates and licenses. Issuance of unnecessary NOCs also creates problems. Failure in reaching consensus among provinces is another challenge that results into delays and dissatisfaction. The issue needs to be resolved at the state level.

3. Regulatory Regime: A stringent regime of checks and balances is required. All steps, ranging from the construction of infrastructure to provision of services, should be taken according to the government's guidelines. A free-for-all attitude ruins the rule of

law and obligations. Hence, illegal construction should be checked. Only registered entities should be authorized business and unregistered should be penalized and banned.

4. Training:

a. Tourism involves glitz and flare and can be deprived of dynamism once dispensed within red tapes. However, most of the affairs are managed by the administrative machinery of the state. Public sector officials and members of foreign services therefore must be trained, through special cadres, to promote Pakistan's tourism.

b. Tourism as an academic and vocational training subject has to be developed further and suitably upgraded. Vocational training institutes and study of tourism appropriately offered at undergraduate and graduate levels as a full-fledged course of study at Pakistani universities and recognized by the Higher Education Commission as a priority area of study and research will help build national capacity and development human resources required for multi-dimensional realization of Pakistan's tourism potential.

6. Marketing Concept: Tourism is sometimes more about the way it is promoted and brought to the market rather than understood as a bureaucratic subject. If kept too close to the administrative ways of doing things, the sector may lose its natural vitality. The individuals and organizations linked with tourism thus need to know the dynamics of the marketing concept – a philosophy focussed on knowing and satisfying the needs of customers. It is about the creation of tourism products, i.e. services and commodities, and selling them. Incorporation of the market mix technique to this setup is an additional value for profit maximization. This mix comprises the product, price, place and promotion. As the number of leisure and business tourists increase, it will be important to maintain a holistic approach for planning and competitiveness. internet, and normal law and order situation.

- **Effective Marketing and Promotion of Tourism:** Most of the countries have adopted an integrated approach for the marketing and promotion of tourism based on proper market research and data collection about the potential tourists, their preferences and spending power etc. Diversified products have been developed for

various segments of tourists and targeted marketing activities have been undertaken to attract maximum number of tourists. For example the marketing campaign of India Tourism under the brand name of “Incredible India” has shown great results in the past few years. There is need to develop a brand name for Pakistan as a tourist destination that that brand name should be promoted through joint marketing strategy by effectively pooling in available resources. The public sector organizations should participate very effectively along with their private sector players in international tourism markets such as London Tourism Mart, ITB Berlin and Beijing Tourism Mart which attract buyers and sellers from all over the world in large number. Role of print and electronic media to promote the soft image is very important. Exposure trips of media persons, travel writers and TV channel teams should be organized regular basis to get positive projection on media. Private sector should also be encouraged to launch an exclusive TV channel on travel and tourism. A joint task force should be constituted to provide synergy between private and public sectors in marketing and to formulate innovative marketing strategy to promote Pakistan as an all season tourist destination.

7. Financing Strategy: Promoting tourism through incentives, such as micro-financing, loans, industry linkages with fresh ideas, and local champ contests, will attract more talent into the field. The strategy may also invite sponsorships through crowd funding and angel investment.

8. Data-analytics: Any management strategy runs best through information gathering and data analysis. Tourism planners; structured and stratified monitoring and opinion surveys; and qualitative and quantitative data research and analysis are a few ways to regulate the sector; identify target markets; conduct market research; and determine and develop factors of demand and supply.

9. Preservation of Cultural Heritage: Sociocultural and environmental impacts of tourism policies and activities should be regularly evaluated, though they cannot be easily quantified. Special consideration needs to be given to the preservation of cultural heritage and natural assets against the increase in visits. Regular monitoring and expert supervision will be helpful to detect and address problems.

10. Uplift of Transportation Sector: Tourism entails enormous activity and pressure on infrastructure and services can cast a negative impact on the receivers and visitors. This problem of “overtourism”¹ requires proper management. Infrastructure is not only about roads, hotels and services. It is also related to air traffic and energy and education sectors. The ability to attract tourists also demands world class hospitality and transportation services, especially aviation, and arrangements for inland travel. A lot of work needs to be done to ensure facilitation in this regard.

11. Religious Tourism: Pakistan can become a “special interest destination” due to a natural advantage in adventure, cultural and religious tourism. Old events like the Basant festival, Cattle shows, and other traditional events should also be restored. Another significant measure will be to label the minorities’ religious sites as sacred areas and not public places. The sanctity of these places will thus be safeguarded for pilgrims besides being a tourist attraction.

12. Societal Renewal: The development of tourism industry is not achieved by the state’s policies only. It relies more on the readiness of its people to nurture a value-based culture and harmony. There is a need of a societal renewal to create a tourist-friendly environment in Pakistan based, among other things on, on clean surroundings, easy travel, unimpeded multimodal transport and digital connectivity, a relaxed and open social environment, easy access to affordable accommodation, high-speed

. Diversification of Tourism Products: In addition to the cultural tourism and adventure which Pakistan has been promoting through its promotional campaign, there is need to develop other tourism products such as wellness tourism, medical tourism, sports tourism, rural tourism, ecotourism and spiritual tourism. The government should adopt a very strategic approach for the development for these tourism sources, by creating guidelines for each type of tourism product, along with employment schemes for potential jobseekers in each sector.

Importance to Domestic Tourism: Although attracting more and more foreign tourists is always the preference of all the countries due to its potential to generate much needed foreign exchange but the importance of domestic tourist market cannot ignored. Therefore, the focus

government should be on the development of infrastructure and facilities to serve the much larger domestic tourist market.

Attracting Religious Tourist from Abroad: There is need to pay special attention to attract foreign religious tourists from abroad as we have many holy sites belonging to different religions such as Hinduism, Sikhism, Buddhism and Islam. Necessary infrastructure should be developed to facilitate such tourists to practice their religious rituals and prayers at the sites of religious importance. 9.14 Development of printed and electronic information material on tourist site: Development of attractive printed and electronic information material on tourist site in multiple languages should also be the main focus of tourism promotion organizations.

Use of IT in Tourism: Most of the countries are using Information Technology (IT) very effectively to promote tourism. Online visa, online hotel booking, airline and transport booking and other services are now common features of most of the web portals of these countries. The tourism websites should provide a one stop solution to interested visitors to get all the information and facilitation they are required before leaving their home.

7.4. Limitation of study

As Pakistan is an emerging tourism hub, the information available through various channels is limited. One of the main limitations faced while conducting this research were the lack of proper statistics available. As the main part of this research was conducted during the covid-19 pandemic, it was complicated to reach out to tourism providers due to closures and restrictions. However, despite all restrictions faced during the study, the research conducted can be used as a guiding point for future researches and big-scale researches needing to be carried out by professional organisations.

7.5. Conclusion

A coordinated management of tourism sector is crucial for its development. It is with the help of a shared vision that nations walk the road to stability and progress. Synergy between relevant offices and stakeholders, between public and private sectors, and between state, market, communities, and civil society is, therefore, crucial for improving the tourism sector of Pakistan. The progress of tourism in Pakistan will be a

process of shaping the future of mobility and hospitality by bringing together the public and private sectors to ensure that these measures meet demands. Having employed the best means and having taken requisite steps all roads should of necessity go towards sustainable and inclusive tourism development in Pakistan.

7.6. Contributions and Need For Further Research

In this modern, competitive and complex world of business, studies conducted in the past are easily superseded and replaced by more modern and hi-tech research. Consequently, research conducted cannot be deemed remain relevant and influential forever as new ones are poised to bring new ideas, facts and data that are huge improvements of them. This study, therefore, expresses the need for future research to be conducted in this particular area of business,. This research has contributed to knowledge through the shedding of light on how marketing is carried out in Pakistan's tourism industry. There is ample empirical literature and information on the tourism marketing practices in the Western countries such as Europe and the Americas. However, information and data on those of Pakistan have been scanty, if non non-existent. This research has provided enough data on the current practices of Pakistan's tourism industry thereby contributing to literature. This research contributes a lot in guiding tourism providers to reap maximum profits for their businesses in the future.

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9. Appendices

9.1. Research Questionnaire

Cover Letter

Dear Respondent,

My name is Sara, and I am of Pakistani origin. I am conducting this research for my doctoral degree; this research aims to analyse the current marketing trends employed by the tourism industry in Pakistan. As someone who has travelled to Pakistan, you may be aware of the beautiful landscape and awe-inspiring scenery as well as many UNESCO recognized world heritage sites in Pakistan that have yet to be discovered by many international tourists. Due to unfortunate events in the past the tourism industry in Pakistan suffered a great deal and has been in decline for over a decade now. As political and security situation improves, the industry is seeing a steady yet slow rise in tourist figures, however many foreign tourists are still unaware of the improvements

and progress that has been made and are wary of coming to Pakistan. This research intends to identify the inadequacies in marketing practices and how that affects the tourism figures. All responses will be kept confidential. Thank you very much for your participation.

Yours sincerely,
Sara

Research questionnaire

Instructions to complete the Questionnaire:

- i) Please fill all the questions and do not leave anything blank.*
- ii) The questions are in two general formats. (Appendix A & B)*
- iii) One format requires to circle a choice, for example,*

Married	<input checked="" type="radio"/> Single	others
---------	---	--------

- iv) The second format is based on different scales to select the option, for example:*

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree			
1	2	3	4	5			
1- Honesty is the best policy.			1	2	3	4	5

If you are strongly agreed with the above statement you would circle the number 5.

The following information is concerned about your position and other personal information. Please encircle the appropriate one.

- | | | | | | |
|--|----------------------|----------|--------------------------------|----------------------|------------|
| 1. Gender | Male | Female | Others | | |
| 2. Age (in years) | 21 – 25 | 26 – 30 | 31 – 35 | 36 - 40 | 40 & above |
| 3. Residence | KP | Punjab | Baluchistan | Sindh | Abroad |
| 4. Marital Status | Married | Single | Others | | |
| 5. Ethnicity | Asian
(Pakistani) | White | Middle East | American | Others |
| 6. Purpose of Travel | Leisure/Relax | Business | Visiting Friends
and Family | Others | |
| 7. Frequency of
Travel (Per year) | Once | Twice | Thrice | 4 times and
above | |
| 8. I have visited Pakistan | Yes | No | | | |

Strongly Disagree	SD	1
Disagree	D	2
Neutral	N	3
Agree	A	4
Strongly Agree	SA	5

Country Image		SD	D	N	A	SA
CI1	Pakistan is a safe country to travel.	1	2	3	4	5
CI2	My safety is not compromised as I move around in Pakistan.	1	2	3	4	5
CI3	The tourist's safety is guaranteed in Pakistan.	1	2	3	4	5
CI4	The political regime supports for the safety of the tourists.	1	2	3	4	5
CI5	The government invests in attracting and protecting the tourists in Pakistan.	1	2	3	4	5
Friendliness of Local People		SD	D	N	A	SA
FLP1	Local people are very hospitable towards the tourists.	1	2	3	4	5
FLP2	Local shopkeepers are kind towards the tourists.	1	2	3	4	5
FLP3	The staff at hotels and restaurants is friendly and welcoming towards the tourists.	1	2	3	4	5
FLP4	The residents are willing to aid the tourists.	1	2	3	4	5
Recreational Activities		SD	D	N	A	SA
RA1	There are variety of recreational activities available at the tourist's destinations.	1	2	3	4	5
RA2	The recreational activities are budget friendly for the tourists.	1	2	3	4	5
RA3	The recreational activities are relevant for the tourists.	1	2	3	4	5

RA4	The recreational activities are relevant to the leisure of the tourists.	1	2	3	4	5
RA5	The recreational activities are satisfactory for the tourists.	1	2	3	4	5
RA6	There are sports facilities and activities available for the tourists.	1	2	3	4	5
Feeling of Personal Safety		SD	D	N	A	SA
FPS1	I feel safe and secure while I travel different tourists' destinations in Pakistan.	1	2	3	4	5
FPS2	I am satisfied that I am not discriminated against as a tourist.	1	2	3	4	5
FPS3	The activities at tourist destinations are safe and risk free for the tourists.	1	2	3	4	5
FPS4	I feel that my accommodation is reliable and room security is ensured.	1	2	3	4	5
FPS5	I believe that the local transport is safe.	1	2	3	4	5
FPS6	Touring different destinations in daytime is safe and secure.	1	2	3	4	5
FPS7	Walking around streets and nightlife is safe and secure.	1	2	3	4	5
Easy Access to Information		SD	D	N	A	SA
EAI1	Accurate and honest information related to tourist destinations and tour operators is available on websites and social media.	1	2	3	4	5
EAI2	I have easy and quick access to the different tour operators in Pakistan.	1	2	3	4	5
EAI3	The tourist's destinations venues clearly state the services offered.	1	2	3	4	5
EAI4	The tour operators provide accurate and reliable information.					
Presentation of Local Culture		SD	D	N	A	SA
PLC1	There are a lot of cultural attractions in Pakistan.	1	2	3	4	5
PLC2	There are numerous interesting cultural activities for the tourists.	1	2	3	4	5
PLC3	Local customs are very attractive, and it is nice to learn them.	1	2	3	4	5

PLC4	There is variety of food options available for the tourists.	1	2	3	4	5
PLC5	It is easy to communicate with the local people.	1	2	3	4	5
PLC6	The language barriers are very minimal for the tourists as information is presented in multi languages at the tourist's spots.	1	2	3	4	5
Value for Money		SD	D	N	A	SA
VM1	The tour operators charge justifiable money for the services.	1	2	3	4	5
VM2	The level of services at accommodation is worth the money charged.	1	2	3	4	5
VM3	The transport cost is affordable for the tourists.	1	2	3	4	5
VM4	The ticket pricing at tourist destination is affordable.	1	2	3	4	5
VM5	The local food items are affordable as far as the quality of the food is concerned.	1	2	3	4	5
VM6	Different facilities offered at the tourists' venues are worth the money.	1	2	3	4	5
VM7	The pricing level of the souvenirs and gifts is good.	1	2	3	4	5
VM8	Overall value for money is justified for the tourists.	1	2	3	4	5
Positive Destination Experience		SD	D	N	A	SA
PDE1	This tourist destination respects the natural environment.	1	2	3	4	5
PDE2	The destinations can be easily reached.	1	2	3	4	5
PDE3	There is availability of parking spaces at the tourist destinations.	1	2	3	4	5
PDE4	The quality of facilities at the destinations is good.	1	2	3	4	5
PDE5	The directional signs at the highways are accurate for the tourists.	1	2	3	4	5
PDE6	The tourist destinations are neat and clean.	1	2	3	4	5

PDE7	The climatic conditions are good at the tourist's destinations.	1	2	3	4	5
PDE8	There is diversity of cultural/historical attractions.	1	2	3	4	5
Tourist Satisfaction		1	2	3	4	5
TS1	Overall, staying in the tourist destination has been very valuable to me.	1	2	3	4	5
TS2	I have gained a lot of new knowledge and experiences in the tourist destination.	1	2	3	4	5
TS3	I am pleased that I chose Pakistan for my holiday.	1	2	3	4	5
TS4	I am satisfied with my tour to different places in Pakistan.	1	2	3	4	5
TS5	I highly recommend visiting Pakistan and explore it.	1	2	3	4	5

9.2. Consent Form

CONSENT FORM

Title of Project:

An investigation of the impact of destination marketing on tourist satisfaction: A case of Pakistan tourism industry.

Name of Researcher: **Sara Zulfiqar**

Please initial all boxes

1. I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.

2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason.
3. I understand that relevant sections of my interview notes and data collected during the study, may be looked at by individuals from **the University of the West of the Scotland**, where it is relevant to my taking part in this research. I give permission for these individuals to have access to my records.
4. I agree to my employer being informed of my participation in the study.
5. I understand the data you are collecting from me, will only be used in UWS for academic purpose. But if you need to disclose outside the UWS you need to take my permission.

Name of Participant Date Signature

Name of Person taking consent. Date Signature

Deosai National Park

Hunza Valley

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Nanga Parbat

Hingol National Park

Nankana Sahib Gurdwara

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